

Exploring the Value of Graduate Apprenticeships from a Learner Perspective

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Abstract

Emerging as a policy response to skills shortages, graduate apprenticeships offer a distinct educational model that integrates a degree with workplace practice. Yet their academic-professional positioning means their legitimacy is contested, shaped by longstanding hierarchies of esteem and the competing agendas of universities, employers and policymakers. Although they are often presented as mutually beneficial, persistent challenges around curriculum relevance, employer engagement and retention rates raise questions about the value these programmes offer to apprentices – a group whose voices remain comparatively underrepresented in the literature.

The thesis addresses this gap by examining how apprentices experience value within the tripartite structure of university, workplace and their own agency. Drawing on semi-structured interviews, an open-ended questionnaire and an extended review of secondary data, this qualitative study explores four graduate apprenticeship programmes at a Scottish post-92 university. Based on the accounts of learners and university staff, the findings show that value is relational, defined by how a programme contributes to an individual's goals. Apprentices look beyond the credential to the quality of learning and the extent to which it enables authentic application in practice. These experiences are shaped by structural conditions, including gaps in support and a misalignment between curricula and workplace realities. Although apprentices demonstrate inherent motivation, the transformative potential of the programme is limited when they must navigate their learning without guidance, or when academic content fails to reflect their practice. A pedagogy of scaffolded autonomy is therefore proposed, a developmental trajectory that draws on the principles of andragogy and heutagogy to nurture self-direction through guided problematising, structured reflection and real-world application of learning.

The principal contribution is the Tripartite Value Model, a conceptual framework that synthesises the structural, relational and pedagogical dimensions of apprenticeships that shape the overall learning experience. In addition to offering practical implications for programme design, the model advances wider understanding of how value is negotiated within graduate apprenticeships.

Declaration

I confirm that this thesis is my own work and has not been submitted, in whole or in part, for any other comparable academic award.

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Abbreviations

AAG	Apprenticeship Approvals Group
FA	Foundation Apprentice; Foundation Apprenticeship
FE	Further Education
GA	Graduate Apprentice; Graduate Apprenticeship
HEFCE	Higher Education Funding Council for England
HE/HEI	Higher Education/Higher Education Institution
HESA	Higher Education Statistical Authority
MA	Modern Apprentice; Modern Apprenticeship
OfS	Office for Students
QAA	Quality Assurance Agency
REF	Research Excellence Framework
RPL	Recognition of Prior Learning
SAAB	Scottish Apprenticeship Advisory Board
SAAS	Student Awards Agency Scotland
SCQF	Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework
SDS	Skills Development Scotland
SFC	Scottish Funding Council
SQA	Scottish Qualifications Authority
SVQ	Scottish Vocational Qualification
TEF	Teaching Excellence Framework
TQEF	Tertiary Quality Enhancement Framework
VLE	Virtual Learning Environment
WBL	Work-Based Learning
YTS	Youth Training Scheme

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Research Rationale

Launched in 2017 to address skills shortages in key sectors, graduate apprenticeships are a relatively new addition to higher education in Scotland. This apprenticeship model straddles academia and practice, offering a distinctive hybrid learning environment that challenges the hegemony of how and where degrees are delivered. However, this reimagining of work-based learning has also taken place against a backdrop of growing tensions across higher education, leaving the scheme vulnerable to wider sectoral pressures that have shaped undergraduate curricula for decades. Furthermore, their positioning in universities sees graduate apprenticeships enter a hierarchy of esteem that has long favoured academic pursuits over vocational, which colours perceptions of the scheme's legitimacy both inside and outside of academia.

These programmes operate in a complex landscape of competing expectations and are often framed in both policy and academic discourse as mutually beneficial for all stakeholders. Yet previous research highlights persistent challenges with curriculum relevance, employer engagement, and learner support. This raises questions around value in graduate apprenticeships, specifically how it is defined and for whom it is intended. While the perspectives of universities and employers have been explored thoroughly, the learner voice has historically been less prominent in scholarship, despite their learning outcomes ultimately serving as the measure of apprenticeship success. This thesis therefore emphasises the importance of understanding how apprentices derive value within this dynamic. Drawing on critical examination of four programmes through the lens of learners' experiences, this study also presents the Tripartite Value Model as a conceptual framework for understanding how value is constructed in graduate apprenticeships.

1.2 Research Objectives

This study seeks to understand how learners derive value in graduate apprenticeship programmes. To address this central aim, the research is structured around six questions.

Principal Research Question:

- How do learners define the value of graduate apprenticeships?

Subsidiary Research Questions:

- How do stakeholder dynamics shape programme design and delivery?
- How do apprentices navigate competing stakeholder expectations?
- How do programmes emphasise experiential learning?
- How do apprentices reconcile learning and practice?
- How do apprentices articulate programme value in relation to their goals?

By carefully examining these distinct elements, the qualitative data builds a rich, multi-dimensional overview of graduate apprenticeship provision at the case study university. This, in turn, illustrates the complex and layered nature of value by highlighting the variables that shape its construction.

1.3 Thesis Structure

An extended literature review is presented across chapters two, three and four, which forms the contextual foundation of this study. The decision to conduct such a detailed review of literature and policy was informed by the inherently pluralistic nature of graduate apprenticeships, which have been established with the implicit expectation of addressing increasingly divergent stakeholder needs. In addition, the scheme has been subject to a number of revisions since its launch and ongoing structural uncertainty has raised questions around its long-term sustainability. These tensions highlighted the importance of critically interrogating graduate apprenticeships from multiple perspectives to establish a panoramic overview of their context.

Chapter two introduces graduate apprenticeships and provides an overview of the Scottish skills landscape, outlining the structure and strategic aims of the scheme against a backdrop of complex policy and stakeholder dynamics. The origins of the academic-vocational dichotomy are also examined, focusing on negative perceptions of vocational pathways and the potential implications for contemporary provision. This chapter traces the history of apprenticeships and considers how the updated model can avoid the pitfalls of previous work-based learning initiatives. Next, **chapter three** focuses on the higher education landscape to establish the institutional context of apprenticeships. It explores the university's evolving role in society and how this is shaped by an enduring reputational hierarchy. It also considers growing sectoral pressures and how these influence institutional decision-making. **Chapter four** then interrogates learning as a concept, a process, a product, and a philosophy. Drawing on the work of educational theorists including Marton and Säljö (1976), Kolb (1984) and Bonwell and Eisen (1991), the chapter focuses on how individuals learn within apprenticeships.

Next, **chapter five** unpacks the research methodology and philosophical perspectives underpinning the study. This chapter also introduces the case study context, outlines the data collection and analysis process, and transparently documents challenges encountered. Limitations of the research methods are acknowledged, and the reliability of the findings is evaluated. Finally, ethical research practices, reflexivity and researcher positionality are given due consideration.

The findings are then presented across four chapters. First, **chapter six** offers a detailed description of learners' experiences, while **chapter seven** focuses on the perspectives of staff at the university. A critical discussion of the findings is provided in **chapter eight**, which is structured around the five subsidiary questions at the heart of the study before addressing the central question of how graduate apprentices define value. **Chapter nine** then synthesises the empirical findings with key pedagogical literature to illustrate how the structural conditions of apprenticeships shape value construction.

Finally, **chapter ten** lays out the conclusions of the study, with a number of recommendations and implications presented. Both the novel contribution and limitations are discussed, and areas for future study are identified.

1.4 Significance of the Study

Although graduate apprenticeships continue to evolve and expand, relatively little is known about how apprentices themselves define their value. This study therefore presents one of the first empirical accounts of how this is articulated by graduate apprentices. By foregrounding their lived experiences, this study adds a new perspective to scholarly discourse, which has historically focused on university and employer needs. It also advances ongoing discussion by challenging assumptions that graduate apprenticeships present equal value to all stakeholders. In addition, the findings complement existing literature (Brown and Souto-Otero, 2020; Smith, Henderson and Mapletoft, 2023) by advocating for greater negotiation of learning outcomes and a more nuanced definition of academic success. The most significant contribution of the study is its introduction of the Tripartite Value Model, a conceptual framework that illustrates the structural, relational and pedagogical elements of apprenticeships that shape the learning experience. In addition to providing practical guidance for programme design, the model also highlights how value is negotiated within the tripartite structure and supports the study's principal aim of enhancing wider understanding of the apprenticeship learning experience.

Chapter 2: Apprenticeships and Work-Based Learning

When education is positioned so centrally in public and policy discourse as the solution to economic problems, education is blamed when, inevitably, the economic problems do not go away.

– Allais (2014)

2.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter introduces graduate apprenticeships, outlining their origins, structure and strategic aims in the wider context of Scotland's rapidly evolving skills landscape. The roles of key stakeholders are also discussed, considering the interplay between them and how this affects the development and administration of apprenticeship provision. The chapter also examines the strategic positioning of work-based learning in higher education. Trends are identified in areas such as learner demographics and socio-economic contexts, allowing a comparison of the scheme's performance against policy aims of widening access. This chapter provides an overview of the model's potential in terms of academic legitimacy, as well as institutional and political threats to long-term viability.

2.2 Overview and Aims of the Scheme

2.2.1 Introducing Graduate Apprenticeships

In 2015, the UK Government introduced degree apprenticeships in England to address a recruitment crisis and widening skills gaps in key sectors of industry. The Scottish Government, holding devolved powers over education policy, then launched the graduate apprenticeship scheme in 2017 following a successful pilot the previous year. Yet the issue of skills shortages in the labour market is not new, especially in the context of university graduates joining the workforce. Employers have long expressed frustrations around graduate employability, pointing out that additional training is often required to address a lack of soft skills and contextual understanding (Bacon, Benton and Gruneberg, 1979; Little and Brennan, 1996; Clarke, 2018). This misalignment between skills and organisational needs was then compounded by a widespread reduction in workforce development starting in the early 2000s (Green *et al.*, 2013), which went unaddressed for a number of years.

In recent years, rapid technological advancement has given rise to the fourth industrial revolution, or Industry 4.0, which has seen growing digitalisation and automation (Taylor-Smith *et al.*, 2019). Due to the increasingly central role of technology in industry, skills gaps are widening and organisations are facing prolonged recruitment challenges. In many cases, employers are struggling to recruit individuals

with the skills to carry out even entry-level roles (The Open University, 2021). However, the effects of this are not limited to new hires; the Scottish Government (2022) estimates that 80% of the individuals who will make up the Scottish workforce in 2030 are currently in, or are actively seeking, employment. Independent research organisations such as The Edge Foundation (2020) and PwC (2024) also caution that a significant number of current UK employees are at high risk of displacement due to increasing automation. This highlights an urgent need for training; where organisations may have previously focused recruitment efforts on new graduates, evolving sector needs demand a parallel upskilling of the existing workforce to avoid skill stagnation.

While graduate employability is not a new concern, Industry 4.0 has intensified the need for higher education that is responsive to industry needs and adequately prepares graduates for the realities of navigating shifting workplace priorities (Penprase, 2018; The Edge Foundation, 2018). This prompted the development of degree apprenticeships, which updated the traditional apprenticeship model by extending it into universities (Taylor-Smith *et al.*, 2019), offering individuals the opportunity to obtain a degree in sectors most impacted by skills shortages (gov.uk, 2015a; Skills England, 2025). Scotland echoed this by introducing the graduate apprenticeship scheme, which this chapter explores from a strategy and policy perspective.

2.2.2 Strategic Aims of the Scheme

The establishment of graduate apprenticeships was part of a UK-wide degree apprenticeship agenda developed in response to growing concerns around widening skills gaps, with the aim of producing workplace-ready graduates whose skills matched the immediate needs of employers (Lambert, 2016). At its inception, the graduate apprenticeship scheme was viewed as an innovative approach to higher education; it offers a debt-free means of obtaining a degree that blends an academic curriculum with practical workplace experience in a model presented to education providers as "uncharted territory" (Skills Development Scotland, 2016a). Employer input is framed as the cornerstone of the model, with several bodies within the skills system (introduced in section 2.3) emphasising employer consultation to ensure maximum relevance and responsiveness to sector needs (The Scottish Parliament, 2021). In addition to their aim of embedding sector-specific skills, the collaborative element of framework development was introduced to address a longstanding misalignment of employer expectations and traditional graduate competencies (Barr and Parkinson, 2019). It seems they are delivering against this aim, as Barr and Nabi (2022) suggest that the scheme has the potential to reduce the "employability skills deficit" seen in traditional graduates.

Over the past decade, apprenticeships have established themselves as a central element of the skills agenda, focusing on the needs of sectors like digital technologies, engineering, and health and social care, where skill shortages are most acute (Skills Development Scotland, 2023; Skills England, 2025). As illustrated in Table 2.2 (p.21), graduate apprenticeships have steadily expanded into new sectors since the scheme's launch, which implies growing industry recognition of its strategic relevance and perceived value. It also suggests that graduate apprenticeships are viewed as a credible mechanism for development in areas facing critical skills shortages. However, education providers have called for a more streamlined process for the adoption of new programmes; Jackson (2025) suggests that the current procedure is a barrier for many universities due to its "frustrating" complexity. This has been acknowledged by the Minister for Higher and Further Education, who described "imminent" changes:

I recognise the strong demand now for the expansion of graduate apprenticeships and the need to make the development process faster and simpler. The government will therefore work at pace to implement changes to how frameworks are developed, from assessing demand to shaping content. (The Scottish Parliament, 2025, 04:15)

2.3 The Scottish Skills System

2.3.1 Skills Development Scotland

Reeve and Gallacher (2022, p. 150) describe Scottish apprenticeship provision as governed by a "skills system" – a constellation of agencies working toward the common goal of advancing national work-based learning priorities. At the centre of this system is the national skills agency, Skills Development Scotland (SDS), who work with schools, career services and industry to equip the workforce with the "right skills at the right time" to drive sustainable economic growth (Skills Development Scotland, no date). Work-based learning, the central tenet of the national upskilling agenda, is delivered at three levels: foundation apprenticeships, completed by senior secondary school pupils in place of a standard curriculum class; modern apprenticeships, which provide recognised qualifications in a range of areas and sectors; and graduate apprenticeships, representing the first Scottish apprenticeship pathway to offer a degree. The full suite of Scottish apprenticeships is outlined below in Table 2.1.

	Foundation	Modern	Graduate
Apprentice Age	16 - 18	16+	16+
Principal Setting	Secondary School	Workplace	Workplace
Frameworks	15	104	15
Duration (Years)	1 - 2	1 - 4	3 - 4
Education Provider	College/Private	College/Private	University
SCQF Award Level	6	4 - 11	9 - 11

Table 2.1: Overview of Scottish apprenticeship schemes

Source: (apprenticeships.scot, no date b)

As part of administering work-based learning, SDS works in consultation with employers, regulatory bodies and educational institutions to facilitate the design of frameworks that reflect occupational standards and sector-specific competencies. The OECD has highlighted their central role in enhancing Scottish apprenticeship offerings, emphasising the positive impact on changing labour needs and their commitment to lifelong learning (OECD, 2020).

2.3.2 Graduate Apprenticeship Frameworks

In this context, a framework refers to the formal brief that outlines the essential components of a specific graduate apprenticeship. Frameworks stipulate the programme title, SCQF award level (Table 2.3, p.23) and key areas of assessment, as well as outlining the expectations placed on the learner, employer and education provider. In addition, the learning outcomes for the programme are specified, although they do not prescribe specific modules or the mode of delivery. Each framework has been developed in consultation with industry to ensure these outcomes align with present and future sector needs. There are currently 15 frameworks, as shown below in Table 2.2.

Programme Name and SCQF Award Level	Launched	2022/23 Intake
Accounting L10	2019	4.8%
Business Management L10	2018	30.6%
Business Management: Business Analysis L10	2024	-
Business Management: Project Management L10	2024	-
Civil Engineering L10	2017	11.0%
Construction and the Built Environment L10	2018	8.9%
Cyber Security L10/11	2017	8.7%
Data Science L10	2018	5.0%
Early Learning and Childcare L9	2019	4.4%
Engineering: Design and Manufacture L10	2017	10.4%
Engineering: Instrumentation, Measurement and Control L10	2018	1.8%
IT: Management for Business L10	2017	3.1%
IT: Software Development L10	2017	11.3%
Operating Department Practice L9	2024	-
Social Work (pilot scheme) L10	2025	-

Table 2.2: Graduate apprenticeship frameworks
Source: Skills Development Scotland (2024b, 2025)

2.3.3 Framework Development Bodies

Two central figures in the development of new frameworks are the Scottish Apprenticeship Advisory Board (SAAB) and Apprenticeship Approvals Group (AAG). SAAB is an independent and employer-led body, acting as the "voice of industry" (The Scottish Parliament, 2021). Positioned between SDS, the Scottish Government and a number of industry-focused actors, SAAB has responsibility for end-to-end oversight of new apprenticeships and providing strategic guidance on policy, standards and structure.

A sub-group of SAAB, the AAG is responsible for the relevance and quality of apprenticeships. AAG is similarly employer-led but takes a more operational role in framework development, with a focus on ensuring that activities and learning outcomes are aligned to current and future sector needs. Figure 2.1 illustrates their positions within the advisory group structure.

Figure 2.1: Scottish apprenticeship advisory group structure

Source: Adapted from Skills Development Scotland (2022c)

2.3.4 Funding Bodies

The Scottish Funding Council (SFC) is a non-departmental branch of the Scottish Government. Their primary responsibility is distributing public funds across colleges and universities, which is used to meet the costs associated with delivering further and higher education. SFC works in partnership with various agencies, including supporting SDS in the expansion of graduate apprenticeship provision and the Higher Education Statistical Authority (HESA) in reporting sector data. SFC also allocates funding to the Student Awards Agency Scotland (SAAS) to cover the tuition fees of Scottish-domiciled students. Following a procedural change in 2021, graduate apprenticeship tuition fee grants are now awarded by SAAS, mirroring the process of full-time degree programmes.

2.3.5 Quality Assurance Bodies

The quality standards embedded within apprenticeship frameworks are set by the Standards and Frameworks Group (SFG), another branch of SAAB. Although universities are bound to these when designing a programme, the institution has overall responsibility for the quality of its apprenticeship curricula (Quality Assurance Agency, 2018; Skills Development Scotland, 2019a). However, there are several mechanisms and agencies indirectly involved in quality assurance. First, the Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework (SCQF) is the nationally recognised framework that enables standardisation and comparison of education provision between providers. The framework is shown in Table 2.3.

SCQF Level	Scottish Qualifications Authority*	Higher Education Institutions	Apprenticeships and Vocational Awards
12		Doctoral Degree	
11		Master's Degree	GA; SVQ 5
10		Honours Degree	GA
9		Ordinary Degree	GA; SVQ 4
8	HND	Diploma of HE	SVQ 4
7	HNC	Certificate of HE	MA; SVQ 3
6	Higher		FA; MA; SVQ 3
5	National 5		SVQ 2
4	National 4		SVQ1
3	National 3		
2	National 2		
1	National 1		

Table 2.3: Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework

Source: Adapted from SCQF (2024)

*The SQA is expected to be replaced by Qualifications Scotland in February 2026

The SCQF level of each graduate apprenticeship is stipulated by SDS within the framework, allowing universities to design academic content aligned to the recognised standard.

In addition, the Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAA) plays a central role in steering quality enhancement activities across the higher education sector. As an independent expert in this field, QAA was one of the agencies responsible for the Tertiary Education Quality Framework (TEQF). Since 2008, QAA Scotland has also published a number of resources and enhancement initiatives that focus on emphasising graduate attributes and employability in degree programmes, objectives closely aligned with the efforts of graduate apprenticeships.

2.4 The Graduate Apprenticeship Model

Prior to its launch in 2017, the graduate apprenticeship scheme was presented as a disruptive model of higher education, which SDS (2016a) described as "uncharted territory". Certainly, it represents a departure from previous iterations of work-based learning initiatives. Traditionally associated with a single trade or craft, apprenticeships and work-based learning programmes in the UK have historically targeted school leavers and young adults, providing qualifications at SCQF levels 4-7. In contrast, graduate apprenticeships are delivered by universities and offer a funded opportunity to complete a degree tailored to each learner's job role. In previous work-based learning schemes, the training by further education providers was often viewed as supplementary to the learner's employment. In this case, the positioning of graduate apprenticeships within universities lends an academic legitimacy that was absent from previous iterations. Their positioning within higher education also challenges the longstanding debate of education versus training, which is explored in section 2.6.1.

A graduate apprentice occupies a dual role as both a full-time employee and student. Programmes are considered full-time undergraduate degrees and, as such, require learners to complete the standard 120 academic credits per year. The scheme's eligibility criteria stipulate that apprentices must be Scottish residents and employed for a minimum of 21 hours per week by an organisation with at least one base in Scotland. The model emphasises an 80/20 split, whereby 80% of the week is spent in the workplace, with the remaining 20% ringfenced for academic activities. However, frameworks do not stipulate how this should be delivered, meaning universities retain flexibility around how and when apprentices engage. The 80/20 format is also non-negotiable; "sandwich" models (wherein learners alternate between blocks of time with the university and their workplace) are not considered to be in the spirit of the scheme. The integration of work and learning at the core of graduate apprenticeships reflects the principles of Lave and Wenger's (1991) situated learning theory, which is discussed in section 2.6.2.

This model bears a striking resemblance to work-based learning programmes developed at Middlesex University, an institution whose innovative contributions to this field were recognised with a Queen's Anniversary Prize in 1996. Their emphasis on tripartite collaboration in work-based higher education (Garnett, 2005) arguably laid the foundation for contemporary frameworks.

2.4.1 Work-Based Learning: What's in a Name?

Learning in a professional setting is by no means a new phenomenon but renewed attention in recent years has seen a rise in the use (and conflation) of certain terms in the lexicon. Work-based, workplace,

workplace-based and work-integrated are just a few examples of the terms used interchangeably by some (Smith-Ruig, 2014; Morris, 2018) in reference to any programme of learning which involves time spent in a place of work. Yet, workplace learning largely refers to interactions, knowledge exchange and embedded processes in a single environment, leading to individual or organisational development without formal training or external influence (Fenwick, 2008; Lancaster, 2019, p. 29). Also, many of the above terms are not mere descriptions of the environment; rather, they refer to distinct learning processes. For example, the amount of time spent at work has no bearing on the academic elements of work-integrated learning. As Billett (2025) argues, the content of occupational tasks is essentially a red herring in a work-integrated approach, secondary to the successful reconciliation of learning and practice.

This thesis refers to *work-based learning* for two reasons. First and foremost, this is the language used by SDS, who describe graduate apprenticeships as "work-based learning programmes that lead to degrees" (Skills Development Scotland, 2019a). Additionally, this is the term best suited to the scheme as defined in the literature. Garnett (2005, p. 118) understands work-based learning as a programme with a focus on addressing sector-specific needs, delivered "at, through and for" work. In university settings, this is often project-based, emphasising the contextual application of degree-level learning to develop both the learner and organisation (Garnett, 2005, p. 118; Ferrández-Berruenco, Kekäle and Devins, 2016). Graduate apprenticeships, which centre employer-defined outcomes and work-based projects, align comfortably with this description.

2.4.2 The Tripartite Agreement

A defining feature of the graduate apprenticeship scheme is its tripartite model, which focuses on three core stakeholders: the university, the employer, and the apprentice. Frameworks encourage meaningful collaboration between these three partners, which is emphasised as central to successful delivery (Skills Development Scotland, 2016a, 2019a). This relationship also plays a key role in ensuring coherence across the dual learning environment, which spans the university and the workplace. While Garnett (2005, p. 118) argues that curricula in work-based higher education should be dictated by the needs of the employer and learner, graduate apprenticeships encourage a more balanced approach. In theory, each of these stakeholders provides an equal contribution in shaping the programme and, in turn, will reap rewards that meet their individual needs. Yet, Smith *et al.* (2021a) have found that this is often not the case in practice. Despite policy rhetoric emphasising graduate apprenticeships as employer-led in nature, this refers to industry consultation during the initial framework development process. When it comes time to decide a programme's content, Smith *et al.* (2021a) argue that this

framework-based approach places control with the university and limits the extent to which individual employers can influence the curriculum. Rowe, Moss and Moore (2018) caution against Garnett's prioritisation of employer and learner needs, arguing that universities must perceive a tangible stake to ensure their continued commitment. The authors also suggest that institutions in an unbalanced partnership may adopt a transactional attitude to delivery, leading to decisions driven by cost-effectiveness rather than best pedagogical practice. While Garnett still foregrounds employer and apprentice outcomes twenty years later, he acknowledges the importance of equal collaboration within the tripartite partnership (Garnett and Reynier, 2025).

The apprenticeship model also aims to extend this balance to its embedded support system. Upon enrolment, each apprentice is allocated two mentors: a workplace mentor who supports their development within the organisation by ensuring access to suitable tasks and opportunities, and an academic mentor who guides the integration of theory and practice. Each party signs a tripartite agreement, a formal document which outlines the expectations placed on each stakeholder to ensure that the learner receives adequate individualised support throughout the programme. Although not legally binding, the contract serves as a commitment to shared responsibility for the learning journey. In addition to this wraparound support structure enhancing the coherence of the learning experience, the focus on mentorship over management aims to foster a collaborative relationship that encourages the apprentice to drive their own development (Skills Development Scotland, 2018).

2.4.3 Programme Design, Delivery and Expansion

Universities are the designated providers of graduate apprenticeships, responsible for delivering the curriculum, assessing learning outcomes, and conferring the final award. Although institutions must adhere to the degree title and learning outcomes outlined in the framework, they otherwise retain pedagogical control. This means that, within the parameters set out by SDS, each university has the freedom to put its stamp on an apprenticeship with regard to curriculum design, delivery mode and assessment methods. This flexibility creates variation between institutions (and between disciplinary areas within a single institution) but results in provision standardised in its outcomes. It also enables universities to respond to local employer needs while showcasing their pedagogical strengths.

As discussed in section 2.3.4, universities are responsible for the quality of their provision, including graduate apprenticeships. While the academic elements of a programme can be standardised through the use of quality assurance tools and frameworks, employer engagement is a variable that threatens the overall quality. As part of the agreement with the university, employers are required to allocate a

workplace mentor, as well as ringfencing 20% of the week as protected time for academic activities. However, Scotland has notably low levels of employer engagement compared to countries leading in apprenticeship delivery (OECD, 2022) and the learning experience is often negatively impacted by inadequate mentorship or employer support (Chadwick, Dimungu Hewage and Hazzam, 2025). This is difficult for a university to mitigate and so it poses a significant challenge in terms of managing the quality of apprenticeships. Moreover, Jackson (2025) argues that a lack of employer readiness is a key contributor to the scheme failing to scale in Scotland. She highlights that established apprenticeships in Switzerland and Germany impose strict criteria on employers regarding programme structure and mentor training, which is not the case with degree-level apprenticeships in the UK; Quew-Jones and Rowe (2022) note that little training or resources are available for workplace mentors, who often face inconsistent expectations and lack clarity around their role. As a result, there can be a variable learner experience within a programme (Jackson, 2025; McAdam and Perrin, 2025).

2.4.4 The Graduate Apprentice Learner Profile

In 2017, the then Minister for Employability and Training announced the government's commitment to expanding graduate apprenticeship provision, thereby "broadening access to higher education and increasing adult participation, as well as developing the capabilities and skill sets of organisations and individuals" (Hepburn, 2017). The emphasis on adult participation represents a significant departure from earlier work-based learning initiatives, which were intended to address rising youth employment (explored in section 2.7). The removal of the upper age limit of modern apprenticeships in 2004 was a promising step toward inclusivity, yet funding continues to prioritise individuals aged 16-24 (Skills Development Scotland, 2022b). In contrast, the positioning of graduate apprenticeships in universities attracts a broader demographic. As shown in Table 2.4, the majority of learners are aged 25 and above.

	16-19	20-24	25-34	35-49	50+
2018/19	18.6	29.1	25.0	24.6	2.7
2019/20	18.7	24.9	31.2	22.9	2.2
2020/21	15.5	24.4	34.7	22.6	2.8
2021/22	19.0	23.9	30.9	22.6	3.6
2022/23	25.0	23.6	27.9	21.0	2.5

Table 2.4: Graduate apprenticeship entrants by age (% of intake)

Source: Skills Development Scotland (2025)

Notably, the scheme is most often used by employers as a mechanism to upskill existing staff rather than as a means of attracting new talent. As Table 2.5 illustrates, more than 80% of apprentices are

existing employees. A trend of recruiting new apprentices emerged as frameworks expanded into new sectors, although no data has been published in this area since 2021/22. Nonetheless, the most recent figures show that the vast majority of apprenticeship entrants have been in their role for a minimum of six months at the time of enrolment.

	2017/18	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22
New Employees	16.9%	7.9%	13.6%	11.5%	18.2%
Existing Employees	83.1%	92.1%	84.6%	88.5%	81.8%

Table 2.5: Graduate apprenticeship entrants by length of employment

Source: Skills Development Scotland (2022a)

The 2017/18 cohort also reflected a significant gender disparity, with males making up 82.5% of the first intake. Although the balance has been redressed slightly in subsequent intakes, a pattern of high male participation has persisted. A comparison is shown below in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Graduate apprenticeship entrants by gender (%)

Source: Skills Development Scotland (2025)

This is particularly evident in STEM-focused programmes; the popularity of Civil Engineering, Cyber Security, Data Science and IT contributes substantially to the imbalance. These are historically male-dominated industries and intake data continues to reflect this; in 2022/23, 78.4% of entrants to these were male. The programme with the highest female intake is Early Learning and Childcare, followed by Accounting.

2.4.5 Graduate Apprenticeships and Social Mobility

In addition to upskilling the workforce, apprenticeships are often framed as a vehicle for widening access to higher education (Crawford-Lee and Moorwood, 2019; Skills Development Scotland, 2021b; Pullen *et al.*, 2024). While the scheme's emphasis on Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) has provided access to many individuals who do not hold the standard university entry qualifications (Hughes and Saieva, 2019), recent intake data demonstrates persistent underrepresentation of disabled learners, minority ethnic backgrounds and individuals from economically deprived areas (Skills Development Scotland, 2025). Below, Figures 2.3 and 2.4 compare the ethnic backgrounds and reported disabilities of apprentices and full-time Scottish-domiciled undergraduates.

Figure 2.3: Comparison of 2022/23 GA and UG intake by disability

Source: HESA (2024); Skills Development Scotland (2025)

Figure 2.4: Comparison of 2022/23 GA and UG intake by ethnicity

Source: HESA (2024); Skills Development Scotland (2025)

Next, Figure 2.5 compares the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) quintiles of apprentices to full-time undergraduates. Quintiles 0-20 represent the most economically deprived areas and 80-100 the most affluent.

Figure 2.5: Comparison of 2022/23 GA and UG intake by SIMD
 Source: HESA (2025b); Skills Development Scotland (2025)

It is noted that apprentice enrolment in deprived areas is largely in line with full-time undergraduate degrees, highlighting an opportunity to look beyond parity and expand widening participation efforts by actively engaging underrepresented groups. However, this would require substantial changes to present recruitment practices, which are employer-led. Currently, universities offer a number of places to an employer, who then nominates employees for enrolment (Smith *et al.*, 2021b). This means that apprentices are often high-performing individuals previously earmarked for progression within the organisation (Pullen *et al.*, 2024), which risks inadvertently reinforcing existing inequalities.

2.5 Funding Provisions and Economic Impact

2.5.1 The Apprenticeship Levy

The apprenticeship levy was introduced in 2017, marking a significant shift in the UK skills agenda. The levy is essentially a training tax paid by businesses with an annual payroll in excess of £3 million. For the first three years, Scotland received an average of £230 million from the levy per year, which was allocated as targeted support for apprenticeship development. However, since 2020/21, income from the levy is no longer ringfenced for apprenticeship development; the funds are now allocated as part of the general block grant, affording the Scottish Government discretion over spending decisions

(Evans, 2024). Importantly, rather than providing an additional revenue stream, the levy income has simply replaced the share of apprenticeship funding historically received from Westminster (Scottish Government, 2016b).

Historical attempts to develop the workforce have highlighted a frustrating paradox: the UK struggles to sustain a long-term, impactful skills initiative due to relatively poor economic productivity, but this productivity is unlikely to improve without a more skilled workforce (Mohamud *et al.*, 2006). This dilemma has been compounded by chronic underinvestment in training by employers since the turn of the century (Green *et al.*, 2013). Becker's (1962) human capital theory suggests that employers are unwilling to fund training in general or sector-wide skills due to the risk of losing staff to competitors and seeing no return on investment. Since migrating to a demand-led skills system, this view has created a disconnect between employer demands and training providers, wherein organisations request bespoke training programmes that are impractical or economically unviable to deliver (Green and Hogarth, 2016). This challenge is also magnified in the context of extended programmes such as graduate apprenticeships; while the model generally offers a substantial return on investment in the form of enhanced productivity and capabilities, the programme length and advanced level of study significantly increase the investment risk (Wolf, 2015; Gambin and Hogarth, 2017).

Faced with growing skills shortages following decades of underinvestment in workplace training, the UK Government introduced the apprenticeship levy as a means of mandating employer contribution (Winch *et al.*, 2025), though it was met with some concern. The Scottish Government consulted with employers and, while the feedback was largely positive, almost a fifth of respondents disagreed with levy funding being used for graduate apprenticeships. The majority of complaints cited low demand for programmes at this level, either due to a misalignment with sector needs, an oversubscription of graduate applicants, or a lack of infrastructure to support an apprentice. In addition, some employers expressed a reluctance to "subsidise" training for other organisations (Scottish Government, 2016a).

Historically, universal levies have not been successful in the long term, and the UK has a colourful track record of introducing and abolishing short-lived training levies (Dougherty and Tan, 1997; Smith and Billett, 2006). Importantly, this was implemented unilaterally; while skills policy is a devolved matter, training levies remain in the hands of the UK Government, which means the Scottish Government had little input in the decision and no scope to grant exemptions. In their limited capacity, the rules around accessing training funds were relaxed in Scotland, with some of the levy proceeds used to establish the Flexible Workforce Development Fund (FWDF). In cases where a company was unable to make

use of formal apprenticeship programmes, this allowed them to access funded training opportunities more appropriate for their needs. However, the fund was subsequently discontinued and, due to the focus on framework development in priority areas, entire sectors have been left contributing to the levy with no means of a return. Wolf (2015) makes a compelling argument for mandated employer contributions but the negative responses to the government consultation reveal an individualistic attitude amongst many employers, whose concerns were not entirely unfounded. With regard to long-term sustainability, it is unlikely that the levy can continue in its current form without experiencing significant pushback from underserved sectors of the labour market.

2.5.2 Funding Reforms

In the relatively short period since the scheme was launched, apprenticeship funding mechanisms have experienced periods of flux. In the early stages of the project to expand apprenticeship training, a European Social Fund (ESF) grant of £8.6m (Douglas, 2020) was allocated for the development of graduate apprenticeships. ESF support ceased following the UK's exit from the European Union and a recent SDS financial report confirmed that ESF income was settled in June 2024 (Skills Development Scotland, 2024a).

Graduate apprenticeship funding was initially distributed by SDS, who allocated income from the levy (with additional support from ESF) to education providers. In 2021, this responsibility transitioned to the Scottish Funding Council (SFC), and graduate apprentices are now required to apply for tuition fees to be paid through the Student Awards Agency Scotland (SAAS). This funding model is an example of the flexibility offered by graduate apprenticeships in comparison to degree apprenticeships, their English counterparts. SAAS tuition fee grants are awarded to the individual apprentice and paid directly to the university, allowing the learner to move freely between employers with no impact on their studies. In the case of degree apprenticeships, the funding agreement is with the organisation, and so apprentices in England are tied to their employer for the duration of the programme.

Eight years since the launch of the scheme, graduate apprenticeships continue to face uncertainty around their position within the skills system. In February 2025, the Tertiary Education and Training (Funding and Governance) (Scotland) Bill was introduced, which proposes that overall responsibility for the scheme is transferred from SDS to SFC. At the time of writing, the Bill has been subject to a number of amendments and is at Stage 3 of the approval process.

In terms of policy alignment, the scheme plays a vital role in supporting a number of national agendas, including the National Strategy for Economic Transformation (Brasted, 2024). In 2021, the Future Skills Action Plan committed to investing in graduate apprenticeships after a growing demand for upskilling opportunities was identified (Scottish Government, 2021). However, the funding allocation does not meet the level of investment required to sustain the current model. This lack of financial commitment, combined with significant shifts in pedagogy and institutional culture required to successfully embed work-based learning within existing university structures, has raised questions about the model's long-term sustainability (Jackson, 2025). An example of pedagogical change is the one-to-one mentorship mandated by the framework, which, as Jackson explains, makes teaching significantly more labour-intensive than full-time degrees. This often leads to apprenticeships operating at a loss, creating what the author describes as a "perverse incentive".

Withdrawing the FWDF is a further example of a disconnect between the Scottish Government's words and actions. The fund was introduced in 2017 to provide levy-payers (and, later, non-payers) a means of developing staff in cases where SDS apprenticeships did not meet organisational needs. In January 2023, the Lifelong Learning and Skills Directorate published a lengthy evaluation of the FWDF, in which its contributions to several prominent national strategies were highlighted. The report concluded that the initiative was delivering against its key aims and should continue (EKOS, 2023). Despite this, the Scottish Government chose not to allocate any money to the FWDF in its 2023/24 or 2024/25 budgets and later confirmed that the fund has been discontinued (Scottish Government, 2024a, part 5).

Policy rhetoric continues to express a need for dynamic solutions to workforce development but such shifts in funding signal a reorientation of the government's priorities, which do not appear to include meaningful investment in graduate apprenticeships. Below, Table 2.6 provides a breakdown of annual funding allocations by apprenticeship type.

	Foundation		Modern		Graduate		
	SFC	SDS	SFC	SDS	SFC	SAAS*	SDS
2019/20	–	£14m	£50m	£82m	–	–	£12m
2020/21	£9m	£15m	£50m	£80m	–	–	£17m
2021/22	£9m	£12m	£50m	£78m	£7m	£2m	£17m
2022/23	£9m	£9m	£50m	£76m	£15m	£3m	£10m
2023/24	£10m	£8m	£50m	£84m	£23m	£5m	£6m

Table 2.6: Apprenticeship funding allocation (2019/20 - 2023/24)

*SAAS provides tuition fees for graduate apprenticeships only

Source: Scottish Government (2025a)

The Minister for Higher and Further Education has attempted to assuage concerns, stating that the Scottish Government is "absolutely committed to continuing funding for all types of apprenticeships" (The Scottish Parliament, 2025, 07:58). However, the scheme's long-term viability will remain a source of concern until such time as there is greater alignment of words and actions at a policy level.

2.6 The Value Proposition of Graduate Apprenticeships

2.6.1 Are Apprenticeships Education or Training?

Despite their delivery by higher education institutions and, in some cases, a curricular overlap with full-time degree programmes, graduate apprenticeships can reasonably be described as vocational learning. The OECD (2019) defines this as a programme that (i) sees at least 25% of the curriculum delivered in the workplace, (ii) results in a sector-specific qualification, and (iii) allows a learner to carry out a job role with no further training required. The historical role of vocational study in higher education is explored further in chapter three.

Defining graduate apprenticeships as vocational also invites scrutiny in terms of whether or not they should be considered education in the traditional sense. Typically, education is associated with a broad accumulation of knowledge and transferable skills, such as the development of critical thinking, while training focuses on acquiring a narrow set of skills required to carry out a specific role (Mazenod, 2016). Although universities retain autonomy over curriculum and assessment design, they are bound to the learning outcomes stipulated in the framework, which may narrow the scope of the programme and steer it toward the definition of training. The framework approach also has the potential to limit the disciplinary depth achievable within SDS's parameters. It is therefore vital that pedagogical intent is firmly established to ensure the academic legitimacy of graduate apprenticeships, rather than allowing them to decline into what are essentially credentialised training schemes.

The Wolf Report (2011) heavily influenced the launch of degree apprenticeships (gov.uk, 2015b) and, by extension, graduate apprenticeships. In her extensive review of vocational provision, Wolf (2011, p. 73) reasons:

The labour market recognises qualifications that are stable and familiar, but English vocational qualifications have been and remain subject to constant change. [...] The English Government has now, for decades, been introducing new types of vocational qualification, abolishing them, and introducing yet another new set. Academic qualifications have, by comparison, been fairly stable, at least in their titles.

Here, the author raises an interesting point that may offer something in the way of an explanation for situating apprenticeships in universities rather than further education colleges, which are historically the domain of vocational and work-based study (Brockmann, Clarke and Winch, 2010). Initially, the schemes were referred to as degree-level and graduate-level apprenticeships. Based on Wolf's above observation, it seems that a choice was made to academicise the model and strengthen the academic alignment of its name as a means of enhancing qualification recognition and transferability within the labour market.

The debate of vocational programmes in higher education long pre-dates graduate apprenticeships, however. In 1916, John Dewey voiced concern about utilitarian (vocational) programmes encroaching on liberal (academic) spaces, which he attributed to rising economic pressures. Dewey (1916, p. 301) cautioned against the "curious intermingling" of vocational pursuits in academic institutions:

The "utility" element is found in the motives assigned for the study, the "liberal" element in methods of teaching. The outcome of the mixture is perhaps less satisfactory than if either principle were adhered to in its purity.

Over a century has passed since Dewey offered this opinion, yet many vocational disciplines still carry a perception of being inferior to academic pathways and lacking in intellectual interest (Sweet, 1995; Basit *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, such misperceptions often lead to negative assumptions made about the intelligence and socio-economic background of vocational learners (Young and Hordern, 2022; Van de Weerd, 2023). In a study of stigma attached to vocational and technical education in the USA, Gauthier (2020) observed that the literature is largely separated into two schools of thought: one that views the higher education institution as a place for knowledge acquisition and personal development, and another that views it as an active participant in the knowledge economy, emphasising universities as a space for innovation and economic impact.

Although the debate of education versus training remains unresolved, the breadth-depth distinction offers a useful framing. As degree programmes, graduate apprenticeship curricula emphasise breadth within a vocational structure, positioning them as a potential bridge across the academic-vocational divide (Mazenod, 2016; Young and Hordern, 2022). Their delivery by universities also provides a strong sense of academic legitimacy, further supported by their alignment with the SCQF. On the other hand, curriculum design is guided by employer-defined and sector-specific learning outcomes. While the frameworks describe "broad" learning outcomes, this does not refer to breadth of knowledge; rather, this is an assurance that the programme will appeal to a diverse range of employers in a single sector

(Skills Development Scotland, 2019a). If breadth versus depth is indeed the deciding factor, then the scheme's focus on sector relevance and industry-defined competencies tips the scale toward training.

Applying these parameters more broadly, any number of competitive and academically demanding degrees can be framed as vocational training. Indeed, a study by the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE, 2018) defined vocational degrees as delivering a narrow set of skills and leading to employment within a specific sector. The most vocational subject areas were identified as medicine and dentistry, which the report used to illustrate that the characterisations of academic and vocational are not mutually exclusive. Thus, based on the notion that a medical degree is vocational training and therefore shares academic parity with a graduate apprenticeship, any stigma toward the latter can likely be attributed to negative stereotyping of the word *apprenticeship* and misperceptions around the typical vocational learner profile (Lester and Bravenboer, 2020; Young and Hordern, 2022; Van de Weerd, 2023).

2.6.2 The Comparative Value of Apprenticeship and Traditional Degrees

In the late 1990s, New Labour believed that the UK's economy hinged on an educated workforce and so higher education was framed as the pathway to achieving national (and personal) prosperity. In the years that followed, their "education, education, education" mantra led to an exponential increase in university attendance, and the number of degree awards rose by 56% between 2000/01 and 2023/24 (Statista, 2025). This meant the labour market was quickly saturated with university graduates, and credentials became a screening tool for employers. Many then began demanding degrees regardless of the skills required for the role, which led to debates around degree inflation due to concerns that their value was being diluted. Indeed, as the number of university-educated applicants grew, it became common for job vacancies to stipulate a higher degree classification (Bennett, 2002; Brooks and Everett, 2009).

However, a trend of increasing first class and 2:1 awards emerged (Figure 2.6, overleaf), which pushed many individuals to pursue postgraduate study in an effort to gain a competitive advantage (Allais, 2014). The resultant credentialisation saw a third of individuals who graduated after 2007 experience wage penalties related to overeducation, impacting some for up to five years post-graduation (Savic, Vecchi and Lewis, 2019). These dynamics contributed to wider massification, marketisation and mass credentialism, which are explored further in chapter three.

Figure 2.6: Undergraduate awards by degree classification 2006/07 - 2023/24

Source: HESA (2025a)

Policy rhetoric around the demand for highly educated workers, coupled with the normalisation of university attendance for school leavers, contributed to assumptions that a degree was the golden ticket to a lucrative career, but subsequent research found that graduates felt that the value of higher education had been mis-sold (Brooks and Everett, 2009; Tomlinson and Watermeyer, 2022). The influx of degree-holders also did nothing to address longstanding employer complaints around graduate employability, which cite widespread difficulties translating theory into practice and a lack of soft skills required to navigate the workplace (Bacon, Benton and Gruneberg, 1979; Little and Brennan, 1996; Clarke, 2018). However, recruitment trends in recent years indicate a notable shift in labour market needs. Following a study of 21 million job adverts, Brown and Souto-Otero (2020) found that only 18% of vacancies explicitly referenced qualifications, but the overwhelming majority specified social or transferable skills that contribute to workplace readiness. This shift in recruitment priorities reflects rapid sector developments and suggests that employers are now less willing (or able) to invest time in training new recruits.

It also suggests that three decades after higher education was framed as the path to financial security, we have come full circle. Where a degree was once considered the minimum requirement for many roles, now it is often viewed as inadequate preparation for the workplace. This shift provides insight into the rationale for the graduate apprenticeship scheme, as its model provides an environment for learners to gain sector-specific knowledge alongside the socialisation and internalisation of workplace norms missing from traditional degrees (Marsden, 1995). This aligns with the principles of Lave and Wenger's (1991) situated learning theory, which posits that learning is most effective when conducted

through active and extended participation in a "community of practice", which highlights an important point of comparison between graduate apprenticeships and full-time degrees. Upon completion of an apprenticeship, learners not only hold a degree in a relevant discipline but have also developed a nuanced understanding of the norms and expectations of their workplace. While many traditional degrees offer short-term or sandwich placements, it is almost impossible for the average full-time degree to facilitate the same level of workplace integration as a graduate apprenticeship.

This integrated, participative model can also offer learners a range of monetary and mobility benefits. Firstly, apprentices are full-time employees earning their normal salary, which enables them to obtain a degree without acquiring debt. Although Scottish undergraduates do not pay tuition fees to study in Scotland, a large proportion of full-time students rely on maintenance loans to cover their daily living costs, with the average graduate's debt totalling £17,990¹ in 2024/25 (Bathmaker *et al.*, 2016, p. 4; Student Loans Company, 2025). However, the scheme's *earn while you learn* tagline addresses the issue of affordability, which has historically presented a significant barrier to adults entering higher education. Secondly, embedding programme delivery in the workplace allows learners to establish professional networks and showcase their development in situ. From this perspective, graduate apprenticeships appear to offer the more strategic option in terms of career resilience and financial opportunity.

The integrated design of the apprenticeship model also lends itself to greater graduate employability. As academic credentials appear to have fallen out of favour with employers and attention has turned to softer, more communication-based skills, universities have made concerted efforts to embed employability initiatives in the curriculum – with limited success. Employability is sometimes viewed as supplemental to core academic activities and has attracted criticism for reducing the academic depth and rigour of degree programmes. However, credentials are no longer a reliable indicator of employability and so graduates must be able to robustly demonstrate professional capabilities (Clarke, 2018). Graduate apprenticeships arguably result in greater workplace preparation than traditional degrees; through situated learning, soft skills are developed in an authentic environment, addressing the gap between degree-level graduates and workplace readiness. Despite this, a recent UCAS (2021) study found that 87% of respondents viewed a traditional degree as key to obtaining a job, compared to 57% who saw similar value in degree apprenticeships. This points to a need for clearer information around the comparative benefits of apprenticeships.

¹ Provisional figure to be finalised by the Student Loans Company in 2026

2.6.3 Meta-Skills and Employability

A core tenet of graduate apprenticeships is their responsiveness to evolving industry needs and SDS has demonstrated a commitment to this through the expansion of frameworks into new sectors. Furthermore, the needs of learners have changed since the scheme was established; factors such as the Covid pandemic have caused a societal shift in how we work, increasing demand for resilient, adaptable and self-motivated employees (De Carlo *et al.*, 2025). In response, SDS introduced a new framework template, which included a list of meta-skills. These represent a specific type of graduate attribute described as "high-level capabilities" (Skills Development Scotland, 2019b).

Self-Management	Social Intelligence	Innovation
Focusing	Communication	Curiosity
Integrity	Feeling	Creativity
Adapting	Collaborating	Sense-Making
Initiative	Leading	Critical Thinking

Table 2.7: Graduate apprenticeship meta-skills

Source: Skills Development Scotland (2019b)

Following a successful pilot, these meta-skills have been embedded in all frameworks developed since 2019 as secondary learning outcomes to further increase employability. By supplementing the core disciplinary learning outcomes with these attributes, graduate apprenticeships operate as a template for the OECD's (2021) definition of "successful" learning. However, further discourse may be required to temper employer expectations, as a study by Fabian *et al.* (2023) highlights a number of job adverts seeking apprentices already equipped with the attributes that graduate apprenticeships are designed to instil.

From a policy perspective, meta-skills are described as playing a pivotal role in delivering the Future Skills Action Plan agenda (Scottish Government, 2021). However, the intangible nature of meta-skills presents pedagogical challenges, particularly in terms of measuring these learning outcomes. Meta-skills were deliberately embedded into frameworks to encourage development across the academic and workplace learning environments, but these attributes are largely context-dependent and will not be captured through traditional university assessment methods. Inconsistent employer engagement also means that workplace feedback is not a reliable means of recording learner progress, therefore the burden of integrating the required assessment mechanisms falls to the educator. The workload of this additional monitoring is unlikely to be an issue for small cohorts but would intensify at scale (Thomas and Grimes, 2003), reinforcing Jackson's (2025) observations of the labour-intensive nature of apprenticeship delivery.

2.6.4 Achieving Parity of Esteem

The benefits offered to stakeholders by graduate and degree apprenticeships are often presented in literature (Garnett, 2005; Crawford-Lee and Moorwood, 2019; Lester, 2020; Emms *et al.*, 2021). Yet, despite evidence of apprenticeships outperforming full-time degrees against a number of key metrics (City & Guilds Group, 2020), negative views of vocational learning persist. The cultural preference for academic pathways highlights a dissonance stemming from cultural and institutional biases reinforced by decades of a two-tier educational system: polytechnics versus universities.

In this context, parity of esteem refers to the notion that academic and vocational programmes carry equal value, a concept that has long been contested. In their study comparing employer perceptions of university and polytechnic graduates, Bacon, Benton and Gruneberg (1979) themselves described the latter as "university rejects". The authors also found that polytechnic learners were assumed to be socially and intellectually inferior to university graduates – perceived deficiencies that employers would not overlook regardless of a candidate's industry experience. Fast-forward almost half a century and graduate apprenticeships, established in part to address the social-intellect-experience dilemma identified by employers in 1979, still bear residual stigma. Mazonod (2016) suggests that vocational programmes are often perceived as training rather than true education, leading to them being held in lower regard. This is supported by a study by the City & Guilds Group (2020), which found that despite the fact that apprenticeships outperform full-time degrees in terms of value for money, longevity of skills and preparing a learner for the workplace, there is still considerable stigma attached. The study found that while 73% of respondents viewed apprenticeships as the stronger option for workplace preparation, 50% would still opt to undertake a full-time degree.

Moreover, negative perceptions of vocational programmes are not limited to the general public; the same views can be heard within universities. Although many academics are enthusiastic about apprenticeships, others have expressed the belief that work-based learning does not constitute true education and fear that teaching apprentices would diminish their position to that of a trainer (Basil *et al.*, 2015). Such views may be shaped by institutional context, however. Some universities are less well-versed in widening participation activities, meaning their academics have limited experience with a broad student demographic. In graduate apprenticeships, particularly in the case of mature learners who may have held their job for many years, the learner is the expert in their role. The educator must therefore adapt to their needs and act as a facilitator in their journey. This shift flips the transmission of knowledge from supply to demand (Chiţiba, 2012), which may represent an uncomfortable position for some academics. Regardless, the inherent snobbery toward vocational learning (Hanshaw, 2024)

evident in some areas of higher education poses a significant barrier to the successful integration of apprenticeships and undermines efforts to achieve parity of esteem. This concept is revisited in the next chapter, which explores the conditions that dictate how vocational education is positioned in the sector's reputational hierarchy.

In a report titled *Independent Review of the Skills Delivery Landscape*, Withers (2023) described the graduate apprenticeship scheme as having "a misleading name, but a huge potential". However, the decision to adopt *graduate* rather than *degree* apprenticeship can be interpreted as a strategic move by the Scottish Government. Prior to 2016, public communications made reference to "degree level" and "graduate level" apprenticeships. Following the announcement of the apprenticeship levy by the UK Government, Scotland's Minister for Employability and Training made a statement: "This was done without any prior consultation with the Scottish Government and the other Devolved Administrations, despite apprenticeship policy being a fully devolved matter" (Hepburn, 2016). Hepburn emphasised the government's commitment to protecting its "distinctive Scottish approach" to education, and the name *graduate apprenticeship* appeared in all communications henceforth. Subsequent publications (Hepburn, 2017) continued to underscore a desire for political distancing from Westminster, so it can be reasonably assumed that the decision not to adopt the title of degree apprenticeship was to further emphasise a separation of the schemes.

Yet such descriptors are ultimately inconsequential, as negative perceptions are firmly attached to the word *apprenticeship* (Straw *et al.*, 2022). Beyond a simple issue of branding, this disconnect has contributed to a fundamental lack of understanding around the purpose and value of graduate apprenticeships, which must be addressed if they are to shed this hangover of stigma. While Crawford-Lee and Moorwood (2019) argue that degree apprenticeships have successfully demonstrated their value as equal to traditional degrees, this thesis contends that true parity of esteem will remain an aspirational concept without a large-scale culture shift from within academia itself.

2.7 The Decline of Work-Based Learning

The final section of this chapter explores the decline of trade apprenticeships in the UK, why there have been so many failed work-based learning initiatives in recent decades, and whether there are lessons to be learned from respected apprenticeship models in Germany and Switzerland. As a point of clarification, the focus of this study is specifically Scottish apprenticeship provision, however education was not a devolved matter until the establishment of the Scottish Parliament in 1999. Prior

to this, the UK Government was responsible for education and training policy and so this section refers to UK-wide initiatives.

2.7.1 A History of Work-Based Learning in the UK

Apprenticeships soared in popularity following World War II and reached a peak in the 1960s, at which time roughly 35% of male school leavers adopted a trade (Vickerstaff, 2003). This can be attributed to demographic and socio-political shifts; the post-war baby boom led to large secondary school cohorts and this demographic bulge meant there was deep concern around the number of opportunities for young people, particularly when National Service ended (Vickerstaff, 2007). Apprenticeships were largely unregulated in the 1960s and there was little in the way of quality assurance, which meant that a trade apprenticeship did not guarantee the skillset required to succeed once time-served (Ministry of Labour and National Service, 1958; Marsden, 1995). Demand for traditional manual labourers experienced a sharp decline in the 1970s, falling by up to 90% (Haxby and Parkes, 1989) as single-craft apprenticeships fell out of favour with employers, who saw them as outdated and out of step with the demands of the modern workplace. By the end of the decade, most employers were opting to recruit time-served workers over trainees (Marsden, 1995).

Concerns over youth unemployment led to the establishment of the Manpower Services Commission (MSC) in 1973, a public body tasked with overhauling employment and training policy. One of the commission's key objectives was to raise the public profile of vocational learning to such a level that the dichotomy between education and training was eradicated (Tusting and Barton, 2007). As this thesis is making similar arguments more than fifty years later, it is safe to say MSC was unsuccessful in this regard. Under the commission's governance, the Training Opportunities Scheme, an adult skills service, began to falter as funding cuts caused curricula to narrow. Ultimately, the programme lacked depth of knowledge and attracted criticism for failing to facilitate any meaningful development of transferable skills (Evans *et al.*, 2025). In 1976, the Work Experience Scheme opened what would be a revolving door of initiatives targeting youth unemployment. This was followed two years later by the Youth Opportunities Programme (YOP), but this was also criticised for being of limited value, and employers were accused of exploiting the scheme as a source of cheap labour. It was around this time that policymakers decided to place all of their metaphorical eggs in the basket of Britain's youth, leading to a withdrawal of adult education subsidies (Matheson, 2014, p. 170).

By the mid 1980s, the UK economy was experiencing rapid transformation, and demand for traditional manual labour was replaced by a need for employees skilled in emerging sectors such as information

technology, electronics, and optics (Haxby and Parkes, 1989). The launch of the Youth Training Scheme (YTS) in 1983 sought to address these emerging skills gaps in addition to youth unemployment, signalling a shift toward a more responsive and future-focused training model. In contrast with trade apprenticeships of previous generations, wherein the learner bore the brunt of training costs through drastically reduced wages (Marsden, 1995), YTS offered participants a financial incentive. Successful completion also led to a recognised, transferable qualification. This is a key differentiator between the YTS programme and its predecessors, which were fragmented and often deliberately designed to be non-transferable to deter poaching by competitors (Marsden, 1995). In this sense, YTS represented a disruptive model in the vocational landscape, challenging public perceptions of work-based learning (Levy, 2012). However, like YOP before it, YTS also faced accusations of exploitation. Young adults participating in the scheme likened it to "slave labour" (Raffe and Smith, 1987) and the government was accused by trade unions of developing a pool of cheap labour for its own ends. YTS was rebranded and relaunched twice but was ultimately abandoned.

Following the abolishment of YTS, the flagship modern apprenticeship scheme was launched in 1994, which marked a significant shift in vocational education policy. The model also challenged the idea that apprenticeships were purely for trades, as modern apprenticeships offered structured training and transferable qualifications across a diverse range of sectors. Modern apprenticeships have undergone significant reform since then but their responsiveness to sector needs has seen the scheme become the most enduring of its kind in the UK.

The central issue that has plagued previous initiatives is their myopic framing as a means to address unemployment, focusing on delivering work experience rather than meaningful skills training. This was compounded by institution-led recruitment and a lack of employer involvement in training delivery, which led to a misalignment of employee capabilities and long-term organisational needs (Fuller and Unwin, 2011). The focus on industry relevance and employer-led recruitment of graduate apprenticeships represents a significant departure from this approach, which may indicate that they are the first step toward breaking a decades-long cycle of unsuccessful workforce development.

2.7.2 Beyond Britain: Lessons from Abroad

While the UK has seen apprenticeships decline in engagement and status for a number of decades, there are notable examples of thriving models in Europe. In Germany and Switzerland, for example, vocational education plays a significant role in workforce development and is viewed as a vital element of the post-secondary education landscape (Deissinger and Gonon, 2021). Both countries operate a

dual apprenticeship system wherein vocational learning is integrated with highly structured workplace training programmes. Although there is a clear dichotomy between university and vocational routes, apprenticeships are culturally embedded and held in high esteem, offering a credible alternative to academic pathways – something that the UK has not yet been able to replicate (Brockmann, Clarke and Winch, 2010; Graf, 2017). Moreover, in contrast with the limited number of apprenticeship frameworks in Scotland, these dual systems offer training across the vast majority of sectors.

While the German and Swiss systems are similar in many respects, there are a number of structural differences. In Germany, the practical components of apprenticeships are based in the workplace, with theory-based elements delivered by publicly funded vocational institutions. However, there is a power imbalance apparent within their tripartite structure; the employer shoulders the majority of the costs, which can be significant due to a series of complex legal standards that dictate the content, quality and delivery methods of training programmes, which has led to the German training landscape operating as a seller's market (Deissinger and Gonon, 2021). In turn, apprentices earn a lower rate of pay, which aids in redressing the financial balance and incentivises their recruitment by smaller firms (Haasler, 2020). Roughly half of all German school leavers enter an apprenticeship (CEDEFOP and BIBB, 2024) and while this supports the model to deliver against its aim of supplying the labour market with highly skilled workers, this longstanding institution operates within an incredibly inflexible context. Entrenched corporatism, rigid regulatory oversight and reliance on consensus between high-level stakeholders mean there is little scope for programme customisation (Schmid and Leschke, 2025).

On the other hand, Switzerland operates a decentralised apprenticeship model, which is coordinated at a cantonal (regional) level. Another notable difference between these examples is the award level; an apprenticeship in Switzerland leads to one of two federally recognised qualifications equivalent to SCQF level 8 or 10, while German programmes are regarded as intermediate and equivalent to SCQF level 6. Further study is therefore required to achieve a *Meister*, or professional degree. Over the last thirty years, the system has undergone significant reform and a focus on integrating apprenticeships into Switzerland's educational landscape has led to their acceptance as a legitimate alternative to a degree (Deissinger and Gonon, 2021). Funding arrangements and development activities resemble the graduate apprenticeship scheme more than the German model; training is financed through sector-specific levies and new programmes are developed in consultation with employers and trade unions. However, the Swiss system places greater emphasis on the consistency of learning outcomes than the Scottish model, with employer involvement extending to the development of standardised curricula and assessment (Hoffman and Schwartz, 2015).

The German and Swiss systems are often hailed as the gold standard, with the OECD (2022) describing them as "leading apprenticeship countries". Although their enviable levels of employer engagement and financial investment make wholesale integration of these models tempting, it is improbable that their successes would be replicated in the UK due to differences in structural, institutional and cultural history (Deissinger and Gonon, 2021; Schmid and Leschke, 2025). Introducing such corporatism to the market-led apprenticeship model of the UK would also require unprecedented reform of the national skills infrastructure, including an integration of dedicated vocational pathways from secondary school. Crucially, transplanting a structural model from overseas without first combating negative perceptions of apprenticeships would likely spell disaster for the scheme.

While these examples offer insight into alternative approaches to work-based learning, they will likely remain aspirational. The historically non-interventionist UK government long expressed the view that apprenticeships were a labour market matter, which delayed much-needed investment (Ryan, 2014, p. 41). This put a considerable distance between the training landscapes and it is unlikely that the lost momentum can be recovered. Nonetheless, graduate apprenticeships offer a pragmatic option that is grounded in the national context, and this study seeks to establish their distinctive value proposition.

2.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter introduced graduate apprenticeships as a strategic response to Scotland's evolving skills landscape, mapping the scheme's structure and aims in the wider context of policy, governance and stakeholder dynamics. After clarifying work-based learning terminology, graduate apprenticeships were framed as degree-level vocational training, distinct from both traditional academic routes and early iterations of work-based learning. The chapter explored how labour market needs have changed and assessed the comparative value propositions of apprenticeships and full-time degrees in terms of future-proofing employability. Analysis of the typical apprentice learner profile revealed a pattern in age, gender and socio-economic background, raising questions around the scheme's widening access ambitions. A number of persistent challenges were also identified, including inconsistent employer engagement, negative perceptions of vocational routes, and funding allocations that fail to recognise the additional costs associated with apprenticeship delivery.

Overall, this chapter provides insight into the potential and limitations of graduate apprenticeships as part of the wider Scottish skills landscape. Next, chapter three shifts the focus to how the scheme is positioned within the higher education sector.

Chapter 3: Exploring the Higher Education Landscape

While the marketisation of higher education in the UK offers a discourse of 'choice', thus apparently offering the possibility of attending any institution to any potential student, this itself occludes the complex architecture of exclusion.

– Walkerdine (2021)

3.1 Chapter Overview

Having introduced the concept and policy context of graduate apprenticeships in chapter two, the focus now pivots to the dynamics and reputational hierarchy within the higher education sector. This chapter traces the evolution of British universities from elite institutions of the nineteenth century to the mass system we see today. Constraints on institutional agency are also explored, particularly in terms of marketisation, vocationalisation and credentialism. Bourdieu's theory of capital provides a useful lens through which to examine how institutional status shapes cultural perceptions of academic legitimacy. Advocating for a widespread shift in perspective, this chapter frames apprenticeships not as a remedial option but as a distinct pedagogy with the potential to challenge the deeply entrenched sectoral hegemony.

3.2 Chapter Considerations

3.2.1 Terminology and Usage

This chapter describes an implicit hierarchy of universities in the British higher education sector. To differentiate between the tiers therein, this thesis organises institutions into four broad categories:

Ancient: This refers to Scottish universities established in the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries. They are also described as traditional, research-led and research-intensive institutions.

Pre-92: This refers to chartered institutions, which were established after their ancient counterparts and granted university status by royal charter in the 1960s.

Post-92: This refers to modern institutions, which gained university status with the introduction of the Further and Higher Education Act 1992.

Specialist: These are institutions dedicated to delivering programmes of higher education in a specific field, such as art schools and conservatoires.

It should be noted that this thesis refers to institutions with a physical campus, therefore the Open University in Scotland has been excluded and all financial figures adjusted accordingly. Table 3.1 outlines the number of Scottish higher education institutions in each of these categories.

Ancient	Pre-92	Post-92	Specialist
4	4	7	3

Table 3.1: Number of Scottish higher education institutions by category

3.2.2 Geographical Scope

Although a focus on Scottish apprenticeship provision is central to this thesis, this chapter examines the trajectory of Scotland's universities within the wider structural and policy context of higher education in Great Britain. Universities in Scotland and England have operated under distinct systems for centuries, including legal frameworks, governance structures, and divergence in their curricula. However, increasing intervention by the UK Government since the early nineteenth century has shaped the trajectories of both systems. Though Scotland now retains authority over its education policy, it is important to recognise that these devolved powers are a recent development in the overall timeline of the nation's universities. This historical enmeshment has had a lasting impact on the Scottish higher education landscape, making it almost impossible to examine the current context of Scotland's universities in isolation. For example, the resource stratification and reputational hierarchy present across British universities is arguably rooted in the binary education system implemented by the UK Government – a persistent hangover despite almost thirty years of devolution (Raffe and Croxford, 2015; Carpentier, 2021). For these reasons, unless explicitly stated, this chapter refers to developments across Great Britain.

3.3 The Stratification of the Higher Education Sector

3.3.1 The Evolution of the British University

Higher education in Great Britain has evolved over centuries from a cluster of elite institutions into a diverse sector increasingly defined by its role in driving innovation, and this thesis argues that graduate apprenticeships are the logical next step. While they may appear far removed from the concerns of post-Enlightenment scholarship, understanding the historical events that shaped an academic system makes it far easier to anticipate its future trajectory (Clark, 1978). This section therefore traces key developments in the (relatively) recent history of British higher education to contextualise the dynamics and tensions underpinning graduate apprenticeships. Doing so also offers insight into the construction of institutional identity and academic legitimacy.

In the early nineteenth century, the ancient universities (and those modelled on them thereafter) in England had shed their monastic overtones and embraced a new purpose: preserving the culture of the societal elite (Donovan, 2013). Tapper and Palfreyman (2010, p. 17) explain that the collegiality of Oxford and Cambridge reinforced a socio-moral code that sought to cultivate graduates ready for the elite ranks of society. They argue that this collegial model distinguishes a university from a "managed machine" of higher education. Ashby (1956), on the other hand, offers a less flattering assessment of their role in society at that time, describing Oxbridge as a "nursery for gentlemen".

Scottish institutions were pursuing a vastly different agenda at that time. Despite the nation making impressive strides in intellectual leadership during the Enlightenment thanks to figures such as Adam Smith and David Hume, Scottish universities entered the nineteenth century with outdated structures which were misaligned with the needs of the growing student body. Known for taking a more flexible approach to student entry requirements than their English counterparts, universities in Scotland were in desperate need of curricula reform in order to meet the needs of middle-class learners. This eventually came in the form of two parliamentary acts in 1858 and 1889, respectively. The universities remained committed to an ethos of public relevance, adopting a wider focus on professional and applied disciplines in response to growing industrialisation. The mid nineteenth century also saw a period of significant reform in England; higher education was becoming increasingly secular and the establishment of civic institutions had opened the door to university-industry cooperation (Soysal and Baltaru, 2021). This represents a watershed moment for the role of the university, which Tapper and Palfreyman (2010, p.78) characterise as "the training of experts rather than the education of well-rounded, cultivated gentlemen".

Another landmark moment for the sector arrived with the recommendations of the Committee on Higher Education (1963), more commonly known as the Robbins Report. Chaired by Lord Robbins, the committee advocated for an expansion of higher education provision and parity of esteem across institutions. The report highlighted inequalities within the existing system and argued that degree-level work should be recognised with a degree regardless of the disciplinary focus. In addition, the report recommended a broadening of curricula. The committee recognised the phenomenon as described by Tapper and Palfreyman and felt strongly that the purpose of a modern university was to produce well-rounded graduates with a transferable skillset. The Robbins Report was just one of many similar reports published around that time and, bolstered by a global push for expansion, the recommendations faced little resistance (Scott, 2014). However, their implementation was delayed by the arrival of the binary system in 1965, which formalised the separation of academic and

vocational learning. Despite this being a temporary stay in the adoption of the "Robbins-designed system" of today (Scott, 2014), the binary detour arguably sowed the seeds of anti-vocational rhetoric that remains entrenched in British perceptions.

There are some who argue that the changes set in motion by Robbins were detrimental to the sector (Strohl, 2006). While access has increased exponentially, the process has been uneven, focusing on structural expansion over reflection on its philosophical or ideological place in society (Scott, 1995, p. 23). This has left the university's ethos somewhat unmoored – a concept explored in section 3.7.4.

3.3.2 Navigating the Reputational Hierarchy

In 1973, Trow predicted a massification of higher education, indicating that "not merely the further expansion of the elite university systems, but [...] the growth of popular nonelite institutions" would be required to serve the growing, and increasingly diverse, student population. Two decades later, central institutions (in Scotland) and polytechnics (in England and Wales) were granted university status by the Further and Higher Education Act 1992, from which the nickname "post-92" was born. In official terms, the Act marked the end of the binary education system, unifying funding mechanisms and creating parity between degree-awarding institutions (Croxford and Raffe, 2015). In reality, the merger led to further sector stratification as the newly minted universities took their place at the bottom of the institutional pecking order (Pratt, 1999). Since then, the role of the university has steadily evolved to meet changing societal needs. Increasing alignment of institutional missions and curricula should theoretically lead to an erosion of these invisible boundaries (Scott, 1995, p.1), yet initial perceptions of post-92s remain largely unchanged as the sector continues to be governed by what Croxford and Raffe (2015) call the "iron law of hierarchy".

The phenomenon of academic drift, or the suggestion that vocational institutions have historically sought to emulate elite universities, is often cited as a contributing factor in the departure from the binary system. However, Pratt (1999) warns against interpreting unification as an attempt to establish parity of esteem. Rather, he believes it to be a result of increasing vocationalisation in research-led institutions, which had begun to blur sectoral boundaries. Polytechnics had also demonstrated their value in terms of widening access and workforce development – priorities closely aligned with those of the UK Government. Pratt argues that unification was simply a pragmatic response to a set of circumstances that presented an opportunity to serve a political agenda.

The status hierarchy is also not confined to public opinion but is reflected in the uneven distribution of public funds. Annual SFC allocations are divided into three categories: teaching activities (Table 3.2), research activities (Table 3.3), and innovation and knowledge exchange (Table 3.4). As these figures² illustrate, the allocations reinforce the hierarchy by concentrating the majority of funding on research-led institutions. Funds are reduced with each institutional tier, which compounds this longstanding stratification. This pattern is evident over the last seven years of SFC financial reports and, according to figures presented by Gallacher (2014), has remained fairly stable since at least 2011.

	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	Average
Ancient	30.7%	30.5%	30.9%	30.0%	30.5%	31.9%	31.8%	30.9%
Pre-92	25.9%	25.9%	25.9%	24.9%	24.9%	25.1%	25.5%	25.4%
Post-92	40.3%*	40.5%*	40.1%*	40.7%*	40.2%*	37.7%*	37.3%*	39.5%*
Specialist	3.1%	3.1%	3.1%	4.4%	4.4%	5.3%	5.4%	4.1%

Table 3.2: Funding allocated for teaching activities

*Figure includes annual 5% uplift from Widening Access and Retention Fund

Source: SFC (2019, 2020b, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024a, 2025)

	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	Average
Ancient	69.1%	69.3%	69.5%	69.9%	69.7%	69.6%	69.4%	69.5%
Pre-92	24.3%	24.2%	24.0%	22.5%	22.5%	22.7%	22.9%	23.3%
Post-92	4.6%	4.5%	4.5%	5.7%	6.0%	6.0%	5.9%	5.3%
Specialist	2.0%	2.0%	2.0%	1.9%	1.8%	1.8%	1.9%	1.9%

Table 3.3: Funding allocated for research activities

Source: SFC (2019, 2020b, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024a, 2025)

	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24	2024/25	2025/26	Average
Ancient	38.8%	38.8%	38.8%	38.5%	41.3%	38.0%	38.9%	39.0%
Pre-92	24.1%	24.2%	24.2%	24.0%	24.4%	25.6%	25.4%	24.5%
Post-92	23.8%	23.8%	23.8%	24.3%	21.7%	21.9%	20.4%	22.8%
Specialist	3.1%	3.1%	3.1%	4.4%	4.4%	5.3%	5.4%	4.1%

Table 3.4: Funding allocated for innovation and knowledge exchange

Source: SFC (2019, 2020b, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024a, 2025)

At first glance, Table 3.2 is misleading as it appears that post-92 institutions receive the highest allocation of funding for teaching activities. However, this is the largest group within the sector, with almost as many member institutions as the ancient and pre-92 groups combined. Importantly, the

² SFC source material includes Open University funding, which is not reflected in the figures presented here

figures are artificially inflated by targeted funds to support widening access activities, which are not received by any other tier group, resulting in the misperception that post-92s are better resourced than they are. The allocation of targeted widening access funding also implies an expectation for the newer universities to deliver more inclusive, resource-intensive teaching provision than their ancient and pre-92 counterparts.

As these uneven allocations have reflected a similar split since at least 2011, it appears that funders have fallen into a trap identified by Trow (1973, p. 38), where it is assumed that learning and teaching costs at newer institutions will remain fixed below those of more prestigious universities:

Research is inherently highly expensive. Moreover, there is a tendency everywhere to identify research with the highest standards of higher education, an identification that has a strong component of reality in it. It is research that attracts the most able and creative academic minds, and it is the institutions that recruit these men that gain higher status in any system of higher education. [...] The more ambitious and energetic the new institutions are, the more they will demand the libraries and research facilities, the salary schedules and the other amenities of the old institutions, and the more likely they are to drive their per capita costs up.

This pattern of resource allocation suggests that funders may be more concerned with efficiency than parity. Long-term funding constraints and comparatively fewer opportunities to generate additional income from research outputs also mean there is little scope for newer institutions to emulate the structure or priorities of those with higher status, compounding the self-perpetuating nature of the hierarchy (Croxford and Raffe, 2015; Liyanage, Villalba-Romero and Carmichael, 2024). Such dynamics are also damaging to wider social equity efforts (Reay, 2021) and present a risk of further stratification through policies that disproportionately favour high-status institutions. In a speech delivered in 2017, Professor Sir Peter Scott observed the risks that the hierarchy poses to the sector as a whole:

Talk of the 'best' universities inevitably implies the rest are second-rate. But it is the 'rest' that will always enrol the majority of students, and certainly new groups of students from less privileged backgrounds. It is no surprise that students from more deprived social backgrounds in Scotland (as elsewhere) are concentrated in the colleges and the post-1992 universities. This language also produces perverse policy outcomes. Being in the top 10, 50 or 100 adds not a jot to the real research quality and capability of these universities, however hyped it may be by marketing departments, and it carries the real risk that strategies will be distorted by focusing excessively on the metrics that determine league-table positions. (Scott, in Scottish Government, 2017a, para. 20)

Scott's statement perfectly captures the tension explored in this section: the persistent reputational hierarchy skews institutional priorities and policy outcomes, belies the value that newer universities offer to the sector, and undermines the perceived legitimacy of vocational programmes.

3.3.3 Widening Access and Massification

Trow (1973) describes three higher education systems: elite, mass, and universal. Drawing boundaries between them based on the proportion of school leavers attending university, he suggests that elite systems see enrolments of under 15%. Mass systems cater to a much larger and more diverse student audience, experiencing enrolments of anywhere between 15% and 50%. Above this, the system shifts toward universal access. In this context, the term *massification* refers to the process of transitioning from an elite system to a mass system.

The UK can be considered a mass system based on these criteria, with 36.4% of school leavers entering higher education in 2024. Table 3.5 shows the entry rate for each of the four constituent countries.

England	Northern Ireland	Scotland	Wales
37%	38%	30%	30%

Table 3.5: Higher education entry rate for school leavers in 2024

Source: Bolton (2025)

Trow acknowledges the limitations to global application of his schema, which he frames as a "way of thinking about the development of higher education" rather than a prescriptive framework. As Scott (2019) highlights, there is a lack of theory underpinning Trow's conceptualisation of education systems, and the USA-centric view of higher education as a single level fails to consider binary systems, which are more common in Europe. While this would have made its application to the UK context difficult in 1973, this has been resolved through sector unification in the decades since, so Trow's proposed system boundaries are accepted for the purposes of this thesis.

Mass higher education attendance gained significant momentum following the Robbins Report's call for increased access, though this vision was delayed by the implementation of the binary system. The introduction of the Further and Higher Education Act 1992 and subsequent unification of the sector marked a key turning point, and enrolment rates began to increase. Three years later, Tony Blair famously announced "education is the best economic policy there is" (C-SPAN, 1995, 22:27), and New Labour's agenda in the late 1990s and early 2000s positioned higher education as the key to social mobility and prosperity. However, this arguably backfired in the long term; the push toward university attendance saw UK-domiciled enrolments increase from 926,000 in 1994 to almost 2 million in 2024 (HESA, 1996; 2025b). As raised in chapter two, this accelerated massification and saturated the job market with graduates, eventually raising questions around the cultural value of academic qualifications (Brooks and Everett, 2009; Allais, 2014; Savic, Vecchi and Lewis, 2019; Carpentier, 2021).

Admittedly, Industry 4.0 has compounded the current recruitment crisis in ways Tony Blair was unlikely to have anticipated in 1995. Nonetheless, encouraging such an instrumentalist view of higher education arguably set the wheels in motion toward the commercialised sector we see today.

Another catalyst of massification was policy emphasis on increasing access to higher education for underrepresented groups. Despite sectoral focus shifting away from the upper echelons of society throughout the twentieth century, the perception remained that university study was a right of the middle class. This was underscored by a persistent reputational hierarchy, with affluent applicants disproportionately admitted to elite institutions over those from lower socio-economic backgrounds (Bathmaker *et al.*, 2016; Reay, 2021). The move toward a mass system therefore brought with it a number of initiatives to address such inequalities. This emphasis on widening participation was also a response to the report by the National Committee of Inquiry into Higher Education (1997), commonly known as the Dearing Report. Many of its recommendations focused on increasing provision for disadvantaged groups, including targeted funding for institutions demonstrating a commitment to increasing participation. This is reflected in current SFC allocations, which include an uplift from the Widening Access and Retention Fund for post-92s. In addition to this targeted funding, mechanisms to increase access include contextual admissions policies and articulation programmes developed with further education colleges, which offer an intermediary pathway for underrepresented groups.

The resultant system bears a passing resemblance to the vision articulated by the Robbins Report. However, sector stratification means that parity in terms of learner experience and outcome is yet to be achieved. Social inequalities have persisted as access has increased; students from disadvantaged backgrounds are more likely to attend lower-status institutions, which often has negative implications for their future earning potential compared to graduates of more prestigious universities (Croxford and Raffe, 2015; Carpentier, 2021; Reay, 2021). This is also the group most likely to take on high levels of debt during their studies (Bathmaker *et al.*, 2016), which raises further questions about the equity of the system.

In his recent report titled *Renewing the Alliance for Fair Access*, Professor John McKendrick referred to the government's fair access agenda as a "misnomer" (McKendrick, 2024, p. 23). He points out that national targets focus on entry to university, reasoning that truly fair access must encompass the entire academic journey. As such, McKendrick recommends a recalibration of the agenda, giving equal weight to entry, student experience (including academic achievement, engagement with wider opportunities, access to support services and the impact of financial circumstances on study) and

graduate outcomes. The need for a more holistic approach is reinforced by Salisu, Douglas-Oloyede and Jones (2024), whose *Advance HE* publication *Open Doors, Narrow Corridors?* emphasises looking beyond recruitment to ensure that intentional and inclusive support is embedded across the learning journey for underrepresented groups. However, in response to McKendrick's recommendations, the Scottish Government (2024b) indicated their unwillingness to commit at that time and described their progress on the recommendation as "ongoing".

The expansion of access has also taken place unevenly across the hierarchy (Carpentier, 2021; Reay, 2021), with demands for inclusive teaching provision falling disproportionately on newer institutions. As discussed in section 3.3.2, the uplift from the Widening Access and Retention Fund implies an expectation that they will shoulder the responsibility of widening access activities, despite operating with significantly fewer income streams than research-led institutions. This reinforces a "hierarchy of participation" that sees students from more affluent backgrounds overrepresented in prestigious universities, while those of disadvantaged backgrounds attend lower status institutions (Carpentier, 2021; Reay, 2021).

Rather than fulfilling a democratic promise of a university education, widening access efforts have reinforced the reputational hierarchy and widened the gap in graduate outcomes (Croxford and Raffe, 2015). Moreover, the prevalence of widening participation activities in post-92s has arguably devalued an initiative designed to promote equity. This phenomenon can be seen in graduate apprenticeships; emphasis on upskilling and employability, as well as their frequent association with newer institutions, presents a risk to perceptions of their academic legitimacy. This concept is explored further in section 3.7.1. Widening access initiatives have also contributed to a gap in degree outcomes. Bachan (2017) identified a negative correlation between "good" degrees (first class and 2:1) and students admitted through widening participation schemes. This suggests that learning and teaching provision does not sufficiently meet the needs of those entering university through a non-traditional pathway. In a mass system, it is crucial that universities take into account varying abilities in order to support learning at all stages. This is underscored by findings of the Commissioner for Fair Access, who recommended that the fair access agenda focus on activities to "better prepare disadvantaged candidates [...] for life at university" (McKendrick, 2024, p. 22).

In structural terms, the higher education landscape largely follows the blueprint set out in the Robbins Report. Operationally, however, there has been a significant divergence from its recommendations, and Scott (2014) describes today's sector as a Robbins-designed system that Robbins himself would

struggle to recognise. Challenging the egalitarian vision articulated by the report, the landscape has become increasingly marketised, globalised and pluralistic (Scott, 1995).

3.3.4 Institutional Agency and Managed Compliance

Historically, autonomy in teaching, research and institutional development has been considered an intrinsic part of university operations. However, as Tapper and Palfreyman (2010, pp.41-42) argue, autonomy has always been contingent on financial self-sufficiency, and growing reliance on public funding has invited increasing levels of political steering. External, market-like pressures have also shifted institutional priorities to the extent that the higher education landscape now mimics that of the private sector. This is known as marketisation, which is explored in greater depth in section 3.4.

Universities face immense pressure to satisfy stakeholders from every angle, including increasingly consumerised students and government bodies looking to further policy agendas. As a consequence, institutional agency is at an all-time low, increasingly eroded by managed compliance, which is described as an institution that appears to operate autonomously but is structurally bound by performance metrics and rigid stakeholder expectations (Schulze-Cleven *et al.*, 2017; Scott, 2021). For example, many universities are now caught in a paradox: SFC incentivises innovation through targeted funding streams, yet innovation is increasingly constrained by external metrics imposed by SFC (Beckmann and Cooper, 2013; Research Excellence Framework, 2024). The outcomes of these metrics are often highly visible, impacting league table position and influencing potential applicants when considering where to study. Furthermore, there is a growing trend of student satisfaction scores taken as an indicator of teaching quality, a metric to which Scott (2021) is vehemently opposed. He argues that marketisation has positioned students as consumers and, in this role, they feel entitled to dictate their learning experience. With recruitment strategies often depending on positive student feedback, Scott suggests that many institutions have acquiesced to these demands, with negative consequences for pedagogical practice.

This constraint is also compounded by a rise in managerialism. This model of governance resembles corporate management structures, emphasising efficiency and accountability over academic freedom. These new institutional priorities have reshaped core processes such as programme development and curriculum design, which Macfarlane (2015) attributes to a rise in standardised learning outcomes and academic performativity. Building upon Lyotard's (1984) discussion of performativity in education, Beckmann and Cooper (2013) point to a correlation between managerialism and performativity, which they believe has reduced the value of higher education to scripted outputs and performance metrics.

They also characterise quality assurance mechanisms such as the Research Excellence Framework (REF) as a form of surveillance rather than genuine performance indicators. Collini (2018) expands on this further, highlighting that metrics such as graduate destinations and student retention statistics are often used to draw conclusions about teaching quality, despite the fact that pedagogical practice has little bearing on these outcomes. Burrows (2012) is robust in his critique of what he calls "metric assemblages", arguing that universities are not only modelling market conditions but actively adopting them. Together, these descriptions portray a commercial ideology wherein universities increasingly operate as for-profit businesses and students are viewed as consumers.

Similar managed compliance can be seen in graduate apprenticeships, where institutional agency is both emphasised and constrained. Although universities retain autonomy in curriculum design, the content is shaped by expectations to address an economic agenda. Frameworks also prioritise policy compliance over pedagogical freedom, which contributes to a wider argument that innovation and academic creativity are being stifled in higher education. The graduate apprenticeship model requires institutions to walk a tightrope of stakeholder expectations, while being held accountable for policy alignment, employer recruitment, and the delivery of high-quality learning and teaching. However, these pressures of performativity are unevenly distributed within the sector. Given that prestigious institutions benefit from higher funding allocations and more diverse income streams than post-92s (Liyanage, Villalba-Romero and Carmichael, 2024), they are in a position to strategically disengage from activities perceived as detrimental to their brand. Indeed, the majority of ancient universities have opted to cease graduate apprenticeship delivery in recent years, a trend discussed further in section 3.7.1. This limited institutional agency presents a potential barrier to the long-term viability of the scheme; high-quality apprenticeships rely on newer institutions resisting the systemic pressures that increasingly commodify undergraduate provision.

3.4 Marketisation: The Business of Education

3.4.1 Drivers of Market Behaviours in Higher Education

Over the past thirty years, the higher education sector has become increasingly marketised, forcing universities to adopt operational practices akin to the private sector in order to remain viable. Brown and Carasso (2013) explain that this growing alignment with private sector behaviour was driven by an amalgamation of policy reforms, mass enrolment and globalisation. Funding pressures also played a central role; following the unification of the binary system, competition for supplemental income grew as public funding cuts encouraged universities to pursue alternative revenue streams (Williams, 2016). Combined, these pressures led to a significant shift in institutional priorities and pedagogical

approaches, reshaping the sector into "a service industry that seeks to please student desires" (Scott, 2021).

The introduction of university tuition fees further accelerated marketisation. Following the release of the Dearing Report, the Labour government introduced UK-wide fees of £1000 per annum to attend university. However, this period represents yet another key point of divergence in the Scottish and English systems due to the introduction of the Scotland Act 1998 and the subsequent establishment of a devolved government. These sections therefore follow their markedly different trajectories.

3.4.2 Marketisation in English Universities

The annual tuition fee of £1000 remained in place in England until 2006, when it was increased to £3000. This figure tripled again in 2012, raising the fee cap to £9000 per year. Tuition fees in England have periodically increased since this time, most recently reaching £9535 in academic year 2025/26 (gov.uk, 2024). Like the Scottish system, UK-domiciled students studying in England do not pay for higher education at the point of access. Instead, the majority fund their studies through tuition loans, which are repaid through salary deductions after graduation and treated by many graduates as a tax (Smith, 2023) rather than a debt to be repaid. Although the fee reforms were framed as necessary to secure the long-term sustainability of higher education, a direct consequence of positioning students as paying customers is a rise of consumerist structures across the sector (Scott, 2021).

In England's case, the drivers for marketisation are clear. Tuition fee increases consistently fail to meet the rate of inflation and the shortfall is not covered by government allocations, leaving the majority of English universities in a position where they are forced to charge the maximum annual tuition (Institute for Fiscal Studies, 2024). Given that financially undercutting competitors is not feasible, higher education is now a buyer's market, with students in a significant position of power. This puts pressure on institutions to demonstrate value for money, often using reductive metrics to do so, as raised in section 3.3.4. This is also evident in financial incentives offered to English universities for participating in the Teaching Excellence Framework (TEF), where universities submit data on student experience and attainment in exchange for a rating. These are awarded by the Office for Students (OfS), who describe the TEF as "creat[ing] an incentive to improve by putting a spotlight on the quality of a provider's courses, influencing providers' reputations and informing student choice" (OfS, 2023). Institutions that participate in the TEF are granted a cap uplift, enabling them to charge higher domestic tuition fees than those that do not (gov.uk, 2024).

3.4.3 Marketisation in Scottish Universities

Scottish students were required to pay £1000 per year until 2001, when tuition fees were replaced by an endowment scheme, which doubled the rate to £2000. However, in an effort to minimise barriers to entry, payment could be deferred until after graduation. The endowment scheme further promoted access by offering exemptions to specific groups, including mature students, lone parents and entrants to nursing and midwifery (legislation.gov.uk, 2001). The endowment scheme was abolished in 2008 following the election of the Scottish National Party, and higher education has since remained free for Scottish-domiciled students. Annual tuition fees are capped at £1820 and are paid by SAAS. However, Scottish students who choose to study elsewhere in the UK are liable for the full fee of that system and are responsible for sourcing the relevant funding. Students from other constituent nations are charged their domestic fee rate to study in Scotland.

Although they do not rely on domestic tuition fees in the same way as their English counterparts, Scottish universities are subject to the effects of marketisation in other ways. Firstly, it is important to note that undergraduate study is not free, per se; while there is no cost to the student, public funds cover domestic tuition fees, which means the Scottish Government caps the number of undergraduate places each year. In addition, the stagnant SFC allocations described in section 3.3.2 fall far below the rate of inflation. In real terms, the 2024/25 allocation meant that institutions received 22% less per home-domiciled student compared to 2013/14 (Ogden, 2024). These constraints have led to a growing reliance on recruitment from overseas due to the significantly higher fees for international students, which are not limited by caps. Universities are therefore required to market themselves globally in an effort to make up their financial shortfall. However, the UK's departure from the European Union means that EU-domiciled students are now required to pay the international fee rate, a change that has seen EU student enrolments at Scottish universities fall by 81% since 2016 (Scottish Government, 2025b). Furthermore, new visa rules have led to a notable decline in international student recruitment (Ogden, 2024).

Despite operating within a distinct system, Scottish institutions are subject to a number of UK-wide structures, including the reputational hierarchy. They are also entrenched in the same longstanding narratives around employability and delivering value for money, which means institutional strategy and public perceptions are similarly influenced by metrics such as national league tables and student satisfaction scores. Finally, as discussed in section 3.3.2, public funding is allocated based on activities considered core to university operations, including research, innovation and knowledge exchange, which then acts as a metaphorical carrot for less well-resourced institutions, encouraging strategic

alignment with measurable outputs. This also extends to global rankings, particularly as reliance on international student recruitment increases. Naidoo and Jamieson (2005) warn that market pressures may lead to a breakdown of the teacher-learner relationship due to competing interests – a risk that is amplified in graduate apprenticeships, which carry the expectations of an unprecedented number of stakeholders.

3.5 Sectoral Tensions in Learning Design

In the context of university curricula, learning design does not exist in a vacuum; educational provision is shaped by a number of external pressures, particularly at an undergraduate level (Palfreyman and Tapper, 2014). This also contributes to a change in cultural perceptions of what a university is and the purpose it serves in society. As such, the modern university can be conceptualised as a halfway house, operating somewhere between its historical identity as gatekeeper of knowledge and enquiry and its contemporary role in driving social and economic progress. This section explores a number of tensions across the sector and their impact on how learning is designed, delivered and experienced.

3.5.1 Consumerism and Commodification

The rise in consumerism presents a core tension as many students now view universities as private service providers, which Jabbar *et al.* (2018) capture in an observation of student attitudes: "I've paid my money, give me my degree". According to their findings, educators report increased workloads and cite the student-consumer role as a key source of stress due to an expectation from students to provide 24/7 customer service. The authors argue that in addition to becoming commodified, universities are increasingly centralised, leading to reduced pedagogical autonomy and, crucially, poorer student experiences. The attitudes described by Jabbar *et al.* also highlight transactional perceptions of higher education, with some students seeking the symbolic value of a degree rather than genuine education.

In the context of education, commodification refers to the embedding of market logic in institutional priorities and practices such as curriculum design, thereby reducing a degree to a commodity to be bought and sold. Rising marketisation and managerialism mean that higher education is increasingly framed in terms of efficiency, productivity and value for money. Furthermore, increased focus on the needs of the labour market emphasises employability, transferable skills and quantifiable outcomes that satisfy external stakeholders. Tomlinson and Watermeyer (2022) also attribute this trend of measurable learning outcomes to an increase in credentialism, a concept discussed in greater detail in section 3.7.1. They describe how this puts pressure on institutions to differentiate their offerings,

leading to widespread adoption of an instrumentalist ethos. This has filtered into the curriculum, favouring vocational and skills-based activities over disciplinary depth. Green *et al.* (2013) argue that insistence on credentials reflects a government preoccupation with targets and funding streams. For this reason, they suggest that a degree is not necessarily a reliable indicator of ability. Brown and Souto-Otero (2020) echo this and call for a re-evaluation of the meaning of merit.

The findings of this study reveal the impact these tensions have on graduate apprenticeship provision and so Brown and Souto-Otero's recommendation is revisited in chapter eight. How such pressures shape apprenticeship pedagogy and assessment is then explored in chapter nine.

3.5.2 Modular Curricula and Degree Coherence

For the purposes of this study, modular curricula refer to degree programmes comprising multiple single-semester classes, an approach that has been widely adopted in the higher education sector. Further flexibility is often offered in the form of elective classes, which enable students to "pick and mix" programme content. While expanding the breadth of a curriculum affords students greater agency over their learning, it risks sacrificing disciplinary depth. French (2015) highlights a number of benefits offered by a modular design, including resource efficiencies for institutions and flexibility and mobility for students. However, the author also warns that modularisation carries a risk of fragmenting the learning experience, which she argues can lead to poorer learning outcomes and incoherent degrees. French observes that students' choice of module may be informed by the desire to avoid a particular assessment method rather than its relevance to their degree. This example also underscores how modularisation reinforces credentialism. Although completing the requisite number of academic credits ensures that a degree will be conferred, the transformative potential of its curriculum may be constrained by module choices that prioritise ease over depth.

Wider institutional fragmentation also has a negative impact on learning, which is cited by Palfreyman and Tapper (2014) as a consequence of the sector's increasing alignment with labour market needs. The authors describe how undergraduate provision is shaped by a combination of forces, including widening access initiatives, retention targets, quality assurance metrics and financial constraints. They argue that this results in a disaggregation of institutional priorities, which limits the time and pedagogical freedom required for quality curriculum design. These structural and systemic pressures highlight tensions around negotiation and control of learning outcomes, particularly in the context of apprenticeships, where these are explicitly defined by the labour market.

However, fragmentation is not only visible at a structural level. Clark (2024) points to a technocentric rhetoric in post-Covid learning, which he argues is negatively impacting integrative learning. Clark describes an increase in educational technology and online delivery since the pandemic, which enables students to engage with asynchronous activities in short increments between other commitments. While undoubtedly offering an attractive option for learners seeking flexibility and self-management, this poses a significant risk of superficial engagement, which dilutes educational value. Furthermore, Clark is not alone in raising these concerns; the next section outlines the critical need for robust digital pedagogy in post-pandemic higher education.

3.5.3 Digital Pedagogy and Post-Pandemic Learning

The closure of university campuses in March 2020 meant a sudden pivot from in-person to online teaching, forcing many institutions to accelerate their digital strategy timelines (Anderson, 2020). Borrowing from business terminology, the Covid pandemic can be considered a black swan – an unforeseen event which fundamentally changes a service landscape (Surbhi and Singh, 2024). In this case, the pandemic was a catalyst for substantial changes to learning and teaching. Doughty (2021) claimed that "the online genie is out of the bottle and won't go back in", and it appears he was right.

Almost five years have passed since his comment, and online and hybrid learning now represent a key component of the higher education landscape. Anderson (2020) reflects on the early days of online teaching in the pandemic, describing a sense of "making do" with the digital tools at her disposal. While the author espouses the benefits of online teaching, she emphasises the need for intentional pedagogical design and a specific skillset. Lock *et al.* (2021) agree with this, arguing that digital learning should not be viewed as merely an alternative method to deliver standard teaching practices. This presents a new issue, as many educators still have no formal training in digital pedagogy and so a hangover of "making do" persists. Marshall *et al.* (2024) also point out that this hangover extends beyond the pivot to online learning in 2020, highlighting a decades-long pattern of attempts to integrate technology. They argue that universities often try to force digital tools into their existing teaching approaches, and that the adoption of online teaching is often motivated by efficiency and scalability, or else as a response to labour market needs. While online learning offers benefits in terms of widening participation and cost savings, adopting this delivery model without intentional digital pedagogy risks reinforcing the same instrumentality often seen in traditional teaching methods.

This also poses specific challenges in the context of graduate apprenticeships. Online or hybrid delivery is often framed in terms of the flexibility it offers learners (Norman, Lambert and Partridge, 2025). It

also minimises staffing disruption associated with traditional day-release, which is likely to encourage employer buy-in. Furthermore, it reduces teaching costs, which educators may view as a way to offset the higher overall cost of apprenticeship delivery. However, Serdyukov (2015) warns against the adoption of online teaching as a matter of convenience due to potential consequences for the learning experience. In apprenticeships, this often translates to the erosion of protected study time, which should equate to 20% of the working week. Despite being mandated by the framework, employers do not always honour this. Lester and Bravenboer (2020) found that online delivery often encourages this behaviour, particularly when teaching activities are scheduled outside of typical working hours, forcing apprentices to complete these in their own time. Serdyukov observes that learners often respond to this type of burden by employing an "economy of effort" approach to their studies. This loss of study time therefore means apprentices may (consciously or unconsciously) reduce their engagement to compensate, shifting to a superficial learning approach that undermines the transformative potential of the programme. This reinforces the need for skilled and intentional integration of digital pedagogy that adequately supports apprentice development.

3.6 Vocationalism and Vocationalisation

This section explores the sector's growing alignment with labour market needs and the resultant rise in vocational learning. For clarity, *vocationalism* refers to a programme of study that has been intentionally designed to prepare students for a specific career and which emphasises the practical knowledge and skills required. *Vocationalisation*, on the other hand, is the process of incorporating practical skills into an academic programme to enhance student employability and address labour market needs. The concept of vocationalisation highlights a trend of universities increasingly used to drive economic policy, with academic degrees expected to produce workplace-ready graduates.

Demand for a greater vocational focus in the sector is not a new phenomenon, with calls for closer alignment between curricula and industry needs since the Dearing Report. However, differentiating between these concepts is crucial to understanding how the university's role is evolving. This section will also illustrate how this distinction reveals an interesting paradox: inherent vocationalism carries a perception of being less valuable or desirable than academic pathways, while vocationalisation of academic programmes is often framed as innovation. This highlights the imbalance of cultural esteem between vocational and academic programmes and underscores the disconnect that is central to this chapter.

3.6.1 Vocationalism in Higher Education

While vocational and work-based learning has historically been positioned in further education colleges, there are notable exceptions, with nursing, teacher training and social work taught in universities. These programmes are delivered with a dual focus on theory and practice, combining work-based placements and academic modules closely tied to relevant professional standards. Despite the vital societal role played by graduates within these fields, vocational degree programmes have yet to match their academic counterparts in terms of cultural capital (Findlow, 2012). These dynamics are reinforced by symbols such as the funding classifications by SFC, which group degrees according to their relative delivery cost. Although these are practical distinctions due to factors such as course length and the cost of practice-based elements, they reinforce cultural perceptions of a disciplinary hierarchy, particularly as the most expensive are concentrated in prestigious institutions. Table 3.6 presents a breakdown of vocational degrees by cost of delivery, with group 1 being the most expensive to deliver. The programmes in this table were identified based on HEFCE's (2018) definition of vocational degrees as delivering a narrow skillset and leading to employment in a specific sector.

Price Group	Subject Area
1	Clinical Medicine; Clinical Dentistry; Veterinary Medicine
2	Pharmacy and Pharmacology
3	Pre-Clinical Medicine; Pre-Clinical Dentistry
4	Nursing
5	Architecture; Initial Teacher Training
6	Law; Social Work

Table 3.6: Vocational degree subjects by cost of delivery

Source: SFC (2024b, p. 23)

3.6.2 Vocationalisation of Academic Provision

While the ethos of vocationalism centres around education designed to prepare students for entry to a specific industry, vocationalisation is a systemic trend through which academic provision is reshaped to align with industry needs. Although the authors blur the definition between these two concepts, Lyon and Murray (1993) describe vocationalisation (or what they call new vocationalism) as an expectation of higher education to "deliver the goods" for the labour market. This has led to a widespread shift in institutional priorities, which Tight (2023) argues is often to the detriment of pedagogical aims. He suggests that educational value is increasingly viewed in terms of its utility in the job market and that growing focus on employability limits disciplinary depth and academic rigour in the curriculum.

Furthermore, targeted funding streams implicitly encourage vocationalisation, with the Knowledge Exchange and Innovation Fund offering financial incentives for industry engagement. This is reflective of a broader policy commitment to embed industry-aligned outcomes in higher education activities (Scottish Funding Council, 2025). By encouraging universities to present themselves as centres for innovation, attention is diverted away from teaching provision in favour of employer engagement. In this context, graduate apprenticeship programmes occupy a fascinating space wherein they facilitate the delivery of non-vocational degree disciplines through vocationalised structures. This offers a unique lens through which to examine vocational (and vocationalised) provision in higher education.

3.6.3 Case Study: Nursing Education

Nursing education was delivered through apprenticeships until 1989, when the transition from vocation to profession began (Findlow, 2012). The on-the-job training model was abandoned due to growing concerns within the nursing profession as to its effectiveness; apprenticeships were viewed as outdated and failing to equip trainee nurses with the skills required to perform their duties in a rapidly expanding healthcare sector (Francis and Humphreys, 1999). Although a number of nursing degree programmes had been established across the UK, reform ultimately came about due to Project 2000, a proposal made by the United Kingdom Central Council for Nursing, Midwifery and Health Visiting (UKCC), whose proposed changes were accepted and implemented by the UK Government. This decision was partly pedagogic and partly strategic, driven by professionalisation agendas which sought to elevate the status of nursing within the NHS. The transition to university delivery meant that trainees became students and were paid a bursary instead of a salary. Crucially, it also introduced nurse educators into academia. Described by Findlow (2012) as higher education practitioners, they navigate specific tensions in their dual role.

While vocational degrees are often concentrated in post-92 institutions, nursing education can be considered an outlier, particularly in the Scottish context. The University of Edinburgh established the first UK nursing degree in the 1960s, an example that challenges assumptions about the status of vocationalism within research-intensive institutions. Nonetheless, nursing education has struggled to accrue cultural capital in the sector, leaving it in a "halfway house" between academia and practice (Findlow, 2012; Pursell and McCrae, 2021). Despite the status and epistemic tensions in academia, academicisation adds legitimacy to nursing education in the eyes of the public. This is underscored by a comment from Micheál Martin, the Irish Taoiseach, who suggested that paying student nurses a living wage during the pandemic would "downgrade" their nursing education to an apprenticeship (Meskill, 2021). This largely reflects the cultural academic-vocational divide, wherein apprenticeships

continue to be viewed as inferior, even when compared with an academicised vocational programme. As well as supporting the idea that academicisation lends a sense of legitimacy, this also suggests the existence of a sub-hierarchy in which both academic and academicised provision are favoured over apprenticeships.

Notably, the introduction of a Registered Nurse degree apprenticeship signals a potential reversal in the academicisation of nursing education in England. Developed to align with ambitious targets for clinical apprenticeships set by NHS workforce strategy (NHS England, 2023), these apprenticeships are explicitly framed as vehicles to widen access and diversify the workforce (gov.uk, 2020; The Open University, 2020), more so than any other degree-level apprenticeship. However, the current provision has attracted significant criticism from within the nursing profession. Although the Royal College of Nursing (RCN) has reiterated its support for the concept of apprenticeships in nursing, the organisation has publicly voiced concerns that the model is not fit for purpose (Royal College of Nursing, 2019, 2023, 2024). The RCN suggests that the design and implementation were rushed, which they attribute to a number of structural inconsistencies. They also continue to highlight issues such as funding shortfalls, levy constraints, lack of a coherent workforce strategy, and insufficient clinical placements. The RCN argues that this makes apprenticeships unattractive to employers, compromises educational quality and, crucially, endangers patients.

This reveals a wider issue in terms of quality assurance in apprenticeships. As a profession, nursing is subject to rigorous statutory oversight to ensure that professional standards are upheld, and the sector's infrastructure of regulatory bodies allows quality issues to be quickly identified and addressed. However, the majority of graduate apprenticeships target sectors which are not subject to such regulatory scrutiny. Furthermore, employers may not be in a position to assess the quality of the curriculum and, as a result, issues may go unnoticed. This highlights a potential vulnerability within the model, raising questions around institutional quality assurance mechanisms and the extent of employer contribution beyond the published framework.

As a case study, nursing education exemplifies the core tensions of vocationally-focused degrees that face competing external demands and questions around their academic legitimacy – tensions which are expanding into new areas of higher education with the growth of graduate apprenticeships.

3.7 Pathway or Pedagogy: Reframing Graduate Apprenticeships

Degree apprenticeships are often marketed as "vocational pathways" (Brown, 2025; Laczik *et al.*, 2025), a characterisation this thesis seeks to challenge. To be clear, it does not argue against graduate apprenticeships as a *component* of a vocational pathway. An individual may complete a foundation apprenticeship at school before undertaking a modern apprenticeship, eventually progressing to a graduate apprenticeship. This represents a coherent pathway of vocational learning. Rather, the purpose of this section is to interrogate the legitimacy of graduate apprenticeships as a pedagogical model in its own right. Furthermore, while this thesis advocates for parity of esteem between apprenticeships and full-time degrees, this does not extend to proposing a single operational space. Understandably, the two are considered separate entities due to key structural distinctions, including funding mechanisms, student recruitment and allocation of places. The language used in promotional materials further emphasises this separation:

UCAS is the most cited source for information for applicants across both higher education *and* apprenticeships, highlighting the desire of students to view *both pathways* in a single location. (UCAS, 2021; *emphasis added*)

Given their structural differences, it would be unreasonable to expect graduate apprenticeships and degrees to occupy a single operational space. However, framing them as supernumerary to degrees risks reinforcing misperceptions of apprenticeships as a remedial or second-tier option, which greatly undermines their value.

Having established how the Scottish higher education context was shaped by centuries of symbolic hierarchies, this chapter now poses a pressing question: can graduate apprenticeships be repositioned as a legitimate pedagogy in their own right?

3.7.1 Credentialism and Symbolic Value

Universities operate in a symbolic economy. This plays a significant role in determining perceptions of graduate apprenticeships, whose symbolic value is yet to match that of traditional degrees (UCAS, 2021), especially those awarded by more prestigious institutions. Despite their innovative model and distinct value proposition, the legitimacy of apprenticeships is viewed through a lens of entrenched cultural hierarchies. This section uses Bourdieu's (1986) theory of capital to understand the interplay between credentialism, institutional status and the perceived value of graduate apprenticeships.

Despite their perceived lower status, post-92s have had a profound effect on the sector. These institutions emerged from a history of vocational traditions and play a pivotal role in increasing access to higher education and redefining the boundaries between academia and practice. They also typically prioritise regional needs, focusing on widening participation and fostering links with local industry, qualifying them as drivers of innovative work-based learning, such as graduate apprenticeships. Indeed, with the exception of specialist institutions, all but one of Scotland's universities adopted the scheme following its launch in 2017. Yet, participation has since dwindled in older universities; the most recent intake data reveals that graduate apprenticeships are overwhelmingly delivered by newer institutions, with only one of the four ancient universities in Scotland currently recruiting apprentices (apprenticeships.scot, 2025; Skills Development Scotland, 2025). Table 3.7 breaks down the number of ancient, pre-92 and post-92 institutions that have offered a graduate apprenticeship programme since the scheme's launch.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Ancient (4)	0	2	4	3	1	1	–	–	1
Pre-92 (4)	3	3	3	4	4	4	–	–	4
Post-92 (7)	5	6	6	6	6	6	–	–	6

Table 3.7: Number of institutions enrolling apprentices by tier (2017/18 - 2025/26)

Source: apprenticeships.scot (2025); Skills Development Scotland (2025)

This disengagement from apprenticeships may simply be a strategic decision to divert resources back to more lucrative areas like research, or it may reflect a reluctance to associate with programmes perceived to dilute the institution's academic prestige. The latter is suggestive of broader sectoral tensions around growing curriculum vocationalisation, which may be more readily accepted by newer universities, while research-intensive institutions are more likely to disengage from activities perceived as eroding their academic identity. This also echoes Scott's (1995, p. 170) observation that elite universities tend to "reassert their identity" within mass education systems, which intensifies stratification.

In contrast with the often innovative and experimental approaches taken in post-92s, Talbot (2014) likens education design in a traditional university to a factory production line. Needless to say, the structures defining research-led universities have taken root over centuries and the author acknowledges that these institutions have grown accustomed to operating within a relatively stable environment. It is for this reason, Talbot argues, that some older universities are struggling to evolve at the same rate as their external environments. Moreover, elite universities have not historically

raised their metaphorical heads above the parapet as proactive agents of social change; rather, they have simply accepted change at the demand of external pressures (Pratt, 1999; Silver, 2007).

This reticence to adapt is further compounded by reputational incentives such as preferential funding and global rankings, which reward traditional academic outputs over innovative teaching provision. This results in the expectation that newer institutions will drive progress in policy-aligned areas like widening access and workforce development, yet they must do it in a symbolic economy where their contributions are often regarded as second-rate. The concentration of apprenticeships within post-92s therefore presents a double-edged sword: on one hand, it underscores their commitment to driving policy agendas, on the other, it reinforces perceptions of apprenticeships as a remedial option.

Credentialism introduces an additional layer of complexity to this dynamic. This refers to a reliance (either by an individual or a society) on qualifications as a measure of intelligence, competence and employability. In the context of British higher education, this concept is often enmeshed with perceptions around the prestige of an institution. Therefore, despite the focus on industry relations and employability in newer institutions, their lower status may mean such efforts are devalued by credentialist employers. Tight (2019) suggests that when making recruitment decisions, employers may view credentials not only as evidence of disciplinary knowledge but as a marker of status:

Some are getting a Rolls-Royce higher education, others a BMW higher education and others a Ford higher education. [...] There is nothing wrong with any of these cars or higher education experiences, but we all – policy-makers and employers especially – know the difference.

This observation reinforces the notion that the status of the awarding institution is central to the prestige of a credential. This goes beyond a simple preference for educated employees, reflecting a deeper-rooted cultural understanding of degrees as status symbols. This also implies that the value of a degree relates less to disciplinary area and more to institutional affiliation. It therefore follows that graduate apprenticeships, which are largely offered by newer universities, will be viewed as "Fords" due to their delivery context rather than their content.

The reputational hierarchy also creates a perception that education quality is linked to institutional prestige, which perpetuates the marginalisation of new institutions. In turn, this harms the perceived legitimacy of work-based and vocational programmes, despite the demonstrable benefits outlined in chapter two. However, the hierarchy is deeply ingrained in British higher education and Croxford and Raffe (2015) suggest it is unlikely to weaken without overhauling core elements of the sector, such as funding allocations and student recruitment. As there is little enticement for the most well-resourced

institutions to lobby for such changes, the status quo will likely endure. This hypothesis is supported by Scott (1995, p. 169), who observes that "binary systems never disappear; their boundaries merely shift".

The dominance of post-92s in graduate apprenticeship delivery also presents an interesting paradox that raises questions around the cultural value of work-based learning within universities. Bourdieu's (1986) theory of capital offers a robust framework for this discussion, enabling exploration of this phenomenon from the perspectives of cultural, social, and symbolic capital. In a university context, cultural capital is found in institutional prestige, disciplinary knowledge and research impact. Cultural capital remains concentrated around the ancient universities, which are the best resourced in terms of finances and research outputs – two factors that influence global rankings. This reinforces the notion that traditional degrees hold more academic legitimacy than vocational routes. Student decision-making is influenced by cultural capital within the hierarchy, as evidenced in a study by the City & Guilds Group (2020), which found that the majority of respondents would opt to pursue a full-time degree despite the apprenticeship model better aligning with their goals or circumstances. A study by UCAS (2021) also revealed that 76% and 66% (respectively) of respondents associated the terms *prestigious* and *well-respected* with university degrees. In contrast, 4% associated the terms with apprenticeships.

Second in Bourdieu's theory is social capital, which can be seen in the networks and opportunities available to an individual due to their educational background. Institutions at the top of the hierarchy attract high-performing (and often privileged) students, creating elite networks that grant access to exclusive opportunities, which contributes to universities perpetuating social inequalities (Bathmaker *et al.*, 2016; Reay, 2021).

Finally, the most important of these elements to the focus of this thesis is symbolic capital, which refers to perceptions and recognition. In higher education, this is seen in the ability of a degree to open specific doors due to inferences made about what it represents. Brancaleone and O'Brien's (2011) critique of learning outcomes as commodified "sign values" is closely aligned to this framing of credentials as symbolic capital, with both arguments highlighting education as increasingly valued in terms of what it represents to external stakeholders. In Bourdieu's terms, the symbolic capital of credentials can enhance status and academic legitimacy in the hierarchy. Brancaleone and O'Brien make a similar comparison in the context of measurable learning outcomes, arguing that they do not necessarily indicate transformative learning: "While appearances seduce, they simultaneously deflect

from reality and meaning". In short, degrees appear to evidence meaningful learning but, in reality, often serve as a commodity for the employment market.

This implies that the institutional hierarchy is sustained, at least in part, through credentialism and symbolic signifiers. A hierarchy that presents post-92s and, by extension, apprenticeships as inherently less valuable than their traditional counterparts. So far, this chapter has presented the tangible impact of newer institutions' position in the hierarchy, specifically in terms of funding allocation and operational pressures. The application of Bourdieu's framework reveals further implications, including the risk that potential apprentices and employers are dissuaded from engaging due to a perceived lack of symbolic capital. Yet symbolic capital is not something that can be easily redistributed within the sector (Carpentier, 2021); it requires a significant investment of time and money to establish a portfolio of tradition, networks and outputs to rival institutions at the top – resources that are disproportionately limited within newer universities. This also presents a catch-22 for post-92s: even if they were to invest in traditional academic outputs, their efforts may continue to be undervalued due to ingrained perceptions of their low symbolic weight. The implication of this affects not only institutional priorities but wider discourse around the value and legitimacy of apprenticeships.

3.7.2 Access and Retention

A graduate apprenticeship is a full-time degree in every sense; it is simply delivered in a dual learning environment. Yet frequent characterisation as an alternative pathway positions the scheme alongside non-traditional study options such as part-time and distance learning, or articulation programmes designed to transition learners from further to higher education. While they share some similarities in terms of access (such as flexible entry requirements through RPL), their pedagogy differs significantly, offering an integrated experience that challenges traditional delivery models.

Cavigioli (2019) highlights that part-time undergraduate students often express feelings of loneliness due to fragmented support and limited opportunities for face-to-face engagement. Articulation routes such as 2+2 programmes, where students complete two years at college and two years at university, also result in lower completion rates due to a lack of curriculum continuity and inadequate preparation for the transition between further and higher education (Christie, Barron and D'Annunzio-Green, 2013; Scottish Funding Council, 2020a). In contrast, graduate apprenticeship frameworks emphasise wraparound support, and the dual learning environment aims to foster coherence between academic and professional spaces. This aspect of the model underscores a pedagogical strategy focused on learning continuity and targeted development (Skills Development Scotland, 2018).

However, equity is a concern, with the scheme's impact on widening access best described as uneven. Despite alignment with national agendas such as the Fair Access in Scotland initiative, the only notable example of increased access is the application of RPL, which has opened the door to apprenticeships for many individuals not in possession of the standard entry qualifications (Hughes and Saieva, 2019). While policy documents imply increased access as a benefit of apprenticeships (Scottish Government, 2017b; Skills Development Scotland, 2021b), intake data highlights a persistent underrepresentation of minority ethnic and disabled learners, as well as individuals from economically deprived areas (Skills Development Scotland, 2025).

Retention has been identified as an ongoing issue across both graduate and degree apprenticeship programmes (Rowe *et al.*, 2017; White, 2023; Skills Development Scotland, 2025). In 2019/20, 6.1% of the undergraduate intake in Scotland opted to exit their degree early. This rises to 9.8% of mature students, which HESA defines as an individual aged 21 or over at the time of enrolment. In contrast, 43.4% of the graduate apprenticeship intake exited early, rising to 47.3% of mature apprentices. This is outlined in Table 3.8.

	Enrolments	Early Leavers	Early Exit Rate
Undergraduate (Total)	35,670	2,167	6.1%
Undergraduate (Mature)	10,025	985	9.8%
Apprenticeship (Total)	1,160	503	43.4%
Apprenticeship (Mature)	943	446	47.3%

Table 3.8: Early exit rate of full-time and GA entrants (2019/20)

Source: HESA (2022); Skills Development Scotland (2025)

3.7.3 Evolving Beyond Instruments of Policy

Graduate apprenticeships occupy a distinct space in the Scottish higher education context, positioned at the intersection of economic policy, widening access agendas and apprenticeship reform. At their launch in 2017, they were framed as a strategic response to urgent skills shortages and employability concerns (Lambert, 2016; Skills Development Scotland, 2023). This reflects a longstanding pattern in the UK skills agenda, wherein work-based initiatives are introduced as targeted solutions to challenges in the labour market.

However, analysis of past iterations highlights the limitations of this policy-driven and instrumentalist approach. As outlined in chapter two, a number of work-based initiatives were launched and abolished by the government, all characterised by their myopic aims and a lack of educational depth (Evans *et*

al., 2025). Historic schemes received criticism for prioritising work experience over the development of transferable skills. They also attracted variable levels of employer engagement, though Fuller and Unwin (2011) partly attribute this to an institution-led recruitment model that created a misalignment of training and workplace needs.

Similar trends are also evident in graduate apprenticeships, particularly around employer engagement and the subsequent impact on learning experience (Chadwick, Dimungu Hewage and Hazzam, 2025). Moreover, their positioning in higher education adds a further layer of complexity, pulling them into longstanding debates of academicisation and vocationalisation (Esmond and Atkins, 2022). Are they university-endorsed workplace training? Are they full-time degrees repurposed for delivery in the workplace? Such a lack of epistemic clarity was a common feature in historic initiatives, which arguably failed due to policy ambitions that outpaced the development of robust educational models. Again, this pattern appears to be repeated in recent provision, as evidenced in section 3.6.3. Criticism of the Registered Nurse degree apprenticeship from the RCN (Royal College of Nursing, 2019, 2023, 2024) indicates that its design and implementation were rushed in order to meet ambitious workforce targets (NHS England, 2023). These concerns imply that policy aims have once again outrun coherent educational frameworks, risking the scheme's long-term sustainability.

This uncertainty extends to apprenticeship funding arrangements. Chapter two described a number of changes to the administration and resource management of the scheme, which has seen it grow more closely aligned with the funding process for full-time programmes. This could indicate that apprenticeships are now viewed as embedded in higher education provision rather than a standalone offering. However, the withdrawal of key skills funding and stagnant SFC allocations suggest that the realities of apprenticeship delivery are not understood by funders, which has raised concerns around long-term sustainability (Jackson, 2025). This also serves as a reminder of the scheme's vulnerability, echoing the cyclical pattern of work-based initiatives shaped by short-term economic need rather than long-term educational planning.

Despite these challenges, graduate apprenticeships remain central to the national skills strategy and, as frameworks expand into new sectors, they are poised to deliver considerable value in terms of workforce development. Yet, a question that remains unresolved is the rationale for their positioning in universities, and their educational purpose beyond sector-specific competencies. Clarifying this is crucial if the scheme is to break the mould of previous initiatives and thrive as a coherent educational

model. This thesis therefore seeks to advance understanding of graduate apprenticeships' pedagogical foundations to support their long-term development.

3.7.4 Curriculum Design for Public Good

The civic mission has become steadily deprioritised by many universities as marketisation has shifted institutional focus (McCann, Hutchison and Adair, 2022), and this is also evident in curriculum design. The authors observe that the UK and devolved governments are the sector's most influential external stakeholders, which steers the focus of curricula toward economic development. Alves and Tomlinson (2020) examine higher education through the lens of "public good", finding that curriculum design in England defines public good as alignment with labour market needs. In contrast, they highlight that Portuguese policy discourse places far less emphasis on higher education as an economic driver, and universities continue to position themselves as serving civic and intellectual purposes.

In a UK context, Hall and Smyth (2016) cite the "law of value" as a barrier to higher education as a social good. While Chickering and Gamson argued in 1987 that good teaching relies on meaningful teacher-student engagement, Hall and Smyth describe how, three decades later, this relationship has been subsumed by growing demands to generate value through measurable learning outputs. This often results in a transactional approach to education design, highlighting its narrow conceptualisation in the modern sector, which leaves little space for more civic-minded purposes. It also invites further scrutiny of the design process and so chapter nine examines the implications for apprenticeship value when pedagogical best practice is constrained by managed compliance and market-driven priorities.

3.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter examined the positioning of graduate apprenticeships within the wider higher education landscape, tracing the evolution of British universities from a cluster of elite institutions to a stratified mass system shaped by marketisation and government intervention. By analysing the historical and structural context, it illustrated how a persistent hierarchy influences institutional priorities, resource allocation and cultural perceptions of legitimacy. The chapter also explored how massification has reshaped the role of higher education in society, contributing to increasingly instrumental, market-oriented operations. Managerialism and a reliance on performance metrics were shown to constrain academic agency and foster a culture of managed compliance. The pedagogical aims of graduate apprenticeships were then considered in relation to the hierarchies, agendas and wider debates that inform cultural understanding of their legitimacy. Their frequent association with newer institutions

and framing as a remedial pathway were shown to exacerbate existing misperceptions, reinforcing the need for greater clarity around their educational purpose and epistemic position.

Overall, this chapter provides essential context for understanding how graduate apprenticeships are shaped by the environment in which they operate. Chapter four now turns to the concept of learning, drawing on key literature to establish a working definition and explore how individuals learn in an apprenticeship.

Chapter 4: Learning in Graduate Apprenticeships

When you are learning to drive a car, is the act of driving a learning process, or an outcome of learning?

– Biggs (1999)

4.1 Chapter Overview

As the culmination of the extended literature review, this chapter presents a conceptual foundation for understanding how knowledge is constructed within graduate apprenticeships. First, a working definition of learning is established by drawing on Jarvis' (1987) notion of disjuncture to emphasise transformation as a central feature, which then underpins an exploration of learning as both a process and an outcome. Philosophical perspectives are then examined, highlighting how teaching practice is shaped by our individual understanding of learning. In addition, Marton and Säljö (1976) provide a useful framework for understanding how students engage with academic activities, and the utility of Kolb's experiential cycle is critiqued in relation to apprenticeship design.

By examining these perspectives, this chapter clarifies how learning is conceptualised within the study and establishes a theoretical grounding for the analysis of apprenticeship pedagogy in chapter nine.

4.2 Defining Learning

The term *learning* defies precise definition because it is put to multiple uses. Learning is used to refer to (1) the acquisition and mastery of what is already known about something, (2) the extension and clarification of meaning of one's experience, or (3) an organized, intentional process of testing ideas relevant to problems. In other words, it is used to describe a product, a process, or a function. (Smith, 1982, p. 34)

In the face of these complexities, this thesis borrows its definition from Jarvis (1987), who suggests that learning arises from moments of disjuncture. The author describes this as the point at which our knowledge or assumptions are disrupted by new experience, compelling us to reconstruct meaning. This perspective also extends the constructivist understanding of learning; Jarvis argues that not all experience is meaningful, specifically identifying disruptive experience as a catalyst for change. While this thesis acknowledges the merits of informal or incidental learning, its purpose is to examine the value of formal education and therefore focuses on what Tough (1979, p. 1) calls "highly deliberate learning".

4.3 Learning: Process or Product?

Biggs (1999) uses the example of driving a car to raise the question of whether learning should be considered a process or a product. Does the process of driving constitute learning, or the outcome of being able to drive? Drawing such a distinction is crucial to this chapter, as it reflects broader sectoral tensions around education design. Conceptualising learning as a process implies transformation and incorporates intentional practices such as reflexivity and active engagement in meaning-making. In contrast, viewing learning as a means to an end arguably diminishes its capacity for transformation. Brancaleone and O'Brien (2011) explain this using Marx's notion of commodity fetishism, arguing that conceptualising learning as a product imbues it with a symbolic value that is misaligned with its reality. They characterise measurable learning outcomes as fetishised commodities that appear to represent meaningful achievement but, in reality, serve as a commodity for the labour market. This perspective reinforces concerns of instrumentality in learning when viewed as a product, which may diminish the transformative potential of the learning process.

These tensions are amplified in graduate apprenticeships due to the added complexity presented by their tripartite structure. While apprentices are outwardly framed as active participants in steering their own development (Skills Development Scotland, 2018), the addition of their employer as a key stakeholder introduces a new power dynamic to the typical higher education learning model. Dillard, Sisco and Collins (2024) posit that such power dynamics can dictate what knowledge is considered valuable, which may lead to the apprentice's development becoming a negotiation between employer expectations and their own goals. The framework approach used in graduate apprenticeships also constrains the extent of learner input due to the requirement for curricula to align with the prescribed learning outcomes. Drawing on Brancaleone and O'Brien's argument, this can be considered an example of commodity fetishism, wherein the underlying reality of structural constraints is masked by the guise of learner agency.

To conclude, Biggs' question can be answered by expanding his own definition of learning: effective learning is conducted through a transformative process of meaning construction through reflection, interpretation, and application. However, this thesis recognises that the central tensions of higher education design do not exist in a vacuum, and the commodification of learning is driven by external factors. In the context of this thesis, the process-product tension is not abstract; rather, it is a crucial distinction in apprenticeship delivery wherein employer priorities risk overshadowing learner agency.

4.4 The Philosophy of Learning

Crotty (1998, p. 10) defines ontology as the exploration of "the structure of reality". In short, ontology asks: *what is real?* Although generally discussed in the context of research methodology, this framing of ontology can be applied to the act of learning. This offers a useful lens through which to examine whether learning is best understood as a process of personal transformation, a relational practice, or a quantifiable outcome. Certainly, the answer to this question depends on an educator's perspective. Proponents of social constructionist pedagogy would emphasise learning as an ongoing negotiation of meaning within a social context. On the other hand, someone of a more instrumentalist view may reify learning into defined, measurable outputs. In practice, these perspectives underpin curriculum design and inform what constitutes success in higher education.

While ontology focuses on what we know, epistemology is concerned with "how we know what we know" (Crotty, 1998, p. 3), which raises practical questions around how learning is evidenced and legitimised. Kang (2007) illustrates this in practice through a USA-based study of elementary science teachers. Drawing on Kinchin's epistemological spectrum, Kang demonstrates through three distinct epistemological positions the different ways in which teachers interpret student ideas. The study highlights the interaction between epistemological perspective and teaching practice, and how this shapes learning validation.

This discussion is extended into a higher education context by Samarji and Hooley (2015), who argue that learning and teaching should be viewed as an ontological-epistemological discourse. They frame ontology as beliefs and assumptions that form an educator's practitioner identity, and epistemology as what constitutes knowledge. This, in turn, informs their perception of good practice. The authors also posit an interdependence between being and knowing, with each informing the other. The study reports a notable response from educators when pedagogy shifts from teacher- to learner-centric, requiring them to reconcile their ontological beliefs about teaching with epistemological approaches that centre learner agency.

In ontological terms, graduate apprenticeships are framed as relational and experiential, offering the opportunity for apprentices to learn through their professional practice. Epistemologically, however, the legitimacy of this is measured against prescribed outcomes and evidenced through standardised metrics. This presents a disconnect, with apprenticeships positioned as vehicles for transformative learning (Skills Development Scotland, 2016b), yet stifled by a narrow definition of success. Examining

learning through ontological and epistemological lenses highlights the need for greater philosophical coherence in the design of learning activities and outcomes.

4.5 Approaches to Learning

Another key dimension is the ways in which individuals engage with learning activities. In a seminal study, Marton and Säljö (1976) demonstrated that understanding of a text varied between students due to qualitatively different ways of working; while some focused on simply memorising the text, others sought to interpret its meaning. These differences in intention produced distinct outcomes, forming the basis for the characterisation of *deep* and *surface* learning.

In surface learning, material is studied at a superficial level, and no deeper meaning is sought (Marton and Säljö, 1976). This approach is characterised by an intention to memorise the content rather than to relate or critically evaluate ideas, and an individual will absorb only the information required for a desired output – for example, passing a test (Dolmans *et al.*, 2016). As Teng *et al.* (2019) observe, this can lead to underdeveloped communication and critical thinking skills, which they identify as having a negative impact on graduate employability. In contrast, deep learning seeks to identify underlying meaning and is often driven by intrinsic interest in the subject. Drawing on Dweck's (1999) distinction between performance and learning goals, Yorke (2006) associates this approach with a desire to learn rather than simply perform by achieving a passing grade. Biggs (1993) later identified a third approach: strategic (or achieving) learning. This involves the tactical use of both deep and surface learning approaches, which is often adopted when an individual seeks a high ratio of achievement to effort (Yorke, 2006). Here, learners operate with an overarching surface approach but engage in deeper learning when deemed necessary to meet an objective.

Importantly, these are not fixed; Biggs (1999) emphasises their fluid nature, asserting that a learning approach is not an inherent personality trait. Rather, it reflects the current conditions under which an individual is studying, with surface learning often a reaction to circumstance or external pressures. This is supported by Yorke (2006), who posits that cultural or financial pressures may also dictate the level of priority a learner assigns to their studies. Furthermore, Haggis (2003) highlights that the deep-strategic-surface framework is often applied in practice without due criticality. Educators may seek to "induce" deep learning approaches through tactical curriculum design, which she argues overlooks the complex pressures faced by students, particularly in mass education systems.

This relationship between approach and environment is captured by Biggs' (1993) 3P model, which describes the presage, process and product of learning. Presage factors include characteristics of both the learner and the learning environment. These shape the learning process, informing the approach taken and, in turn, the quality of student outcomes. The model frames learning as systemic, showing how a change in context can shift how a task is perceived.

In the years since the learning approach framework was established, subsequent research has mapped a hierarchy to illustrate how deep and surface engagement shape an individual's understanding of the material. This is shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Conceptualisation of learning
Source: Adapted from Marton and Säljö (1997)

Astin's (1984) theory of student involvement adds a behavioural dimension to the process, arguing that academic development is proportional to the quantity and quality of effort invested in learning activities. Through this lens, a surface approach is less likely to result in transformative learning than a deep approach, which requires sustained engagement. From an education design perspective, this theory shifts the pedagogical focus from teacher to learner, highlighting the importance of observable participation. This emphasis on learner participation reflects a central element of value construction in apprenticeships, which is revisited in chapter nine.

4.6 Intersectionality and the Apprentice Learner

The concept of intersectionality originates in Black feminist scholarship, with the term introduced by Crenshaw (1989) to describe how race and gender overlap to compound marginalisation. She explains

that individuals can be "multiply-burdened", experiencing cumulative disadvantage due to negative interactions between race, gender and wider societal biases. Although initially developed to address the erasure of Black women's experiences, intersectional analysis has been expanded across various fields as a means of understanding how social and structural conditions shape lived experience.

There is a pervasive assumption that frames the typical university entrant as a middle-class school-leaver with limited external commitments (Sykes, 2021, p.81), and degree provision is often designed to this end. Learners whose context diverge from this norm may experience additional pressures that shape the presage factors described in Biggs' (1993) 3P model, influencing the extent to which deep engagement is feasible. In higher education research, discussion of intersectionality tends to focus on what Hanson and Fletcher (2021) call the "trinity" of gender, race and social class. However, the authors argue that this lens is too narrow for adult education, highlighting other structural and contextual factors that play a central role in shaping the learning experience. Their call to look "beyond the trinity" is particularly relevant to the graduate apprenticeship context; as discussed in chapter two, cohorts are consistently male-dominated, predominantly white and overrepresented in the most affluent SIMD quintiles. In other words, the traditional categories of gender, race and class may not accurately capture the typical apprentice experience. On the other hand, research on non-traditional university entrants highlights how age, personal circumstances and institutional culture influence opportunities, engagement and retention (Merrill, 2015; Read, Archer and Leathwood, 2003).

Within apprenticeships, the majority of learners are over the age of 25 (Skills Development Scotland, 2025) and are therefore more likely to have childcare responsibilities than a typical undergraduate (Public Health Scotland, 2024). Parallel work and study is also found to have a negative impact on academic achievement (Moore, Birdi and Higson, 2019), yet apprentices work full-time alongside their programmes. Furthermore, the majority of apprentices enrol as an existing employee, with an established professional identity. This presents an additional layer of risk as employers may position them as an employee first, with their studies viewed as supplementary – or even inconvenient (Brockmann, Clarke and Winch, 2010).

Recent conversations around degree apprenticeships reinforce the need to widen the intersectional lens. Looking at inclusive engagement, Nottingham and Mao (2023) show how apprentices navigate various communities of practice spanning the workplace, university and peer networks, each carrying distinct expectations and power dynamics. The authors describe the role these overlapping contexts play in identity construction and supporting apprentices to engage in learning, highlighting that

inclusive engagement depends on how seamlessly learners can move between these communities and navigate their competing demands. Sohdi (2026) expands on this, positioning apprenticeships within a broader landscape of symbolic hierarchies and intersectional identities. He argues that the learning experience is shaped by a number of overlapping factors that create variable conditions within a single programme, emphasising the need for pedagogies that recognise the "complex social positions" apprentices occupy. These studies underscore the need to widen the conventional race-gender-class lens to identify the axes of identity that best capture the typical graduate apprentice experience. These are arguably age, educational background, caring responsibilities and employer expectations – overlapping social conditions that determine an individual's ability to meaningfully participate in learning (Moores, Birdi and Higson, 2019; Sohdi, 2026).

4.7 Experiential Learning

Experiential learning is an established and respected component of adult learning, which acts as a bridge between theory and practice (Miettinen, 2000; Dillard, Sisco and Collins, 2024). The approach is grounded in constructivism and challenges the idea that knowledge can be passed from teacher to learner (Rasmussen, 1998), instead framing learning as the process of constructing meaning through engagement and reflection. This is a core principle of graduate apprenticeships, which emphasise learning through experience by situating 80% of programme delivery in the workplace.

4.7.1 Experiential Learning Theory

Citing Dewey, Lewin and Piaget as the inspiration for his experiential learning theory, Kolb (1984) suggests that individuals enter a learning environment with their own understanding of a subject, which has been developed to varying degrees through experience. This understanding is then re-shaped through reflection and engagement. Kolb argues that a key responsibility of a teacher is not to transmit new ideas but to revise existing ones. He proposes a four-step iterative cycle of concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualisation and active experimentation. Through repeated engagement with these steps, learners continuously reconstruct their understanding.

Furthermore, Kolb emphasises that it is not enough to simply acknowledge an experience, but rather a learner must engage in a two-step process of *grasping* and *transforming* it into knowledge. He also proposes a number of different learning styles according to how an individual grasps and transforms information, emphasising that effective learning demands the ability to pivot between each style as needed.

These proposed learning styles are outlined below in Table 4.1.

Learning Style	Grasped By	Transformed By	Cycle Stage
Diverging	Apprehension	Intention	CE/RO
Assimilating	Comprehension	Intention	AC/RO
Converging	Comprehension	Extension	AC/AE
Accommodating	Apprehension	Extension	CE/AE

Table 4.1: Kolb's learning styles

Source: Adapted from Burke (2020, p. 32)

The theory has had a significant impact on scholarship and is now ubiquitous in the field of experiential learning (Morris, 2020). However, it has received criticism, particularly toward early iterations of the model. Miettinen (2000) characterises Kolb's work as an inadequate rehash of Dewey and Lewin, describing it as "epistemologically highly problematic". He also voices concern that the ubiquity of the approach risks undermining the legitimacy of adult education research through association with what he considers to be a flawed conceptualisation of learning. Another outspoken critic is Fenwick (2001), who argues that Kolb's theory places too much emphasis on the role of rational intention yet overlooks emotional and unconscious dimensions of the learning process. She accuses the model of reducing learning to a binary process, highlighting that it fails to account for the social and cultural elements that shape experience (Fenwick, 2003) – concerns which have been echoed by others more recently (Garraway and Volbrecht, 2011; Mughal and Zafar, 2011).

In 2015, Kolb released an updated version of his experiential learning theory and credited Vygotsky as a key influence, highlighting his acknowledgement of the social and cultural dimensions of learning. Since then, the theory has been incrementally revised to reflect the changing landscape of education and now incorporates elements such as online learning. Despite the limitations of Kolb's theory, there is evidence of its value in professional preparation. Eisenberg, Walles and Long (2024) describe the benefits in the context of student nursing educators who adopted Kolb's cycle to scaffold learning activities and, ultimately, support their transition into a teaching role. Furthermore, Burch *et al.* (2019) provide empirical support for continued use of this approach, observing that it consistently leads to better learning outcomes than traditional methods, particularly in terms of students' cognitive development.

It would seem, then, that the model serves as a flexible starting point for experiential learning design as opposed to a definitive framework. Dillard, Sisco and Collins (2024) support this, illustrating how the approach has been adapted and expanded to suit a range of contexts. Indeed, Kolb himself has

confirmed the model to be illustrative rather than prescriptive, intended as part of a holistic scheme of experiential learning (Kolb and Kolb, 2018, 2024).

Applied in the context of graduate apprenticeships, the theory's emphasis on individualism highlights a unique tension. Referring back to Dillard, Sisco and Collins' (2024) observation of workplace power dynamics dictating what knowledge is considered valuable, learners in this context must reconcile the highly personal process of transforming experience into knowledge with the immediate demands of the workplace. This reinforces the need for a dynamic pedagogy that reflects the realities of work-based learning, accommodating both individual development and organisational needs.

4.7.2 Active Learning

Bonwell and Eisen (1991) describe active learning as "instructional activities involving students doing things and thinking about what they are doing" and, as such, the approach represents a cornerstone of experiential education. As Chickering and Gamson (1987) summarise: "Learning is not a spectator sport".

Recognising that not all learners respond to transmission-based teaching methods, Bonwell and Eisen stress the importance of active participation in the form of discussion, analysis and formative assessment. Additionally, Biggs (1999) suggests that such activities can narrow the gap between deep and surface learners by forcing the latter to engage in speculation. While acknowledging that the nature of active learning makes it difficult to empirically measure attainment, Prince (2004) reports improved student engagement, critical thinking and information retention.

Within apprenticeships, active learning takes a different form. With 80% of the programme situated in the workplace, apprentices are already engaged in "learning by doing". However, their immersion in practice does not necessarily translate to deeper learning without the scaffolding of intentional pedagogy, which connects day-to-day experience and abstract theory through meaningful reflection. This structure ensures that routine workplace tasks stimulate deeper learning, presenting a key distinction between experiential learning and learning from experience. As Kolb's cycle suggests, experience alone does not lead to transformative learning, and active learning provides a pedagogical bridge between "doing" and "learning".

Irons (2017) demonstrates the adoption of active learning in practice. Reflecting on the design and delivery of a degree apprenticeship, the author describes how a heavy emphasis on active learning

positively benefitted learners by bridging the gap between theory and practice. However, he notes a misalignment between this labour-intensive approach and the pedagogy preferred by the wider institution, which created tensions around workload and efficiencies. This highlights the challenge of embedding effective apprenticeship pedagogy within traditional university approaches. This thesis advocates for parity between graduate apprenticeship and mainstream provision, and Irons' account gives weight to the argument for an overall reduction in didacticism. Embedding active learning across undergraduate teaching activities would be a step toward resolving the institutional tensions Irons describes by repositioning apprenticeship pedagogy as parallel to traditional education design. In this sense, Irons' account emphasises apprenticeships' potential as not only pedagogical innovation but a catalyst for broader curricular reform.

4.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter has established learning as a complex and potentially transformative process, showing how it can be shaped by factors such as the teacher's assumptions about their role in the process and how the learner engages with study. Conceptualisations of learning as a process and a product were explored, illustrating how the complex power dynamics in graduate apprenticeships can amplify this tension. Examination of philosophical perspectives then highlighted how different ontological and epistemological approaches inform teaching practice. Additionally, the chapter explored how external factors can shape an individual's approach to engaging with learning activities. Finally, the principles of experiential and active learning were outlined, reiterating the importance of intentional pedagogy in work-based learning.

4.9 Conclusion: Negotiating Policy, Practice and Pedagogy

By examining graduate apprenticeships from three key perspectives, chapters two, three and four have established a multi-dimensional foundation for the study. Chapter two traced the policy context of the apprenticeship scheme, establishing a comprehensive overview of its potential and limitations in the national skills landscape and presenting the compelling value proposition offered by graduate apprenticeships compared to full-time degrees. Chapter three examined the reputational hierarchies and symbolic economy of British higher education, demonstrating how graduate apprenticeships are shaped in a stratified mass system. Despite their introduction as a response to economic concerns and framing as a vocational pathway, critical evaluation revealed a pedagogically responsive model that warrants greater integration into mainstream provision. Chapter four introduced a pedagogical dimension by exploring key theories as they relate to apprenticeship learning. The discussion in this

chapter suggests that the transformative potential of these programmes lies in intentional pedagogy and coherent support that bridges theory and practice.

This extended literature review offers a detailed overview of how graduate apprenticeships operate within policy, sectoral and pedagogical contexts, which establishes the basis for the empirical analysis to follow. First though, chapter five outlines the research design.

Chapter 5: Research Design

A balanced perspective cannot be acquired by studying disciplines in pieces but through pursuit of the consilience among them.

– Wilson (1998)

5.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter provides a detailed account of the research design, beginning with the philosophical foundations, which are grounded in a relativist ontology and constructivist epistemology. Collectively, these support the study's interpretivist theoretical perspective, which informed the decision to adopt a methodology of interpretive phenomenological analysis. The chapter also outlines the research methods adopted and describes challenges encountered in the data collection process, which invites a candid discussion of iterative research design. In addition, consideration is given to reflexivity and the positionality of the researcher. The focus then turns to ethical considerations, limitations of the research methods, and the reliability of qualitative findings. Using Carcary's (2009) concept of physical and intellectual audit trails, this chapter demonstrates the transparency and integrity of the study.

5.2 Research Aims

5.2.1 Principal Research Question

The principal aim of the research is to answer the following question: How do learners define the value of graduate apprenticeships? First, however, the study must establish what constitutes value in this context. Based on the conceptual foundation laid by the literature review, value is understood as the perceived worth, utility and academic legitimacy of a graduate apprenticeship. However, this is inherently pluralised; learning outcomes are shaped by several stakeholders, each viewing the value proposition from a different perspective. Broadly speaking, there are five key stakeholders and this thesis asserts that their level of influence is ranked as follows:

1. The UK Government (as controller of the metaphorical purse strings)
2. The Scottish Government (with power over education and skills policy)
3. Employers (whose needs dictate programme learning outcomes)
4. Universities (who design the content, assessment and delivery mode)
5. Apprentices

The study posits this as a micro-hierarchy within the wider sectoral hierarchy explored in chapter three. It also contends that apprentices occupy the least influential position in this system, despite their work serving as the measure by which other stakeholders assess the scheme's value. The aim of the research is therefore to ascertain how apprentices derive value within this complex dynamic.

5.2.2 Subsidiary Research Questions

In order to address the principal research question, this study was structured around five subsidiary questions:

1. How do stakeholder dynamics shape programme design and delivery?
2. How do apprentices navigate competing stakeholder expectations?
3. How do programmes emphasise experiential learning?
4. How do apprentices reconcile learning and practice?
5. How do apprentices articulate programme value in relation to their goals?

By carefully examining these distinct elements, the qualitative data builds a rich, multi-dimensional overview of apprenticeships at the case study university. This provides insight into the layered nature of value by highlighting the many elements that influence its construction.

5.3 Research Paradigm

Although educational research is often rooted in practical concerns rather than philosophical enquiry, the presence of the researcher inevitably embeds both in the findings of the study. As Crotty (1998, p. 9) explains, our epistemological stance shapes every stage of the process, from the research design to the interpretation of the findings, which ultimately form our conclusions. Crotty argues that in studies such as this one, which seeks to interpret meaning from lived experience, drawing objective conclusions is impossible:

At best, our outcomes will be suggestive rather than conclusive. They will be plausible, perhaps even convincing [...] but certainly not any 'one true way' of seeing things.

It is therefore necessary to outline the paradigm which underpins this study. Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 105) define a paradigm as a "worldview", arguing that it is not simply preference but a fundamental belief system that dictates how knowledge is constructed. This belief system consists of three inter-related dimensions: ontology, epistemology, and methodology. Following their schema, this section outlines the ontological and epistemological positions that ground this study, as well as the theoretical

perspective and methodological approach to data analysis. Figure 5.1 illustrates this breakdown of the research paradigm.

Figure 5.1: Outline of research paradigm

5.3.1 Ontology

Ontology is concerned with existence and how it is understood. This study's research paradigm is shaped by a relativist ontology, which assumes infinite realities based on individual experience and understanding of phenomena. This approach is valuable within a qualitative research paradigm due to the fact that it allows a narrative to be developed based on social reality and individual experience, which is the core aim of this study. However, this stance is not one of radical relativism, through which truth is viewed as wholly subjective. This study does not claim that all realities are equal, but rather its relativist ontology is tempered by elements of critical realism, which draws a distinction between truth and understanding. The former is suggested to exist independently, while the latter is internally constructed and shaped by individual experiences (Niiniluoto, 2002). This moderate version of relativism rejects the notion that all realities are equal and instead recognises knowledge as fallible and contextual.

5.3.2 Epistemology

As described in section 4.4, epistemology is concerned with "how we know what we know" (Crotty, 1998, p.3). Guba (1992) asserts that relativism is a core tenet of a constructivist epistemology, which forms the second part of my worldview. The epistemology of this study is constructivist, which is rooted in the belief that knowledge is constructed rather than transmitted or acquired (Schwandt, 1994). Crotty explains how interaction shapes understanding using the example of a chair, which the author reasons would exist independently as an object but only as a chair when acknowledged as such. It is important to draw a distinction between constructivism and social constructionism, which has gained prominence in scholarship for its focus on discourse and co-construction in meaning-making. While the role of social influence is acknowledged, a constructivist epistemology is adopted in recognition of the individual nature of apprenticeship learning. The majority of the programme is delivered in the workplace and, although apprentice cohorts engage with a single curriculum, the resultant knowledge will differ for each learner due to its contextual construction within their specific

job role. As this study seeks to understand how value is perceived by learners, constructivism is well-suited to exploring their individual experiences. This stance also aligns with the argument for increased personalisation of apprenticeship curricula, which is presented in chapter nine.

5.3.3 Theoretical Perspective

While ontology and epistemology are distinct concepts, they are intertwined. Crotty (1998, p.10) describes a natural confluence between them, suggesting that the terms sit alongside one another to inform a coherent theoretical perspective. In this study, relativism and constructivism unite in supporting an interpretivist perspective, which views reality as subjective and interpreted through the lens of experience. Beyond merely aligning with constructivist epistemology, Van der Walt (2020) suggests that interpretivism is an extension of its principles, such is its deeply philosophical nature. The author describes how interpretivists reject the notion of a single truth, instead operating on the belief that all knowledge is subject to interpretation, which is shaped by personal worldviews. As Scotland (2012) succinctly puts it: "The interpretive paradigm seeks to understand".

Scotland suggests that interpretivism is generally associated with subjectivist epistemology, which he attributes to the latter's emphasis on personal experience. However, subjectivist principles assume that meaning is constructed internally, based on personal perception rather than through external interaction. While acknowledging individual interpretation in meaning-making, this study adopts a constructivist position, emphasising the importance of external influence as well as social, cultural, and historical contexts. In contrast with subjectivist principles, it recognises the co-construction of meaning through interaction with the world around us. As such, the study views knowledge as a construct to be contextually negotiated and interpreted.

This also highlights the importance of reflexivity in interpretivist research. By accepting knowledge as constructed through situated interactions, the researcher's presence in the study must be recognised for its role in meaning-making. Positionality and reflexivity are therefore explored in section 5.4.

5.3.4 Methodological Framing: Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis

Based on the philosophical and theoretical perspectives adopted in this study, as well as its emphasis on individual participant contribution, a methodology of interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA) was adopted. Smith and Osborn (2015) suggest that this approach is well-suited to the examination of lived experience due to its acknowledgement of interpretation as embedded in the qualitative research process. In the application of IPA, the authors describe how "the researcher is trying to make

sense of the participant trying to make sense of what is happening to them". This aligns with the study's abductive exploration of graduate apprenticeships through lived experience.

The word *experience* is contentious in the view of Sullivan (2014), who calls for greater interrogation of how experience is constructed and interpreted within such studies. Portraying IPA as philosophically promiscuous, he satirically describes the methodology as "up for it" due to its flexible epistemological boundaries. While this raises a valid point of accountability in research, Sullivan's characterisation of IPA as promiscuous has been robustly challenged. Larkin and Seymour-Smith (2014) suggest that the critique implies a lack of academic rigour and caution that flexibility should not be mistaken for incoherence. They acknowledge that IPA is philosophically pluralistic but reiterate its grounding in phenomenology and ideography, arguing that its inherent accessibility and impartiality are a boon for interpretive research. On the other hand, Dennison (2019) accepts the so-called promiscuity but reframes it as a positive attribute, arguing that engagement with multiple dialogic approaches leads to "cross-pollination" of qualitative methods and promotes conceptual innovation.

This study was conducted within a single case study context, the rationale for which is presented in section 5.5.4. As an analytical tool, IPA is suited to case study research; both centre an idiographic approach, allowing for nuanced exploration of individual meaning-making within a set context. However, Engward and Goldspink (2020) caution that IPA researchers are simultaneously part of and apart from their study, and urge reflexivity to ensure "methodological fidelity". IPA's emphasis on the participant voice reinforces the need for reflexive practice; ethically grounded qualitative research must strive to honour the meanings participants themselves attribute to their experiences (Larkin, Watts and Clifton, 2006). In line with this, the following section explores researcher positionality and describes engagement with active reflexivity.

5.4 Reflexivity and Positionality

As a practitioner-researcher in Scottish tertiary education, the influence of my presence in the study is acknowledged. Fleming (2018) challenges the historically narrow definition of insider research with the argument that *a priori* knowledge of the sector can position an individual as an insider regardless of whether they are situated inside or outside of the immediate research context. She also cautions that this type of research can present specific challenges, urging insider researchers to be mindful. These include implicit coercion during recruitment due to perceived power dynamics; assumptions and blind spots arising from overfamiliarity with the research context; ensuring ethical behaviour

regarding participant access and confidentiality; and data interpretation coloured by an inherent desire for positive outcomes. Maher (2025) perfectly captures this core tension:

Rather than being a detached and objective observer of education, whose aim is to uncover value-neutral understandings, I am actively involved in the construction of knowledge about education. To forget, conceal or deny that would, for me, be disingenuous, counter-productive and may compromise (rather than enhance) the rigour of the research that I do.

Although reflexivity is a key element of any research, my position as an insider researcher particularly reaffirms Soedirgo and Glas' (2020) recommendation of active and ongoing reflexive practices. This section therefore considers my proximity to the research topic through exploration of my own return to education as an adult and how this shaped my initial perceptions of the graduate apprenticeship scheme. It also describes the concept of active reflexivity and how this was embedded throughout the research process.

5.4.1 Positionality of the Researcher

My interest in graduate apprenticeships was shaped by my own experiences as a mature learner. An outlier amongst my peers, I opted to enter full-time employment after secondary school. When I was 24, I was encouraged to bolster my sparse Higher results with an HNC, which I achieved through evening classes at a local college. However, like many adult learners, my circumstances did not allow me to leave my job in order to pursue higher education. Though I worked in a university, part-time undergraduate provision was limited and did not align with my needs at that time. I therefore looked to online degree options that I could fit around my commitments, and a post-92 university offered me advanced entry through Recognition of Prior Learning. This allowed me to complete my BA at the age of 28 and my MSc (with the same institution) at 30.

Having been a vocal advocate of online and flexible learning for a number of years, my interest was piqued when my employer institution announced the first graduate apprenticeship programme. I was peripherally involved in its development and I was both excited by the apprenticeship model and slightly envious that it had not been an option for me. Additionally, at that time, a key part of my role was developing industry links and increasing the curriculum's employability focus, so I felt optimistic about the potential impact of a degree co-designed with industry. These factors undoubtedly shaped my early perceptions and expectations of the scheme, which reinforced the importance of practising reflexivity in this study. My experience of returning to education as an adult and undertaking a degree while working full-time provided insight into the demands of juggling parallel employee and student

roles. I was conscious that this posed a risk of over-identifying with apprentice participants and I remained mindful of not projecting my own experiences onto their journeys.

My eagerness was also slightly tempered by an anticipation of mission drift in the final product. Though I am loath to label it outright scepticism, I have observed certain patterns over the course of thirteen years in the tertiary education sector. New initiatives are met with enthusiasm but, despite the best of pedagogical intentions, compromises must often be made due to operational or funding constraints, which dictate how a programme is delivered in practice. While admittedly frustrating at times, I recognise that universities operate in a complex landscape with many elements outside of their control. Having this crucial context allowed me to ensure that my approach to the institutional side of graduate apprenticeships was not unduly critical. Additionally, without question, my access to participants was shaped by my position as a researcher in a Scottish university. This had positive and negative implications while carrying out the study, which are described in section 5.5.2.

Fleming (2018) highlights the potential for enhancement to policy and practice as a benefit of insider research in a higher education context, though this also requires careful navigation. MacPherson and McKie (2010) caution that although proximity eases access and rapport during data collection, it can complicate matters if the research findings offer "difficult" feedback. This underscores the need for diplomacy and transparency as a practitioner-researcher, as well as cognisance that the findings may have direct implications for the participants and wider context.

5.4.2 Active Reflexivity

Positionality is a dynamic relationship between researcher and research, and this is continuously reshaped by interactions and perceptions. Conducting this study therefore posed a number of specific challenges as a practitioner-researcher. As described by Fleming (2018), primary concerns included a risk of superficial engagement due to overfamiliarity with the context and ensuring ethical navigation of power dynamics when engaging with apprentices. These challenges reinforce the need for ongoing reflexive practices, which informed the adoption of active reflexivity during this study.

In line with Soedirgo and Glas' (2020) emphasis on humility in active reflexivity, all interactions were approached mindfully and with consideration of my positionality relative to the participant, including how my position may be perceived by them. For example, I acknowledge that an undergraduate student may perceive a significant power distance when engaging in an interview with a PhD student. Conversely, I recognise that my insider status may close the power distance during interactions with

staff. Engagement with active reflexivity was therefore embedded throughout the research process, guiding data collection and interpretation. Crucially, this practice enabled me to confidently, ethically, and transparently engage participants.

5.5 Research Strategy: Methods and Participants

5.5.1 Multimethod Research Design

Despite its entirely qualitative approach, it is appropriate to describe this study as multimethod according to the distinction made by Brewer and Hunter (2006, p. 4). While others (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998, p. 14) characterise research that does not combine quantitative and qualitative as monomethod, Brewer and Hunter encourage multiple avenues of data collection to compensate for the inherent limitations of interpretive methods. The authors argue that the resulting "convergent findings" are stronger than those of a single-method study. The research design therefore draws on Wilson's (1998) notion of consilience, which refers to the development of a coherent theory through the examination of diverse sources. Through this pluralist approach, the study seeks to present a rich and multifaceted insight into the lived experience of graduate apprentices, therefore a multimethod approach was employed to strengthen the findings. The data collection process used three methods: semi-structured interviews, a qualitative questionnaire, and an extended literature and policy review.

Multimethod design also facilitates data triangulation. Rather than adopting this process purely as a mechanism for validating results, this study understands triangulation as reframed by Denzin (2012), who describes it as reflexive engagement with data from multiple sources with a view to constructing a deeper understanding of a phenomenon. Alase (2017) supports this perspective in the context of IPA, which underpins the theoretical grounding of this study. The author argues that triangulation enhances the credibility of IPA research by enabling a panoramic exploration of meaning-making. Data analysis in this study was enhanced through triangulation due to the inductive emergence of patterns across methods without compromising the idiographic and interpretive commitments of IPA. While inductive elements are featured in the analysis and interpretation of primary qualitative data, the overarching logic of this project is abductive. This thesis posits that the contested value of graduate apprenticeships presents a conceptual puzzle, and this serves as the starting point for the research. Drawing on Van Hulst and Visser's (2025) analytical framework, the study seeks to develop a contextual explanation through iterative exploration of literature, policy documentation, and lived experience.

5.5.2 Research Strategy: Timeline, Challenges and Adaptations

Primary data was collected between 2022 and 2025. A detailed breakdown of the data collection timeline is provided below in tables 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3.

Phase 1: 2022				
Programme	Method	Participant Role	Communication	Outcome
A	Interview	Staff	Email via Coordinator	4 interviews*
		Learner	VLE via Coordinator	2 interviews

Table 5.1: Data collection timeline (phase 1)

**this figure includes one individual in a Professional Services role not attached to Programme A*

Phase 2: 2023				
Programme	Method	Participant Role	Communication	Outcome
B	Interview	Staff	Email via Coordinator	1 interview
		Learner	VLE via Coordinator	–
C	Interview	Staff	No response to request	–
		Learner	No response to request	–
D	Interview	Staff	No response to request	–
		Learner	No response to request	–

Table 5.2: Data collection timeline (phase 2)

Phase 3: 2024 - 2025				
Programme	Method	Participant Role	Communication	Outcome
A	Questionnaire	Learner	VLE via Coordinator	6 responses
B	Questionnaire	Learner	VLE via Coordinator	5 responses
C	Interview	Staff	Email via Coordinator	1 interview
	Questionnaire	Learner	VLE via Coordinator	4 responses
D	Interview	Staff	Email via Coordinator	–
	Questionnaire	Learner	VLE via Coordinator	4 responses

Table 5.3: Data collection timeline (phase 3)

Kapiszewski, MacLean and Read (2022) observe that many researchers are reluctant to deviate from an initial research strategy, meaning they often face obstacles in "quiet crisis". The authors suggest this is compounded by an unwillingness to acknowledge methodological adjustments in academic publications, resulting in a misalignment of researcher expectations. Yet, by candidly documenting the challenges encountered, adjustments implemented and lessons learned, they argue that the integrity of the research process is strengthened rather than threatened. With this in mind, before the data collection methods are outlined, this section describes how the research design evolved over the course of the study and reflects on the implications for my own practice as a researcher.

Semi-structured interviews were initially selected as the primary method of data collection, as open-ended dialogue appeared the most obvious way to facilitate in-depth exploration of participants' lived experience. Participants were also not recruited from all graduate apprenticeship programmes in the first instance; instead, recruitment efforts focused on Programme A as a small-scale pilot study. The rationale for this was to assess emerging themes against key research aims, allowing for any necessary refinement of the process. The merit of this approach is underscored by Kapiszewski, MacLean and Read (2022), who argue for iterative research design as an integral part of interpretive scholarship. The authors celebrate iteration's ability to strengthen a project, though they offer three caveats: that iteration is carried out intentionally and reflexively, any adjustments are proportionate to the obstacle encountered, and all changes are documented in a transparent manner.

Data collection began in 2022. The start of this phase coincided with a busy period of assessment for graduate apprentices and so the initial interviews were conducted with staff involved in the design, delivery or marketing of the programmes. In August of that year, permission was obtained from the academic coordinator to observe face-to-face teaching activities for three Programme A cohorts at one of the case study university's campuses. Following this, Programme A teaching staff circulated an invitation to participate in this study, which led to two interviews. Another two apprentices made contact via email to indicate their interest in participating but no further interviews were scheduled.

The second phase of data collection commenced in 2023 after a formal period of interruption and a transition from full-time to part-time study. An interview invitation email was disseminated by the Programme B coordinator to all learners and staff, resulting in an interview with one academic staff member. Contact was also made with the academic coordinators for Programmes C and D at this time and initial meetings were held to discuss the scope and aims of the study. However, consent to an interview was not granted and further requests for the interview invitation to be disseminated to Programmes C and D, or to be provided with contact details for teaching staff, received no response. This is reflective of Madikizela-Madiya's (2017) experience as a practitioner-researcher, as the author describes how her research study was directly shaped by "unexpected" gatekeeping of participants.

Alternative means of contacting apprentices were explored outside of the teaching departments but, due to data protection concerns, the advice remained that recruitment communication should be circulated through the virtual learning environment (VLE) by a programme's academic coordinator. Despite sustained recruitment efforts, no further interviews were conducted with apprentices. This prompted a re-evaluation of the data collection methods and, in 2024, the study pivoted to an open-

ended questionnaire. The questionnaire's design retained the exploratory nature of semi-structured interviews by encouraging participants to reflect and articulate their experiences in their own words. Moreover, it offered the additional benefits of anonymity and engagement at the convenience of the respondent. All four programme coordinators circulated the questionnaire details via their respective VLE twice, once in late 2024 and again in early 2025. In total, 19 responses were recorded.

Programmes C and D both experienced changes in leadership between the second and third phases of data collection. Contact was established with the new coordinators in late 2024, resulting in an interview with one member of staff from Programme C. While the Programme D coordinator agreed to disseminate the questionnaire invitation to their apprenticeship cohorts, requests to interview staff received no response.

With hindsight, encountering the challenges outlined in this section has proven to be as valuable as the successful elements of the research project. Echoing the critical reflections of Madikizela-Madiya (2017), this experience has highlighted the need for a flexible approach as a practitioner-researcher navigating the structural complexities of higher education. It also provided insight into access and participation barriers, informing the decision to prioritise learner access by making the questionnaire anonymous. The positive and negative implications of this are discussed in section 5.8.4. In short, the challenges experienced over the course of this study have contributed to a greater understanding of (and appreciation for) iterative research design. This will certainly continue to shape my approach to qualitative research, as well as my commitment to transparent, reflexive and academically rigorous practice.

5.5.3 Secondary Data: Extended Literature and Policy Review

Three chapters of this thesis are dedicated to an extended, thematically structured literature review. The decision to conduct such a detailed review of literature and policy was driven by the inherently pluralistic nature of the graduate apprenticeship scheme; despite their consistent and prescriptive format, programmes carry an expectation to address increasingly heterogeneous stakeholder needs. These multi-stakeholder tensions highlighted the importance of critically interrogating the value of apprenticeships from several key perspectives in order to establish a multi-dimensional foundation for this study. This is supported by Smith (2008), who suggests that small, contextually-focused studies like the present one particularly benefit from engagement with secondary data. She argues for its value in establishing the contextual and methodological basis for exploration of qualitative primary data, which is then interpreted with a view to explaining patterns identified in the literature review.

Smith refers to this interpretive use of secondary data to explore new phenomena as the "new social arithmetic".

Moreover, a literature review provides a robust means of developing a broad and detailed overview of a context in a time-effective way through analysis of vast amounts of secondary data (Johnston, 2014) – more data than could be reasonably generated within the constraints of a PhD timeline. Due to political interest in graduate apprenticeships, policy and government data feature heavily in parts of the review, which Smith (2008) considers to be the highest quality available. She also goes on to highlight the generalisability of larger datasets, which are designed to be representative of wider populations. Secondary analysis of such data is of particular value to studies with smaller, purposively sampled datasets as it allows for comparison between primary data and previously identified trends.

Since 2017, the scheme has experienced a number of revisions in terms of structure, oversight and funding. Bureaucratic complexities also mean that apprenticeships are failing to scale at the expected rate (Jackson, 2025), and a number of institutions have opted to disengage entirely. As a relatively new entrant to the higher education landscape, these developments could be interpreted as "red flags" for the scheme's long-term sustainability, which I believe warrant a panoramic exploration that takes into account historical context, policy intentions and institutional perceptions. By examining graduate apprenticeships through three lenses (policy, position and pedagogy), the literature review presents a multifaceted overview of their evolving context and value proposition.

5.5.4 Case Study Introduction and Rationale

This research study adopts a case study approach, focusing on a single post-92 university in Scotland between 2022 and 2025. The decision to use a single case study was steered by the epistemological and ontological architecture of this project; Starman (2013) asserts that case study research is suited to a constructivist-interpretive approach, as it facilitates in-depth exploration of a phenomenon in a specific context.

Although this approach has historically received criticism for lacking methodological robustness, Yin (1981) argues that it is best suited to research that seeks to "examine a contemporary phenomenon in its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident". This is reflective of the present case study context, wherein the boundaries between apprenticeship design, institutional framing and learner experience are intertwined. Collecting data from multiple institutions would likely have resulted in a broader but more fragmented overview of

apprentice experience. In contrast, a single case study allows such complexities to be explored in greater detail, resulting in a deeper understanding. It also allowed for intra-case comparison; design and delivery of graduate apprenticeship programmes vary significantly between disciplinary areas, resulting in notable differences in learner experience across cohorts within a single institution.

Yin (1981) also highlights the value of explanatory case studies in allowing researchers to test existing knowledge. This study reflects Yin's logic through iterative and abductive engagement with literature, policy documentation and primary data to address the core research questions. Although the single case study design is well-suited to the interpretive aims of this study, its limitations are acknowledged and discussed in section 5.8.2.

5.5.5 Recruitment and Participants

Recruitment was carried out using purposive sampling, which Mason (2018, p. 73) describes as an interactive method that enables researchers to steer the direction of data generation. This aligns with the idiographic commitment of IPA as a methodology, which prioritises depth of exploration over breadth, allowing for a nuanced understanding of participant experience (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009, p. 121). Data was collected from 21 learners, all of whom reported that they were enrolled and engaging in a graduate apprenticeship programme at the time of participation. In total, 2 of the learner participants were interviewed and 19 responded to the open-ended questionnaire.

Additionally, interviews were conducted with 6 members of staff at the case study university. Staff participants were employed in both academic and Professional Services roles, and their involvement in graduate apprenticeships spanned a number of perspectives, including design, delivery and external engagement. While this study foregrounds the value of graduate apprenticeships for learners, the decision to interview staff was informed by Stake (1995), who highlights the importance of exploring multiple stakeholder perspectives within a case study. He argues that differing viewpoints illuminate the complexities of an issue, which enhances overall understanding.

Overleaf, Table 5.4 outlines when each interviewee engaged with the study. Table 5.5 then breaks down the questionnaire respondents by programme.

Programme	Participant Role	Position	Data Collection Phase
Programme A	Staff	Academic	Phase 1 / 2022
Programme A	Staff	Academic	Phase 1 / 2022
Programme A	Staff	Academic	Phase 1 / 2022
Programme A	Learner	–	Phase 1 / 2022
Programme A	Learner	–	Phase 1 / 2022
–	Staff	Professional Services	Phase 1 / 2022
Programme B	Staff	Academic	Phase 2 / 2023
Programme C	Staff	Academic	Phase 3 / 2024

Table 5.4: Overview of interview participants

Programme A	Programme B	Programme C	Programme D
6	5	4	4

Table 5.5: Number of questionnaire respondents by programme

5.5.6 Semi-Structured Interviews

The decision to use semi-structured interviews reflects the study's overall constructivist position, as the dialogic format enables meaning to be co-created between the researcher and participant. Maher (2025) suggests that semi-structured interviews are well-suited to studies like the present one due to the inherently intersubjective nature of educational experience.

The first stage of recruitment was direct email contact with apprenticeship programme coordinators, who disseminated an invitation through VLE (to learners) and email (to relevant staff). The invitation included a weblink to a landing page created using Microsoft Sway, which contained plain language information about the research study and what participation would involve. No incentive or payment was offered. Interviews were arranged through email or directly via a Microsoft Bookings page linked to my calendar. Participants were then emailed a digital consent form to be completed prior to the interview. A full description of how informed consent was obtained, including further details of the resources mentioned here, is provided in section 5.7.1. Though the option of a face-to-face interview was offered, all eight participants opted to conduct the interview virtually via Microsoft Teams. Audio and video were recorded with participant consent and used to facilitate transcription prior to data analysis. On average, interviews lasted for one hour.

Two interview schedules were drafted, copies of which are provided as Appendices 1 and 2. The questions in the learner schedule were directed toward personal motivations and goals; experiences of support and mentorship on the programme; relevance of academic content and its application in

practice; and their perceptions of apprenticeships before and after engaging with the programme. Staff questions focused on programme design; apprentice performance, progression and retention; their experiences of tripartite engagement; the role of apprenticeships in universities; and potential barriers to long-term viability.

5.5.7 Open-Ended Questionnaire

Apprentices in all four programmes were invited to participate twice. Academic coordinators shared the invitation via the VLE, once in late 2024 and again in early 2025. The invitation included a link to a Microsoft Sway site containing information about the project as well as a link to the questionnaire, which was created using Microsoft Forms. As with interview recruitment, no incentive or payment was offered for participation. The questionnaire was split into two sections (Appendices 3 and 4). The first section contained 9 demographic questions:

1. What is your student status?
2. What is/was your programme of study?
3. What is your age?
4. What is your gender?
5. When did you start the graduate apprenticeship programme?
6. At which level of study did you enter the graduate apprenticeship?
7. What is your current year of study?
8. Before you joined the programme, what was the highest qualification you held?
9. How long have you been with your current employer?

A range of potential responses was provided, including "prefer not to say" for 7 of the questions. It was not offered for the first 2 questions as these were used to assess participant eligibility. However, an explanation for this was provided at the beginning of the questionnaire, alongside an assurance of anonymity. In addition to verifying eligibility, this section was designed to enable comparison with trends reported by Skills Development Scotland (SDS).

The second part contained open-ended questions, and respondents were encouraged to include as much detail as they felt comfortable sharing. Holmberg *et al.* (2014) assert that standardised surveys oversimplify lived experience, which they argue often reflects the interests of the researcher rather than the subject. Due to the centrality of the learner perspective in this study, an open-ended format was crucial to generating responses that allowed a more nuanced insight into their experiences. The matter of how many open-ended questions to include was informed by the apprentice demographic

at the case study university; during interviews in the first phase of data collection, staff indicated that apprentices are overwhelmingly mature learners navigating the demands of full-time work, full-time study and personal commitments. There was a high probability of these factors negatively impacting response rates (Rolstad, Adler and Rydén, 2011) and so a compact questionnaire seemed prudent. As Cernat *et al.* (2024) point out, reducing the length of a survey can feel counterintuitive because there are few circumstances in which a researcher will purposefully limit data generation. However, it was necessary to balance the richness of the data with participant burden, which was to be placed on an already burdened cohort. Therefore, to maximise the data value while minimising participant burden, 4 open-ended questions were carefully constructed:

1. What inspired you to apply for the graduate apprenticeship programme and what inspires you to complete the qualification?
2. How do you feel about the education you are receiving through your programme?
3. How do the assessed components of your course relate to your professional role?
4. What is your experience of accessing support or mentorship as a graduate apprentice?

To ensure coherence across the data collection methods, 11 of the 15 questions from the interview schedule were mapped to the questionnaire (Table 5.6).

Questionnaire Questions	Interview Questions
What is/was your programme of study?	What programme are you enrolled in?
What is your current year of study?	What year of the programme are you in?
Before you joined the graduate apprenticeship, what was the highest qualification you held?	Had you completed any further education before this?
How long have you been with your current employer?	How long have you been in your role?
What inspired you to join the graduate apprenticeship programme and what inspires you to complete the qualification?	What made you want to apply for the apprenticeship?
	What is your motivation? What do you hope to gain from the programme?
How do the assessed components of your course relate to your professional role?	How have you identified your work-based learning projects?
	Do you feel that the academic content is relevant to your work?
What is your experience of accessing support or mentorship as a graduate apprentice?	Is your employer supportive?
	Do you have a workplace mentor?
	Has the university been supportive?

Table 5.6: Mapping interview to questionnaire questions

The questionnaire and project information site were also subject to an informal peer review prior to dissemination. Test versions of the resources were presented to four colleagues with expertise in learning design, who assessed the written content, functionality and accessibility. This additional step in the process proved to be worthwhile, and adjustments were made based on their feedback.

5.6 Data Analysis

5.6.1 Data Analysis Process

Interviews were transcribed verbatim before being transposed into a bespoke coding template (Appendix 5). Questionnaire responses were downloaded from Microsoft Forms and transposed into a separate template (Appendix 6), with open-ended responses separated by question. Prior to data analysis, the questionnaire responses were subject to additional processing. Attention checks were conducted in line with the recommendation of Braitman *et al.* (2022), who advise employing this as a mechanism to assess the quality of questionnaire data. These checks determined that all participant responses aligned with direct questions within the questionnaire, highlighting no cause for concern in terms of satisficing (responding carelessly or without due effort through lack of motivation). From this point, thematic analysis of the data followed the iterative and inductive cycle outlined by Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009, p. 79): line-by-line analysis; identification of themes and patterns across participant accounts; interpretation of relationships between themes and contextual knowledge; and finally, the development of coherent findings grounded in participants' reflections.

The decision to manually code the data rather than use qualitative research software such as NVivo was informed by both methodological and practical considerations. First, the relatively small sample size meant the dataset did not necessitate machine processing and the investment (financially and in terms of time) required to access and learn the software meant that manual analysis was the more efficient option. There are also a number of limitations associated with such software. García-Horta and Guerra-Ramos (2009) argue that NVivo is no substitute for manual analysis in terms of "assigning meaning, synthesising or theorising". Additionally, Zamawe (2015) cautions that the software creates distance between a researcher and their data. This is a sentiment shared by Maher *et al.* (2018), who point out that NVivo cannot provide broad overviews, which presents a risk of data fragmentation. Manual analysis offered greater adaptability in terms of the coding templates, as well as preserving the original context of participant accounts. This immersion in the data also enabled comparison and iterative refinement of the emerging themes.

5.6.2 Coding and Emergent Themes

Manual coding of learner data identified 199 relevant data points: 143 from questionnaire responses and 56 from interviews. A total of 21 codes were identified, which were organised into 12 categories. Further refinement of these categories revealed 5 key themes: Mentorship, Support and Engagement; Personalisation of Learning and Teaching; The Role of Experiential Learning; Learner Motivation; and Apprenticeship Value. Next, analysis of staff interview transcripts identified 338 relevant data points. A total of 27 codes were identified, which were organised into 9 categories. Refinement of the high-level themes revealed key points of overlap with learner themes 1, 2 and 3. In addition to these, a further 2 themes emerged: Retention and Progression, and Navigating External Influences.

Career Progression	Transferable Skills	Gaining Practical Experience
Keeping Up To Date	Earn While You Learn	Further Study
Personal Satisfaction	Personal Development	Curriculum Relevance
Employer Support	Communication	Delivery of Learning Materials
Flexible/Tailored Delivery	Lecturer Support	Assessment Format
Assessment Relevance	Workload	University Integration
Tripartite Agreement	Collaboration	Perception of Apprenticeships

Table 5.7: Codes identified from learner data

Professional Development/Progression	Personal Development	Assessment Design
Communication and Collaboration	Teaching and Support	Workload and Balance
Value of Work-Based Learning	Learning Environment	Workplace Support
Overcoming Barriers to Education	Programme Design	Integration and Community

Table 5.8: Initial themes identified from learner data

Programme Design	Student Outcomes	Framework and Accreditation
Delivery Methods	Workload	Learner Performance
Work-Based Learning	Cultural Influences	Institutional Constraints
Flexibility/Personalisation	Student Retention	External Influences
Workplace Mentorship	Perception of Success	Access and Diversity
Academic Mentorship	Funder Requirements	Tripartite Collaboration
Employer Motivation	Learner Demographic	Value Creation
Learner Motivation	Academic Readiness	Language
Work-Life Balance	Marketing and Recruitment	Staff Attitudes/Perceptions

Table 5.9: Codes identified from staff data

Programme Design and Delivery	Internal Challenges and Influences	Learning and Teaching
Marketing, Recruitment and Access	Work-Based Learning Integration	Mentorship and Support
External Challenges and Influences	Retention and Progression	Motivation

Table 5.10: Initial themes identified from staff data

5.7 Ethical Considerations

The ethical stance of this study is informed by its participant-centric focus, as well as recognition of the potential moral implications of research as a socially embedded activity (London, 2022). Ethical approval was granted by the Education and Social Sciences School Ethics Committee, and this study adheres to the institutional Code of Research Practice and Research Ethics. The ethical commitment of this thesis also extends beyond procedural compliance; it is embedded and actively practised. London (2022, p.3) frames research as a collaborative social enterprise, which he suggests acts as a bridge between institutions and public need:

The information that research produces is a social and a public good because it constitutes the evidence base on which a range of stakeholders rely to make decisions that impact the rights and welfare of individuals.

This study prioritises participants' agency through a commitment to knowledge construction that is both respectful and representative of their experiences. This extends to the axiology underpinning the research, which espouses transparency, accessibility and the moral responsibility to "do good" as a researcher. My personal values around equity, educational parity and the disruption of academic gatekeeping are also acknowledged for their role in shaping my interpretation of meaning.

5.7.1 Obtaining Informed Consent

In line with the Code of Research Practice and Research Ethics, informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to engagement with the study. Details of the research project were published on a landing page created using Microsoft Sway. Three versions of this page were created: one for staff interviews, one for learner interviews, and one for the questionnaire. Copies of these are provided as Appendices 7, 8 and 9. Although the content of each page was tailored to the intended audience and data collection method, a number of key points were covered:

- An overview of the research project
- Details of what participation in the study would involve
- An explanation of how their data would be handled and used
- Assurances of anonymity in the final research output
- An invitation to request further information
- Contact information for the project's supervision team

Interviews were arranged either by email or directly through a secure booking link. Individuals who participated via interview also completed a digital consent form (Appendix 10). This form emphasised participation as voluntary and reiterated their right to withdraw consent prior to submission of the thesis.

The information page for questionnaire respondents also highlighted that participation was voluntary and the level of detail provided was at their discretion. However, significant emphasis was placed on the fact that subsequent withdrawal of consent would not be possible due to the mechanism which assures anonymity. With hindsight, the demographic questions captured a spread of responses that would allow a participant to be identified and their data removed following corroboration of their answers. However, this could not be foreseen at the time of recruitment. Apprentices were therefore urged to carefully consider their participation and to reach out with questions prior to completing the survey. As it is, no participants have made contact to withdraw consent.

5.7.2 Protecting Participant Identity

The overall value of qualitative research is contingent on mutual trust; the researcher must trust that a participant's account is honest, and the participant must trust that their experience will be accurately portrayed. Researchers have a duty to protect participants from harm, and confidentiality is the principal means of safeguarding their identities and disclosures. Wiles *et al.* (2008) draw an important distinction between anonymity and confidentiality: anonymisation refers to the removal of identifying markers in published data, while confidentiality extends to any disclosure of information from which an individual may be identified. As such, researchers should not divulge sensitive details shared by participants, either in print or otherwise. Participants were informed prior to engagement with the study (Appendices 7-9) that all contributions would be anonymised and their information would remain confidential. Throughout the study, maintaining confidentiality has remained a priority.

Due to the relatively small sample size and single case study focus, careful consideration was given to the risk of "jigsaw" identification, which involves piecing together snippets of information in order to identify an individual (UKRI, 2019). Saunders, Kitzinger and Kitzinger (2015) describe the process of anonymising data as a spectrum, with the degree of anonymisation dictated by the subject sensitivity and the context of the disclosure. In the present study, participant names have been replaced with alphanumeric codes, and job titles, programme names, and references to employers have been anonymised. While immaterial details have been redacted, certain descriptors have been retained as they speak to learners' motivations. For example, a desire to pursue Incorporation or Chartership. This

highlights the competing priorities described by Saunders, Kitzinger and Kitzinger: a balance must be struck between protecting participants' identities and preserving the richness and integrity of the findings.

Crucially, the case study university has not been named. Institutional identifiers and references to employers have also been redacted. Nespor (2000) takes a negative view of anonymisation as the default position, particularly with regard to institutions, arguing that this erases political and cultural aspects of a context and limits public accountability. While he raises some valid points around the relational position between the researcher, participants and place, this study remains committed to anonymity. Given that the majority of participants are current students at the case study university, providing a safe space for reflection on their education was of paramount importance. Additionally, staff participants were asked to reflect candidly on their place of employment, which they did with a reasonable expectation of anonymity.

5.7.3 Reliability of Results

While positivist research approaches aim to measure reliability in terms of replicability, Mason (2018, pp.235-236) explains that reliability is defined in qualitative studies by the consistency, accuracy and transparency with which the process is conducted and documented. This notion of methodological traceability is supported by Carcary (2009), particularly within an interpretivist paradigm. She frames reliability as an indicator of methodological integrity, proposing that this should be demonstrated through physical and intellectual audit trails, which the author argues strengthen the confirmability of qualitative findings. In this study, a physical audit trail is evident in the detailed documentation of procedural aspects of the research, including participant recruitment and processes for collecting and analysing data, which allow the logic of the research design to be traced and the credibility of the study's findings to be evaluated. In addition, the intellectual audit trail is embedded throughout this chapter, particularly in sections 5.4 (Reflexivity and Positionality) and 5.5.2 (Timeline, Challenges and Adaptations), both of which offer insight into key decisions that shaped the study.

The reliability of the findings is further supported by:

(i) Consistency in data collection, including the use of interview schedules to guide discussion. When circumstances forced a change of method, the learner interview schedule then formed the basis of the open-ended questionnaire to ensure data coherence.

(ii) Ongoing engagement with reflexivity to mitigate the impact of insider status (Fleming, 2018) and limit over-identification with participants.

(iii) Deeper interpretive insight through multimethod triangulation (Denzin, 2012; Alase, 2017).

(iv) Authentic and transparent reporting of the research process, including candid reflection on how methodological decisions were shaped by specific challenges (Kapiszewski, Maclean & Read, 2022).

Based on Carcay's (2009) conceptualisation, this study's reliability is evident in the traceability of its design logic, its methodological consistency, and transparent documentation of the research process.

5.8 Limitations of Research Strategy

5.8.1 Literature Review as a Research Method

As a research method, a literature review poses a number of limitations. First, impartiality presents a significant challenge as the literature referenced in the final review is contingent on access and availability. Moreover, the researcher is embedded in the review process and so their existing knowledge and disciplinary interests determine what information is noticed and prioritised. As the amount of scholarship available online grows (Johnston, 2014), it can be argued that technological advancements in data searches may actually impede a literature review's comprehensiveness. Following an analysis of advanced information retrieval methods in the Big Data era, Mansour and Alsaud (2025) highlight algorithmic biases which dictate what information is deemed relevant by a search engine. The authors therefore call for increased ethical oversight of information retrieval models to ensure fair and objective search results. While this study's literature review establishes a nuanced foundation for the interpretation of the primary data, no assumptions are made about its comprehensiveness.

Another significant limitation is the reviewer's lack of involvement in the collection or analysis of the original dataset (Johnston, 2014). First, the original research was not designed to align with the aims of this study, nor was the data intended to answer its questions. Additionally, the methodological transparency of the original research must be scrutinised. Data is processed and sanitised before the findings are presented and, without access to the raw data and analysis methods, the reviewer will be unaware of errors or gaps in the original data. Secondary qualitative data also lacks relational context, which presents a challenge in re-interpreting the original interpretation.

The age of secondary data is another potential limitation, as highlighted by Beck (2023). This extends beyond outdated literature; there is often a delay in the publication of national statistics, which can lead to gaps in the data, making it more challenging to identify patterns or interpret causation. This is the case with key documents referred to in the present study, including the most recent graduate apprenticeship report from Skills Development Scotland (2025), which does not provide data beyond the academic year 2022-23.

While Smith (2008) recommends that secondary data be approached with "appropriate" scepticism, she advocates for recognition of secondary data analysis as a research method in its own right. On balance, the value added to this study by the extended literature review far outweighs the limitations highlighted here.

5.8.2 Single Case Study Limitations

Case studies have attracted criticism for their limited generalisability, and this was a consideration for the present study, the findings of which reflect a small purposive sample within a single institutional context. This study does not claim to be representative of the wider population, or even the wider higher education sector. However, the single case study approach allowed this study to fulfil its core aim of gaining insight into how graduate apprentices perceive the value of their educational experiences. Stake (1995, p.1) captures this idiographic intent, highlighting how case study research can identify connections to wider trends through the distinctive features of a particular context:

The cases of interest in education and social service are people and programs. Each one is similar to other people and programs in many ways and unique in many ways. We are interested in them for both their uniqueness and commonality. We seek to understand them.

Nonetheless, a single case study may limit inter-institutional comparison. Although intra-institutional programme variations are discussed, this study cannot speak to the design or delivery of graduate apprenticeships within other universities in Scotland. This is acknowledged as a potential constraint in terms of wider sectoral relevance. However, this study asserts that its findings offer some transferability across other post-92 institutions due to similarities in their operational contexts. This argument is presented in section 5.8.5.

5.8.3 Semi-Structured Interview Limitations

Semi-structured interviews were selected as the principal data collection method due to their ability to facilitate in-depth and dynamic exploration of participant experience. However, interviews also

present several limitations. First, the researcher's role in shaping an interview cannot be overlooked, particularly when "insider" status is involved, as this can influence learner participant perceptions of a power distance (Fleming, 2018). Despite actively engaging in reflexive practice to mitigate the impact of this (as described in section 5.4), the presence of the researcher in qualitative research presents an inherent challenge.

Next, the generation of high-quality data through interviews is contingent on participants providing honest accounts of their experiences. Importantly, it relies on their ability to articulate the nuance of those experiences. The presentation of these accounts must also remain faithful to the intended meaning, which is dictated by the researcher's subsequent interpretation. Despite the open format of interviews, there is a risk that some of the richness and complexity of the data is inadvertently lost in the analysis and interpretation. In the context of the present study, this was mitigated somewhat by the fact that all interviews were conducted virtually and therefore both video and audio were recorded. This greatly reduces the risk of non-verbal expressions being omitted compared to analysis of audio-only recordings obtained during face-to-face or telephone interviews.

Finally, it transpired that both learner interviewees had previously completed apprenticeships (one modern apprenticeship and one trade), which may have influenced their impressions of graduate apprenticeships. As a result, their previous experiences may have informed their self-selection for participation in this study, pointing to potential underrepresentation of less favourable perspectives. In contrast, an analysis of graduate apprenticeship meta-skills by Barr and Nabi (2022) compelled learner participation by embedding a reflective report as an assessed component of the programme. This resulted in a 100% response rate, with only positive accounts presented by the authors. While it is acknowledged that self-selection may skew findings toward positive views, it can be argued that compelling participation also poses a risk, as a perceived power dynamic may limit candour. In short, the conditions of participation must be taken into account when interpreting qualitative findings.

5.8.4 Open-Ended Questionnaire Limitations

A number of limitations are acknowledged in relation to the questionnaire. First, participants were not required to sign in to their university IT account to complete the online questionnaire. This was a conscious decision made with a view to maximising accessibility for participants. For context, the university's IT security protocol enforces mandatory multi-factor authentication, which creates an additional step in the process. Frequent digital authentication requests can contribute to a sense of "security fatigue" and feelings of anger or frustration (Arnold *et al.*, 2022), so this was identified as a

potential deterrent to participation. Furthermore, by not requiring participants to sign in, anonymity was assured as no identifying details were attached to their responses. However, this means it was not possible to conduct a debrief or provide participants with preliminary results. Furthermore, there is no way to confirm their enrolment at the case study university. The pros and cons of enforcing an institutional login were carefully considered prior to disseminating the questionnaire, and the choice was ultimately made to prioritise participant access.

Although online research may attract "imposter participants", the risk is significantly higher in studies that (i) recruit through open calls on public platforms and (ii) offer a reward for participation (Roehl and Harland, 2022; Wang, 2024). As it is, no incentive was offered for participation in this study. Furthermore, recruitment was a narrow process. The request was emailed to coordinators of eligible programmes, who disseminated a short blurb and survey link via their programme-specific area of the VLE. These areas are accessible only to graduate apprentices enrolled on the relevant programme at the case study university. In addition, Chandler and Paolacci (2017) suggest that another way of reducing fraudulent responses is to provide no specific details of survey content or eligibility criteria in recruitment communications. The survey invitation via the VLE stated only that apprentices at the case study university were invited to participate in a research project. These precautionary measures, combined with the performance of thorough data quality checks, allow me to feel confident in the authenticity of the questionnaire data presented in this thesis.

5.8.5 Generalisability and Transferability in Interpretive Research

The so-called "paradigm war" (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998) between proponents of positivist and constructivist approaches has raised questions around the merit of interpretive and, more generally, qualitative research. This tension stems from the idea that qualitative methods yield findings that are typically less representative of the wider population than statistical methods. While acknowledging that the subjective nature of qualitative research makes standardisation more challenging, Mason (2018, pp.235-236) argues that the measurability of its findings should not be conflated with their value. Moreover, the notion of an objective interpretive science is described by Schwandt (1994, pp.223-224) as a "paradox".

Yet there is a perception that the value of research lies in its relevance to other settings. Scotland (2012) highlights challenges in generalising interpretive research due to the highly contextualised data it produces. He also argues that interpreting qualitative data relies on the subjective construction of meaning, further limiting the extent to which the findings can be transferred or replicated. However,

Lincoln and Guba (1985, p. 124) argue that transferability is feasible between two or more settings so long as they operate within sufficiently similar contexts. This aligns with Larsson's (2009) five-strand framework, which supports the notion that qualitative findings can be generalised through context similarity and pattern recognition. This is of particular relevance to the examination of graduate apprenticeships in this study; although there are likely structural differences between programmes due to institutional autonomy over curricula, chapter three outlined the operational similarities of post-92 universities. Larsson's pluralist approach suggests that through rich description and reflexive analysis, the findings presented within this study can offer meaningful and transferable insights.

Gamble and Hewlett (2025) expand on this by advocating for the development of explicit analytical frameworks, which they propose to narrow the gap between the abstract and the empirical. Drawing on Bernstein's concept of languages of description, the authors argue that qualitative findings can be generalised when a researcher systematically "translates" between theory and lived experience. This offers insight into the subjective (and often opaque) process of data interpretation, which they posit will increase the transferability of findings. Taken together, these arguments affirm the potential for interpretive research to offer meaningful insights beyond the immediate context.

5.9 Chapter Summary

By outlining the research design, this chapter has established the philosophical and methodological foundation of the study. It challenged the historical conceptualisation of insider research to highlight the specific challenges presented to practitioner-researchers and demonstrated how these were mitigated through the active engagement of reflexivity. Next, the multimethod design was shown to support triangulation and in-depth examination of the subject matter, with iterative adaptations to the research strategy documented transparently. The chapter also acknowledged the limitations of the research methods. Finally, a commitment to ethical research practices was emphasised and the reliability of the findings was affirmed through the concept of physical and intellectual audit trails.

Next, in keeping with the idiographic commitment of the study, a detailed description of the findings is presented in two parts. First, chapter six outlines the apprentice perspective, while chapter seven focuses on staff experiences.

Chapter 6: Findings (Part A)

6.1 Structure of the Findings

The findings are presented across four chapters. First, detailed descriptions of the data are outlined, supported by participant accounts. This is organised into two parts: chapter six focuses on apprentice experiences, while chapter seven considers staff perspectives. Chapter eight then synthesises this into a critical discussion of the findings before chapter nine examines them through the lens of pedagogical literature. By drawing on the perspectives of apprentices, academics and professional services staff, the findings offer multifaceted insight into how value is experienced in apprenticeships.

6.2 Introducing the Findings

Data was collected from 21 learners and 6 members of staff. Their accounts have been anonymised and each individual has been assigned an alphanumeric identifier indicating whether they are a learner (L) or staff member (S). Participant identifiers, roles and manner of engagement are outlined below.

Identifier	Role	Position	Data Collection Method
S1	Staff	Academic	Interview
S2	Staff	Academic	Interview
S3	Staff	Professional Services	Interview
S4	Staff	Academic	Interview
S5	Staff	Academic	Interview
S6	Staff	Academic	Interview
L1, L2	Learner	–	Interview
L3 - L21	Learner	–	Questionnaire

Table 6.1: Participant roles, identifiers, and data collection method

L1 and L2 were recruited during the first phase of data collection and so they engaged with the study via a semi-structured interview. Otherwise, learner data was generated through the questionnaire. However, it must be noted that no unexpected or outlying themes emerged by virtue of the method. This coherence across the findings can reasonably be attributed to the fact that the initial round of interviews informed the questionnaire design.

6.3 Case Study Context

The case study focuses on four graduate apprenticeship programmes in a Scottish post-92 university between 2022 and 2025. Table 6.2 outlines the structure of each programme, including the duration, SCQF award level and the year it was established. Table 6.3 provides a breakdown of delivery mode.

	Established	Duration (Years)	SCQF Award Level
Programme A	2018	4	10
Programme B	2019	3	9
Programme C	2017	4	10
Programme D	2018	4	10

Table 6.2: Programme structure and year of establishment

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Programme A	Online	Online	Online	Online
Programme B	On Campus	Hybrid	Online	N/A
Programme C	On Campus	On Campus	On Campus	On Campus
Programme D	On Campus	On Campus	On Campus	On Campus

Table 6.3: Breakdown of delivery model by programme and year of study

All of the programmes in this case study follow a modular structure. A work-based learning module is delivered each year, carrying a weight of 40-60 credits. The curriculum is supplemented with 60-80 credits of relevant classes to provide breadth of disciplinary knowledge. It is noted that Programme B was designed as part of a pilot scheme to address specific skills shortfalls and so its curriculum aligns with an updated framework. The other three programmes in the study adhere to the original format, which does not require the integration of meta-skills.

While learners from all four apprenticeships participated in the study, no staff from Programme D consented to be interviewed. Any structural and curricular information pertaining to Programme D has therefore been gathered through apprentice accounts and institutional documentation.

6.4 Participant Overview (Part A)

Data was collected from a total of 21 learners, all of whom reported that they were enrolled and participating in a graduate apprenticeship at the time of data collection. Of this, 12 were male and 9 were female. Table 6.4 illustrates the spread of participants across the four programmes.

Programme A	Programme B	Programme C	Programme D
8	5	4	4

Table 6.4: Breakdown of apprentices by programme

There are currently no apprentices under the age of 18 enrolled at the university. Otherwise, at least one participant from every age group engaged with the study. Table 6.5 outlines the spread of ages.

16 – 17	18 – 24	25 – 34	35 – 44	45 – 54	55+
0	7	4	7	2	1

Table 6.5: Breakdown of respondents by age

In terms of entry points, 18 participants joined their programme in year 1 (SCQF level 7) and 3 gained direct entry to year 2 (SCQF level 8) through RPL. Table 6.6 provides a breakdown of the respondents by their year of study at the time of data collection.

Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
6	6	8	1

Table 6.6: Breakdown of respondents by year of study

Participants were asked to confirm their highest qualification prior to enrolling in the apprenticeship. 13 participants joined their programme with either Scottish Highers, a Higher National Certificate or a Higher National Diploma, while 7 individuals hold an undergraduate or postgraduate degree.

Prefer not to say	No formal qualifications	SCQF 5	SCQF 6	SCQF 7/8	SCQF 10	SCQF 11
1	0	0	8	5	5	2

Table 6.7: Breakdown of apprentices' educational background

6.5 Key Themes

Thematic analysis was applied to the learner data, followed by the staff data. From each emerged five key themes, with three points of overlap between staff and learner perspectives (Table 6.8). The key themes were then mapped to the subsidiary research questions. As shown in Table 6.9, each research question is addressed by multiple themes.

Learner Themes	Staff Themes
Mentorship, Support and Engagement	Mentorship, Support and Engagement
Personalisation of Learning and Teaching	Personalisation of Learning and Teaching
The Role of Experiential Learning	The Role of Experiential Learning
Learner Motivation	Retention and Progression
Apprenticeship Value	Navigating External Influences

Table 6.8: Emergent Themes

Subsidiary Research Question	Emergent Theme
How do stakeholder dynamics shape programme design and delivery?	Navigating External Influences
	Mentorship, Support and Engagement
	Retention and Progression
How do apprentices navigate competing stakeholder expectations?	Navigating External Influences
	Personalisation of Learning and Teaching
	Mentorship, Support and Engagement
How do programmes emphasise experiential learning?	The Role of Experiential Learning
	Mentorship, Support and Engagement
	Learner Motivation
How do apprentices reconcile learning and practice?	The Role of Experiential Learning
	Mentorship, Support and Engagement
	Personalisation of Learning and Teaching
	Learner Motivation
How do apprentices articulate programme value in relation to their goals?	Apprenticeship Value
	Learner Motivation
	Retention and Progression

Table 6.9: Mapping of Themes to Subsidiary Research Questions

6.6 Overview of Findings (Part A)

Theme 1: The first theme examines the role of mentorship in shaping the learner experience. In line with Chadwick, Dimungu Hewage and Hazzam's (2025) observations, apprentices who have regular opportunities to engage with teaching staff, workplace mentors, and wider university support services report more positive experiences than those with little or no mentorship.

Theme 2: Although the learning outcomes are prescribed by each framework, there is an expectation that the curriculum content will be a product of tripartite collaboration (Skills Development Scotland, 2016a, 2019a). This theme, Personalisation of Learning and Teaching, therefore seeks to understand the extent to which learner needs are considered during this process, focusing on curriculum design, delivery modes, and the relevance of academic materials to apprentices' practice.

Theme 3: According to SDS (2019a), graduate apprenticeships are considered "work-based learning programmes that lead to degrees". This underscores work-based learning as a central element of the apprenticeship model, which is a core distinction from how traditional undergraduate degrees are taught. Indeed, learners report that the experiential elements of the programme are one of the key differentiators between the apprenticeship scheme and alternative study options. This theme, The Role of Experiential Learning, therefore focuses on work-based learning, including how the content bridges knowledge gaps and enhances practice.

Themes 4 and 5: The findings imply a correlation between motivation and value, and so the final two themes are presented together. First, Learner Motivation focuses on what inspired participants to pursue an apprenticeship, including their reasons for choosing a programme and how they navigate competing priorities. This section also considers why learners exit a programme early. Apprenticeship Value then shifts the focus to the specific benefits and challenges of apprenticeship learning, the perceived advantages over alternative study options, and how each programme contributes toward learners' personal and professional goals.

6.7 Theme 1: Mentorship, Support and Engagement

This theme examines the role of mentorship in shaping the learning experience. SDS deems an effective tripartite structure the key to an apprentice's success (Skills Development Scotland, 2021a) and so, as a condition of agreeing to support their enrolment, the employer is expected to provide the learner with suitable mentorship. Following this, a learning and training plan tailored to the learner's role should be agreed between the apprentice, employer and university.

Apprentices were asked about support in their programme, including experiences with academic and workplace mentors, as well as engagement of wider university support. In the questionnaire, this was phrased as follows:

What is your experience of accessing support or mentorship as a graduate apprentice?

Do you have access to a dedicated tutor or mentor, both at the university and in the workplace? Do you have regular meetings, and who attends those meetings? Reflect on the relationships you have developed with your tutor(s) or mentor(s) – do you feel able to speak up when you have a problem?

6.7.1 Academic Mentorship

Policy rhetoric frames the promise of wraparound support as the cornerstone of apprenticeships, and this arguably distinguishes them from traditional undergraduate degrees. Yet this is identified as an area of concern in the literature. On the whole, employer engagement with apprenticeships is notably low in Scotland (OECD, 2022), and inconsistent levels of mentor effectiveness represents a key variable in learner experience (Chadwick, Dimungu Hewage and Hazzam, 2025).

When asked about their experience of academic mentorship, 14 participants reported either positive or neutral experiences, although 2 of these accounts suggested limited engagement. While a number of participants did not make specific reference to an academic mentor, these individuals provided otherwise positive responses praising interactions with either programme tutors or wider university support services. Of those who explicitly referenced academic mentorship, 8 reported a positive experience, 6 reported a neutral experience and 2 indicated that they have either not been assigned a mentor or else their mentor has not made contact.

Positive	Neutral	Negative	No Mentor	Not Mentioned
8	6	0	2	5

Table 6.10: Participant experiences of academic mentorship

The format of engaging with academic mentors varies across the four programmes, largely due to the fact that they each employ different delivery models for teaching activities. For example, Programme B is the smallest cohort in this study. While learners indicated a limited amount of formal mentorship engagement, the small class sizes and face-to-face delivery easily facilitate informal interactions with academic mentors:

We have an academic mentor and workplace mentor, but our academic mentor only visits for observations 2 times a year and provides feedback on your practice. *L17, Programme B*

As the graduate apprentice cohort is small, I regularly get to chat to my university mentor during class time for informal catch ups. This makes the process less daunting and seeking support is more approachable and accessible. *L13, Programme B*

The other three programmes are much larger in terms of apprentice numbers. As chapter seven will highlight, academic mentorship has been identified as an area for improvement in Programme C and so the process has recently seen a number of changes. These were put in place after participants had engaged with this study, however, and so the accounts below highlight the potential implications for learners in large programmes that do not intentionally structure mentor engagement:

We were told we would be assigned a dedicated tutor within the university and one from our workplace. I didn't get a workplace one until year 3 and I never found out if there was ever one at the university. No meetings, I was left on my own to navigate 90% of it. *L19, Programme C*

I know there is a university tutor but I haven't ever met them for any sort of guidance. *L12, Programme D*

After Programme A was launched, the consistency of its academic support was identified as a concern by the teaching department and a number of permanent academic roles were created to ensure that the apprentice cohort had dedicated support in place. Although the programme's online delivery means opportunities for informal face-to-face interactions are limited, participants find their mentors make an effort to be as responsive as possible from a distance:

There was a lot of uncertainty but we got a guy in who was very, very helpful. Anything you had to go to [name] with, you would get 100% with him. So, even if you just wanted a quick chat, a wee fifteen-minute chat, you could have booked in with him and he was always there for you. So, aye, definitely, the link tutors were very, very helpful. *L1, Programme A*

Our link tutors make themselves, like, really available for us, so we can go on and book a meeting whenever we want. We get access to their diaries and stuff, so I've never had a problem getting support or time with my link tutor. *L2, Programme A*

A number of participants indicated that they do not have access to an academic mentor. Despite this, they expressed satisfaction with the guidance and support they have received through other channels, including module tutors and wider university support services. Several apprentices also described how they adopted a proactive attitude toward asking for help, actively seeking out support via a range of channels when necessary:

Tutors are very helpful and are easy to get a hold of, answering emails as soon as they can. *L10, Programme D*

The tutors within the university are very approachable and friendly with questions I have or concerns. *L21, Programme C*

When it comes to asking questions, seeking advice, contributing to workshops, or on campus, or engaging via [the VLE] - I don't hold back. For me it is a whole learning experience that many other nations would be envious of and should not be taken for granted, so I want to make the most of it in the best way possible. *L8, Programme A*

I have emailed staff for advice or help and without any hesitation, support has been offered. This is a huge part of why I want to stay and complete the degree. [...] This course has been a game-changer for me. *L15, Programme B*

We have a dedicated tutor, and contact details for each appropriate co-ordinator and tutor. Over and above this, the course co-ordinator is always on hand. I recently had to correspond with them and the swiftness of response was remarkable given the high volumes of students and administration they will likely have to deal with on the daily. *L3, Programme A*

6.7.2 Workplace Mentorship

Of those that explicitly referenced workplace mentorship, 71% of accounts were positive, while 29% described negative experiences. A breakdown of responses is provided in Table 6.11.

Positive	Neutral	Negative	No Mentor	Not Mentioned
10	0	4	0	7

Table 6.11: Participant experiences of workplace mentorship

Accounts of workplace mentorship were largely positive, and the majority of participants expressed satisfaction with the support offered. Three reported particularly high levels of engagement:

I have regular meetings with my workplace mentor, where we discuss my progress both at university and at work. He is very eager to give me experience in all areas of our business and is constantly trying to put me in situations and on projects where I can both utilise my skills and have the opportunity to learn more. *L9, Programme D*

I have a workplace mentor who helps me with my work-related coursework and has been a big help through this full experience. My workplace also provides a lot of help. *L10, Programme D*

My workplace mentor is on the floor with me daily and is available to chat and have discussions about practice. *L17, Programme B*

However, the figures presented in Table 6.11 belie the reality of mentorship practices. In some cases, participants described feeling happy with the level of support offered, yet their descriptions did not reflect the level of engagement expected within the graduate apprenticeship model:

They've probably not been as involved since we went online. They used to really make a point of being available when our link tutors were coming into the office. Because we don't have that anymore, it's not quite the same relationship, but they check in to see how I'm getting on with my course from time to time. *L2, Programme A*

Similarly, others reported positive experiences of mentorship but admitted that, given the choice, they would prefer more engagement. In some cases, low levels of mentor engagement led the apprentice to seek support from elsewhere in their workplace:

I have a dedicated workplace mentor and have infrequent meetings with them. However, I'm well-supported within the team I am currently working in. *L12, Programme D*

Mentors are senior employees in the organisation, typically the apprentice's line manager, and so they are often navigating competing demands for their time. While participants displayed empathy toward this, high workloads and time constraints presented recurring barriers to engagement:

I understand the workplace mentor has numerous tasks to do and making time for a student is difficult because the reality is that they can not mentor a student to the level they are supposed to. I accept the fact that mentors cannot always be available but when mine is, I do get guidance and support to some level, which is better than none. *L15, Programme B*

He never really engaged with the uni. He's got a busy job himself so I don't really like taking up his time unless I really need it. It was only when I needed projects for my work-based learning module that I would go to him. *L1, Programme A*

In some cases, the mentor did not appear to have a clear understanding of either the apprentice's role or how they were expected to support them:

My university mentors have been very supportive, however, I feel that my workplace mentor in my first year did not understand their role or my role at times. This did improve in my second and final years. *L14, Programme B*

This may indicate that an unsuitable mentor was assigned from the outset or that they were not suitably equipped by their own superiors. On the surface, this supports Quew-Jones and Rowe's (2022) observation of limited training resources for workplace mentors. However, the next chapter (section 7.3.2) describes the frustrations of an academic who experiences consistently low mentor attendance at information sessions, suggesting an unwillingness to engage even when resources are available.

6.7.3 Wider University Support

Chapter two discussed negative perceptions of vocational programmes due to negative stereotyping of the word *apprenticeship* and misperceptions of the typical vocational learner profile (Lester and Bravenboer, 2020; Young and Hordern, 2022; Van de Weerd, 2023). During their interviews, L1 and L2 were therefore asked how they felt about the language attached to graduate apprenticeships. It is noted that both participants had previously completed apprenticeships, which may positively colour their opinions. Indeed, L1 emphasised that the name does not diminish the programme's value:

To me, the way I look at it, it *is* an apprenticeship. You're doing three years to learn the subject. [...] I mean, it's just a word, to be quite honest with you. It didn't faze me at all. No, it's the end product that bothered me – getting the degree. So, to me, it wouldn't bother me. You could call it anything you wanted, for all I cared. *L1, Programme A*

Although L2 shared the same positive view, they described how others in their cohort had expressed negativity toward the scheme's name:

I've been able to do well at work because of a modern apprenticeship, so I suppose, for me, that's a positive thing because I've had that style of learning before. For other people – I mean, I don't know. I'm one of the younger people in the cohort but I think for other people that have been away from learning for some time, that word does have a stigma about it, like, "I've been in this job for 30 years, I'm not an apprentice", and I totally get that. But no, for me, I don't have a problem with it. *L2, Programme A*

With regard to programme structure, the physical separation created by the 80/20 delivery model can lead to feelings of isolation for apprentices (Dziallas *et al.*, 2021). With this in mind, L1 and L2 were asked if they felt included in the university community. Both participants indicated that although they

did not go out of their way to integrate with the wider university community, they did not experience a sense of isolation or "othering" from full-time students:

We didn't really mix with anybody in the uni. It was basically just us in the class and when we went down to lunch, we sat together, so I wouldn't even be able to tell you if I felt an outsider. We were alright in our class so we didn't really mingle with the other students, but I wouldn't say I've felt like an outsider, no. *L1, Programme A*

In terms of feeling like a normal student, maybe not, but we get emails the same as everybody else. The GA Hub site has all the information, support for the library, contacting the Student Union and all of that – it's all there for us. It's not as if anything is hard to tap into if you wanted it. It's maybe just because we've been online for so long, it's – I wouldn't complain, I wouldn't say we've been excluded or we're held at arm's length or anything like that. It doesn't feel like that. *L2, Programme A*

Beyond the mentorship embedded in the apprenticeships model, a number of participants reported positive experiences when engaging with wider university services, which supports L2's account that the case study university views apprentices as part of the main student community:

The Disability Team has provided me with loads of great tools to use. *L4, Programme A*

It has been amazing. So much help and support out there for everything from mental health to academic help and referencing, etc. The uni is fab for this. *L16, Programme B*

I feel like [the university] is one of the better campuses to carry this out. I have many colleagues and friends who went/are going to others and have been struggling. Lecturers always make time and support you. *L10, Programme D*

Campus is great for asking questions, collaboration and using the library. *L17, Programme B*

Brilliant lecturers and support given from [the university], I have never known of such supportive academic staff and university support, such as student services. *L15, Programme B*

6.8 Theme 2: Personalisation of Learning and Teaching

Graduate apprenticeships disrupt the typical degree model by inviting industry involvement, not only in the initial framework development process but also direct employer oversight through workplace mentorship. However, as raised in chapter four, this introduces a power dynamic wherein an employer can dictate what knowledge is considered valuable (Dillard, Sisco and Collins, 2024), potentially placing constraints on learner agency. This is reflected in a recent description of the scheme:

Because they are designed around the needs of industry, employers will have confidence that what their staff are learning at college or university will directly contribute to the success of the business. (Skills Development Scotland, 2025)

By overlooking the learner, this description implies that learning outcomes prioritise institutional and employer needs. The second theme therefore explores the extent to which apprentices' needs are considered in the design of learning and teaching activities. In the questionnaire, this was phrased as follows:

How do you feel about the education you are receiving through your programme?

Are the learning materials or events delivered online or face-to-face? Do you find the course content to be relevant to your work? Have you been able to apply your new knowledge to your role? Are you involved in identifying work-based projects as part of your studies? As an employee, do you feel that your time in the workplace has prepared you for your degree?

6.8.1 Programme Delivery

A total of 17 apprentices described how academic content is delivered in their programme. Of these, 10 responses were positive, 1 was neutral and 6 were negative. Table 6.12 provides a breakdown of these responses by programme.

	Positive	Neutral	Negative	Not Mentioned
Programme A	2	0	5	1
Programme B	3	1	0	1
Programme C	2	1	0	1
Programme D	3	0	0	1
TOTAL	10	2	5	4

Table 6.12: Participant opinions on programme delivery

While opinions were largely positive across all programmes, individuals whose programmes required regular campus attendance reported the highest levels of satisfaction:

I liked the first year being on campus as it provided the opportunity to build valuable relationships with my fellow students. *L14, Programme B*

All of my current lectures are delivered face-to-face. This is helpful as I find face-to-face lecturing allows me to concentrate on the lecture and gain a better understanding of what is being taught. *L11, Programme D*

The programme is based on attending uni once a week. This is the perfect amount of time to continue with my work commitment while also giving me the opportunity to learn. *L20, Programme C*

We are full-time on-campus, which is beneficial to me as I find this way of learning fits my learning style best. *L21, Programme C*

The delivery of Programme B follows a tapered model which incrementally reduces contact time on campus, shifting from face-to-face to online delivery with each year of the programme. Participants appreciate how this aligns with the increase in independent study and express appreciation for the digital resources available to them:

The blended learning in the second and third years has provided essential time to complete reading and work on assignments. *L14, Programme B*

[The VLE] is a great platform which the lecturers invest their knowledge and expertise in. I am glad that I can always refer back to it and look for resources, recorded lessons and slides which help support my studies. It is a new way of learning for me but I have adjusted to it and feel confident utilising it. *L15, Programme B*

In contrast, Programme A is delivered online from the outset, with in-person activities scheduled at set points during the academic year. Of the four programmes in this case study, it received the most criticism from learners:

To be quite honest with you, they could be doing with more on-campus days to help us. I think that would be beneficial. [...] It was really, really hard and it was just, basically – it felt like when you were doing a paper, you were doing the paper on your own and you had nobody to speak to about it. *L1, Programme A*

I would have preferred more on-campus days to better assist the segregation from work, home life and university. A dedicated time to better focus on the task at hand. *L3, Programme A*

I feel it would benefit from more in-class days, say one day a week. This would help split uni and work. *L4, Programme A*

[Teaching is] mostly online. Communication isn't always the best, which can make studying difficult at times. L6, Programme A

This was not the universal experience in Programme A, however; participant reflections included some praise for the online model. In particular, L2 expressed a strong preference for the programme's self-directed approach:

I feel like the way the academic side of things is delivered is really, really flexible for people that are at work, and the way you can dip in and out of it when you can. I think having it delivered online really, really helps because you can go back, whereas if we were in the classroom and it was being taught, we wouldn't have the option to go back and dip in and out and reflect when we needed to. So no, I think it's been perfect, really, for me.

Despite personally enjoying the online format, L2 also acknowledged the challenges this can present. In the case of Programme A, learning activities are delivered in the evening and apprentices' personal commitments can limit meaningful participation. They offered an example, describing changes made to the programme's delivery pattern after the pandemic:

The University were quite keen to make sure they were keeping in touch with people and wanted to implement weekly sessions in the evenings. Although that helped a lot of people, it was quite difficult for other people to, kind of – if that night didn't suit you, it didn't suit you, and you were almost left behind a wee bit because all the support and answering questions was in those weekly sessions. You can go and watch but it just means that you're not actively involved. The goal posts in terms of how much engagement there's going to be have moved a wee bit, but it's more rather than less. It just makes it quite difficult if you're not participating because you can almost be – not *accused*, but you're not engaging when you never signed up for that anyway.

The physical distance created by the programme's online delivery also presents a challenge. This is particularly pronounced during assessment periods, as apprentices have fewer opportunities to speak with academic staff in person. To mitigate this, L1 (Programme A) described finding valuable support in a virtual community of practice with other apprentices from their organisation:

We had a WhatsApp group and the five of us helped each other. Obviously [my workplace mentor] knows how to be a leader and stuff, right? But I don't know if he would be able to, like, connect with the subject the way that the five of us can, and I found that was more beneficial. We had Zoom meetings and we would have a discussion and try to make sure everybody was alright.

6.8.2 Relevance of Academic Content

Apprentices were asked if they felt the curriculum content was relevant to their job role. 17 provided feedback, while 4 made no reference to curriculum relevance. Table 6.13 provides a breakdown of participant experience by programme.

	Relevant	Somewhat Relevant	Not Relevant	Not Mentioned
Programme A	2	1	3	2
Programme B	5	0	0	0
Programme C	0	2	1	1
Programme D	1	0	2	1
TOTAL	8	3	6	4

Table 6.13: Participant opinions on relevance of academic content

The responses tended toward negative, with three of the programmes' curricula deemed to have little or no relevance to apprentices' day-to-day practice. In contrast, 100% of Programme B participants agreed that the academic content is applicable to their job. Moreover, they report making connections between theory and experience, which allows them to apply their new knowledge in practice:

I do find the course materials to be relevant to my role in my setting. [...] I have been able to apply my new knowledge into my role, for example, carrying out observations [and] activities, planning in the moment. *L14, Programme B*

L15, a Programme B apprentice, feels that the programme has had such a positive impact on their development, their workplace performance has now surpassed that of colleagues:

As time goes on I hope that the degree will marry up with the work place as the degree, in certain aspects, is advanced and I am ten steps ahead of what other people in my work know.

In contrast, opinions on the relevance of Programme A content were largely negative. However, there were positives to be gleaned in places; the negative responses were not combative or derogatory, and some offered caveats to balance their views:

At present, the modules are vastly different from my day-to-day role but, as with everything, there is always information that can be garnered and utilised. *L3, Programme A*

Personally, the modules I have undergone so far are not relevant to my job role but I'm aware this won't be the case for everyone. *L6, Programme A*

The content has been mixed, but that is to be expected within an all-round [subject area] degree. *L8, Programme A*

Programmes C and D received the most negative responses on the subject of curriculum relevance, with more than 80% of apprentices expressing that the content had minimal relevance to their role:

I find a lot of the course content is not relevant to my [site-based] role. *L11, Programme D*

There are some hiccups with the content of the courses being non-related to those on a GA course, as we are already working in industry, compared to standard students who are in the degree to get into the industry. *L19, Programme C*

The content isn't very relevant to my work, it's more based towards consultants rather than contractors. *L12, Programme D*

There is some crossover into my day-to-day workload but mostly it's very specific [subject knowledge]. *L21, Programme C*

However, it was noted that the majority of these respondents were in the early stages of their studies. L19, a Programme C apprentice in their Honours year, acknowledged that the content increased in relevance as they progressed through the programme:

The final year subjects finally appeal to my work, as well as the dissertation, letting me feel as though I can finally talk on points that I know instead of re-wording what I've read either online or in a book.

6.8.3 Personalisation of Curriculum

Each graduate apprenticeship framework has been developed in partnership with industry to ensure that learning outcomes meet immediate and future sector needs. While the university retains control over content design, there is an expectation of collaboration with the tripartite structure. In theory, this means that every apprenticeship offers a bespoke programme of education, specifically designed for adults in full-time employment. A level of flexibility should also be reasonably assumed in terms of elements such as timetabling and assessment deadlines due to the additional commitments faced by learners. However, the findings demonstrate that this is not the universal apprentice experience:

What they need to remember is, we work. Plus, then we have to come back, we need to make our dinners, we need to look after our kids, we need to deal with all that. It doesn't just stop. *L1, Programme A*

The GA needs to be better tailored for the student cohort. At times it feels like the content is designed for the full-time on-campus students and forced to fit the GA cohort, who work full-time. *L7, Programme A*

L9 (Programme D) agreed that, for the most part, the academic content was relevant to their job role but expressed frustration toward the work-based learning module. As the core element distinguishing the programme from a full-time degree, the work-based learning module is designed specifically for the apprentice cohort, yet L9 implies a lack of flexibility in terms of identifying workplace projects:

It feels as though the module is trying to force our work to adapt to the module content when, in my opinion, the module should complement our work-based learning. I do understand that the module has to be very broad and general as there are multiple different disciplines on the course. However, we shouldn't be made to feel bad, guilty or left behind if our work isn't directly tying up with what is being asked of us in class. We also should not be penalised in coursework for this same fact, which many of us feel is the case.

The running order of Programme D's modules was also highlighted as a perceived issue. One learner indicated that the order of the modules did not marry up with their workplace schedule, which implies that apprentices were not consulted with regard to programme design and scheduling:

Most of the content isn't that relevant to the work we are carrying out - or would have been more relevant at a different point within the course. *L12, Programme D*

6.8.4 Protected Study Time

Although employers are not required to make a direct financial contribution to the apprentice's development, there is an additional time cost. The model's 80/20 split means employees are entitled to a 20% reduction in their workload, with one full working day devoted to their studies. This may take the form of day release for face-to-face lectures or, in the case of online delivery, a day away from normal duties to focus on coursework. In fact, SDS (apprenticeships.scot, no date a) characterises any time spent working on apprenticeship tasks as "time spent at work". However, Lester and Bravenboer (2020) caution that teaching delivered online or outside of normal working hours can erode protected study time as learners are less likely to receive this time back from their employer – an observation that is supported by the findings. While learners enrolled in programmes with face-to-face elements are released from work to attend lectures one day per week, a number of Programme A participants implied that they were expected to complete their studies in their own time:

The programme is on campus once a month and online twice a week out of ordinary working hours. [...] I would have preferred more in-campus days to better assist the segregation from work, home life and university. A dedicated time to better focus on the task at hand. *L3, Programme A*

Although we don't get dedicated time at our workplace to go and do studies and stuff like that, because it's something I'm doing already, I *am* getting the time to do it, if you know what I mean? It doesn't feel like an extra thing that I have to do. *L2, Programme A*

While L1 (Programme A) found the academic workload to be manageable, they were candid about completing assessments in their own time, sometimes working into the night to meet a deadline. Furthermore, their reflection indicated that protected study time was inconsistent and dictated by organisational demands:

Once the baby went to sleep, that used to be my time at night to sit and do all my work. Sometimes I'd try to leave as much of the weekend as possible so I tried to do most of my writing at night [...] but I had my good days. I managed to have some free time at work and managed to, like, do it in between when I was doing my own work so it kind of helped me out there.

In some cases, the lack of protected time in the workplace extends to other activities relating to the programme. For L17 (Programme B), it appears that the needs of the business were prioritised over time with their workplace mentor, as they explained they "should have time off the floor together but don't get it".

6.9 Theme 3: The Role of Experiential Learning

Building on ideas explored in the second theme, the third theme seeks to understand how apprentices connect theory and practice and, importantly, how programmes facilitate this. Looking beyond the conventional academic content, this theme delves into the bespoke work-based learning elements of the programmes to explore how experiential learning is emphasised by the case study university, how it bridges the gap between theory and industry, and how it impacts participants' practice. In the questionnaire, this was phrased as follows:

How do the assessed components of the course relate to your professional role?

What format do the assessments take, e.g. essays, exams, practical observation? Does your course include work-based assessments? Do you feel the assessments allow you to accurately demonstrate your knowledge and experience?

6.9.1 Bridging Theory and Practice

The last section discussed how apprentices perceived the relevance of programme content in relation to their job roles. Looking beyond mere relevance, several participants confirmed a clear connection between theoretical learning and workplace tasks. A common theme arising from this was an increase in professional confidence:

I feel my time within employment has set me up for a great understanding of the importance of the course content. *L21, Programme C*

One class is to do with our workplace and roles. By going to [university] and working in the industry, I feel like we gain both knowledge and experience, making us better at our jobs. *L10, Programme D*

The course content has been relevant to my work, and it has helped me gain confidence in my ability to do more technical tasks at work. *L9, Programme D*

In a number of cases, participants described applying what they have learned at university in practice, which is positively impacting their time in the workplace. As well as enabling apprentices to take on new responsibilities, the programmes essentially backfill knowledge gaps, contextualising areas of the roles and allowing them to carry out existing duties with greater confidence:

My learning can be directly applied to the work that I do when I'm not at university, which makes it easier to understand and take on board. *L13, Programme B*

There's been a lot of stuff that I probably knew about and was doing already but probably didn't really fully understand the why or how, or why we do things a certain way. This has made me so much more confident at work because I've got the answers and I have a wee bit more in-depth knowledge than if I hadn't been in the programme. *L2, Programme A*

Even though I felt like a fish out of water when I started in my workplace, the course is teaching me in-depth and detailed knowledge and filling in the gaps of knowledge which, at first, I didn't know about or recognise at work. However, it is making sense now. *L15, Programme B*

It has helped me in that it has made me become a better manager, I would say. Because I just took over the management during Covid, so it kind of – I was applying what I was doing in my paper to what I was actually working with. *L1, Programme A*

The communications module helped me to carry out a book analysis in my setting to consider if there was a gap in certain types of books. For example, certain languages, positive gender roles, and diversity. *L14, Programme B*

6.9.2 Assessing Experiential Learning

Participants were asked to describe the format that assessments take within their programme and whether they feel these allow them to accurately demonstrate both their theoretical knowledge and practical experience. In line with apprenticeships delivered elsewhere in Scotland (Nabi *et al.*, 2025), modules at the case study university are assessed using the standard methods employed in traditional full-time degrees. For the majority of the programmes in this study, all modules (including the work-based learning modules) are assessed through fairly traditional methods. Across all four programmes, feedback was overwhelmingly in favour of the assessment methods, with 16 respondents reacting either positively or neutrally. Only 2 participants gave negative feedback, and 3 gave no opinion on assessment. Table 6.14 provides a breakdown of participants' feedback by programme.

	Positive	Neutral	Negative	Not Mentioned
Programme A	4	1	0	3
Programme B	4	1	0	0
Programme C	2	1	1	0
Programme D	1	2	1	0
TOTAL	11	5	2	3

Table 6.14: Participant opinions on assessment

Due to its bespoke design, the work-based learning modules in Programme B adopt more integrative methods, including portfolios, reflective exercises and observations in the practice setting. These are viewed positively by apprentices:

My course includes essays and a work-based reflective portfolio as assessment. This makes me feel like I'm being assessed on what I know and can do in my career, and not just theoretical and academic learning. [...] The workplace learning reflections help me relate to the course content and translate it into working practice. *L13, Programme B*

I believe that they demonstrate my knowledge and experience as it allows my academic skills, subject knowledge and practical experience to be assessed. *L14, Programme B*

Most of the assessments have been very relevant to my role and enhanced it in many ways. *L16, Programme B*

Across the other three programmes, several participants praised the mix of assessment methods for its ability to showcase a range of skills:

The assessments take the form of class tests, course work, lab reports and in-person campus-based examinations. I believe this approach is good to allow all aspects of assessment to take place, from exam techniques to coursework studies, I believe this accurately showcases my knowledge and understanding. *L21, Programme C*

The assessment components are very much the same as any other programme. It involves exams, lab reports, essays and presentations. The assessments generally do allow us to demonstrate our knowledge gained in both the course and our work. *L9, Programme D*

There are various forms of assessments. Tests, posters, reports. Reports especially help me develop better writing techniques that help me in my professional life. *L5, Programme A*

Not all participants shared this level of enthusiasm, although their criticisms were not directed at the assessment approach in general, but rather at specific elements they did not enjoy:

Written essays might not accurately prove [your understanding] due to difficulties in the formatting/writing process. A necessary evil but a lot of pressure. *L3, Programme A*

Assessment components aren't like anything I have to undertake in the workplace. [...] Labs are a good way to show your understanding, however some of the exams are more like a memory quiz. *L12, Programme D*

I like the essay and report formats but dislike the group work. I'd rather be in control of my own destiny. *L8, Programme A*

However, one account did indicate that they may benefit from a different overall assessment strategy. L19 (Programme C) implied a preference for a more integrative or longitudinal approach, describing assessments as a "chore" due to a lack of perceived relevance to their practice:

I am not evaluated on finished work, rather I have to produce and design full projects myself. [...] I've had to find work-based projects as part of the course but since my field wasn't covered until the final year, it was more nit-picking things apart to force them into the curriculum to make them relevant.

6.10 Themes 4 and 5: Learner Motivation and Apprenticeship Value

Combining themes four and five, this section considers the intrinsic and extrinsic factors that motivate learners, the challenges presented to apprenticeship learners, and the perceived benefits offered over alternative study options. The findings highlight a link between motivation and value, as apprentices measure this in relation to how the programme contributes to their goals. In the questionnaire, this was phrased as follows:

What inspired you to apply for the graduate apprenticeship programme and what motivates you to complete the qualification?

Overall, what do you hope to gain by completing your degree? For example, taking a step toward achieving a career goal, or to satisfy a personal sense of achievement.

6.10.1 Motivation for Undertaking a Graduate Apprenticeship

The key motivators reported by apprentices are career-based, including seeking promotion, lateral progression into a new area of the sector, increased job security, and future-proofing employability. Table 6.15 breaks down the most common motivators and how many times each was cited.

Career Progress	Industry Experience	Financial Benefits	Workplace Confidence	Career Change	Further Study	Personal Satisfaction
11	8	4	4	4	3	3

Table 6.15: Common motivations for undertaking a graduate apprenticeship

Reflecting on their reasons for pursuing an apprenticeship, learners' accounts suggest that while the academic credential is viewed as important, it is not the primary motivator. More often, they view the programme as opening doors that will help them to achieve specific goals:

Being able to get a degree at the end of the 4 year course is what keeps me motivated, as it will open doors for me in my career and allow me to gain better opportunities. *L11, Programme D*

The degree course is what is going to elevate me and it has already taught me more than I imagined. [...] I aspire to succeed and reach a high position and this degree is definitely going to help me reach my goals and dreams that I envision for myself. *L15, Programme B*

I want to become a fully qualified engineer to be able to obtain, at a minimum, my IEng. *L10, Programme D*

I want to go as high as I can with my work, so this was an opportunity. It's not even just with my work, in fact. If you've got a degree in [subject area], you might even get a job somewhere else,

so it opens up a lot of doors for me. And the more secure me and my family are – that's the motivation for me: to make sure I've got money coming in to cover my wife and my family and to make sure we're alright. *L1, Programme A*

L1 also highlighted economic and political uncertainty as a factor in their decision to join Programme A, which implies a perception that the graduate apprenticeship scheme may be vulnerable to future shifts in the political landscape:

With things that are going on with Brexit and stuff like that, I felt like you might not get an opportunity to get a degree paid through your work again. [...] Then Covid, as well. So, funding might not be there.

Another common motivator was having the opportunity to obtain substantial industry experience and develop practical skills alongside a degree. For some participants, this was the deciding factor in their choice to undertake an apprenticeship:

I had [considered other study options] a wee bit but nothing really serious. I think the idea of it being tailored and woven through my job appealed to me. *L2, Programme A*

Experience in the industry and on-site learning. A career that allows me to use practical skills and don't have to be stuck in an office every day. *L12, Programme D*

The opportunity to gain a qualification, not only just while working but gaining industry experience that can be applied to course content. *L13, Programme B*

Next, several accounts mentioned the financial burden of returning to education as an adult. Full-time study can present significant financial barriers (Bathmaker *et al.*, 2016), and the cost of part-time or distance learning is not always covered in full by the SAAS part-time fee grant. The findings indicate that apprenticeships are viewed as a more attractive option due to the fact they are funded and allow learners to earn a full-time salary:

I applied as it was completely funded by SAAS, which was a major benefit for me. I also applied as I knew I needed qualifications in my current job role and this was a perfect fit for me getting to work, earn and study all while learning. *L16, Programme B*

You're not worrying about the student side of being skint all the time, if you know what I mean. You've got a good wage coming in, plus at the end of three years you've got a degree. *L1, Programme A*

The main aspect is the ability to work and complete my studies simultaneously. I completed a year of full-time study and the financial struggle contributed heavily to me dropping out. *L9, Programme D*

A number of apprentices expressed a desire for greater workplace confidence. This was articulated in terms of upskilling, bridging gaps in their existing knowledge, and ensuring they remain up to date with best practice:

I want to be able to share my knowledge with colleagues and always be following best practice, to contribute to a strong and informed workforce that is working towards change for the better. *L13, Programme B*

To capitalise on my experiential knowledge spanning over 40 years, at the same time as studying the latest theories and trends. *L8, Programme A*

With this new job role, I felt personally I was lacking the skillset which is required to succeed. By doing this GA, I thought this would be the best way to enhance my knowledge while also allowing me to learn the physical skills. *L20, Programme C*

I feel this will cover a gap in my knowledge and understanding while instilling confidence in established education from previous courses. *L21, Programme C*

Retraining for a new career was another recurring reason for enrolment, and the explanations offered by participants imply that graduate apprenticeships are viewed as offering more financial security than alternative retraining routes:

This was the most viable option for me to change career. *L14, Programme B*

I needed a career change as I felt stuck in a rut and had to change something in my life. It was and is a big risk and I have sacrificed a lot but [...] I believe that the qualification will lead to a stable career path. *L15, Programme B*

I'm taking the opportunity to retrain, which I hope will enable progression. *L4, Programme A*

This is also supported by staff accounts, which are presented in chapter seven. Reflecting on their mentees, one academic participant suggested that "none of them would have left their job to go to university". While the vast majority of responses indicated that professional goals are the main motivators for undertaking a graduate apprenticeship, the apprenticeship is also viewed by some as a stepping stone to more advanced qualifications:

Another thing that motivates me is that this is the first step in potentially achieving a master's or PhD in the subject I am very passionate about. *L10, Programme D*

It gives me more choices to use later in life as well as opening doors to continue learning. *L19, Programme C*

It has supported elements of work-based learning and has provided me with the desire to study further after graduating. *L8, Programme A*

L11 (Programme D) noted that "completing a degree will also satisfy a personal sense of achievement", and they were not the only participant to express such a sentiment. For some, this represents a lifelong goal. Others, particularly those close to completing their programme, expressed a sense of incredulity at their achievement:

This is something I have been meaning to do for around 25 years. *L8, Programme A*

I never thought I would ever have a degree. I mean, I've been a joiner for sixteen years. If you told me I was going to have a degree in [subject area], I'd be like, "nah, come on, you're joking". It just shows you. *L1, Programme A*

6.10.2 Graduate Apprenticeship vs Alternative Study Options

Some responses indicated that the value of an apprenticeship programme lies beyond the academic curriculum. In some cases, apprentices are willing to overlook a lack of relevance to their own practice, viewing the workplace integration as central to enhancing employability and providing a competitive advantage over traditional graduates:

The content isn't very relevant to my work, it's more based towards consultants rather than contractors. The time in the workplace is the most beneficial toward my degree and will definitely help me with future careers. *L12, Programme D*

I believe that a mix of studying and learning on the job is the best way to progress. I hope to gain confidence in [the subject] as a general field and skills with it, rather than having a fancy certificate with no actual experience. *L18, Programme C*

L9 (Programme D) had previously enrolled in a full-time degree but chose to exit the programme prior to completion. This enabled them to compare their experiences in higher education when articulating the value of the apprenticeship:

The foot-in-the-door aspect of already having an employer that is invested in you is a massive benefit. During my time as a full-time regular student, the other major contributing factor to me eventually dropping out was the fact that the career prospects were extremely slim. By the end of my qualification I will already be approximately 5 years ahead of my peers that graduate through a full-time programme in terms of industry experience. This will allow me to complete my professional institution accreditations very early on in my career, which will aid me in future jobs.

6.10.3 Challenges of Learning While Earning

While many apprentices are motivated by a desire to upskill and progress from their current job role, a number of employers have adopted the graduate apprenticeship scheme into their hiring strategy. This means some individuals are offered the opportunity to enrol as a benefit of accepting a position with an employer. L6 (Programme A) is one such apprentice, and they highlighted the challenges of applying learning in an unfamiliar workplace:

I am working on a work-based project. This is a bit more difficult for students who are also apprentices at work as they only start their jobs at the same time as the uni course.

Although this is less of a concern for apprentices more established in their roles, they are not immune to other challenges. One key stressor described by participants was juggling professional and academic workloads, particularly during periods of assessment:

You're staying up to three o'clock in the morning to do stuff like this so you can get it in before a deadline. *L1, Programme A*

It is stressful but I know I can ask for help without being made to feel like an idiot and tutors will do their best to help. *L15, Programme B*

The workload is demanding when working four days a week on top of your studies during assignments. *L17, Programme B*

Teaching activities are delivered during normal working hours in Programme B, which constitutes the mandated study time. L17's comment therefore suggests that 20% of the working week may not be enough during peak assessment periods. Those in the later stages of a programme acknowledged the demands of completing a degree alongside full-time employment but, overall, felt the challenges were outweighed by the benefits:

It's definitely a great opportunity. I would recommend it to anybody. As I say, I would tell them, but, before they did it: if you're not going to have the commitment to it, then don't do it. That would be my main thing. But, to me, you can't complain because you're getting a degree, you're still able to work, you're still making money, your wages, plus you could better yourself. So, to me, it's a win-win. *L1, Programme A*

When I dropped out of uni the first time, I didn't really think I would ever go back to learning again. And so having that opportunity, being in work and knowing that I'm doing something that's for a career I already know that I like and that I want to be in [...] which is why I like it, and why I think I've stuck with it. I know through experience, if I don't have that qualification, I'm probably going to get stuck at a point and there's going to be a ceiling that I can't go past. *L2, Programme A*

6.10.4 Contribution to Personal and Professional Goals

A previous section described the accounts of apprentices who have been able to apply their learning in practice. This section expands on this to examine how this contextual learning contributes to their goals. L2 (Programme A) described how engagement with the academic materials had enhanced not only their practice but also their reputation with management:

For me to be able to say to my manager, "I'm going to go and do some research on this" and come back and know how to do it, to have that skill and to be quite confident in how to present it, and to have that kind of evidence was great. They were so impressed because I don't think they were expecting it. I think even just being able to present things with that, like, academic knowledge has just opened up a lot of opportunities for me at work because I think I'm taken a bit more seriously.

On the other hand, L17 expressed disappointment that Programme B's structure limits its contribution to their professional goals. As shown in Table 6.2 (p.113), Programme B is three years long, culminating in an ordinary degree. It also does not offer the specific accreditation required for senior positions in the sector, necessitating further study for practitioners wishing to enter management:

The fact I will hold a degree at the end [is my motivation]. However, it's disappointing that we have to do extra modules/other courses to go for [senior] posts, and that we only have up to level 9 and not Honours or master's.

In contrast, an ordinary degree is the goal for some participants. L1 (Programme A) explained how this aligned with their ambitions, meaning they entered the programme with the intention of completing three years:

In my eyes, I was pleased that I got the degree. It helps me with my work and I said if I ever want to come back to it, I can always come back to it. But no, I had my sights set on [an ordinary] degree. If I was alright and I felt like I had enough time, I would have done the Honours but I just felt like, "nah, I think that's me".

6.11 Summary of Findings: Part A

Theme 1: This theme examined the role of mentorship and support in shaping the learner experience. As expected, the findings illustrate a correlation between engagement with support mechanisms and learning experience. Although most participants were satisfied with the level of support they received, the findings support observations in the literature that identify inconsistent support as a structural weakness of the model, as navigating workload and scheduling constraints often presents a barrier to meaningful support in the workplace. However, participants who do not have consistent access to

dedicated mentors displayed a proactive attitude toward seeking out support from other sources within the university or their workplace.

Theme 2: Next, the extent to which learner needs are considered in programme design was explored. Although SDS emphasises the importance of tripartite collaboration to ensure that learning outcomes are relevant, the findings suggest that apprentice input is minimal. Three of the four programmes also mirror their full-time equivalents in structure and content, resulting in apprentices perceiving a lack of relevance to their individual practice. This extends to scheduling; the academic calendar is followed without taking into account the fact that traditional assessment periods may clash with pressure points in the workplace. These challenges are exacerbated by a widespread lack of protected study time, which forces learners to navigate competing demands of academic and professional workloads.

Theme 3: This theme explored how work-based learning is embedded in the curriculum. Participants expressed an appreciation for the value of experiential learning and recognised how it bridges the gap between theory and practice. A number of participants reported enhanced practice in their roles, as well as increased confidence in their professional abilities. By applying learning in practice, apprentices have established positive reputations in the workplace, often attracting the recognition of peers and superiors. Assessments largely mirror those used in full-time degrees, and more prescriptive project briefs can limit how apprentices apply learning in the workplace. Despite this, apprentices appreciated the variety of assessment formats used across the programmes.

Themes 4 and 5: Learner Motivation looked at the intrinsic and extrinsic factors driving participants to undertake a graduate apprenticeship. Career progression emerged as the primary motivator, with a number of participants citing a desire for promotion, increased job security and a degree of future-proofing against potential changes in the political or industry landscapes. Secondary motivators were satisfying a personal sense of achievement and accumulating industry experience while completing their education. Overall, participants viewed the scheme as a valuable opportunity to earn credentials without the financial insecurity of traditional study modes. Apprenticeship Value then considered the benefits and challenges of studying alongside full-time employment. The findings identified workload demands and structural limitations within some programmes as key challenges. They also highlighted a need for increased support of newly hired apprentices, whose unfamiliarity with their workplace may limit full participation. Despite these snagging points, the majority of participants appreciated the opportunity to earn while they learn, describing the scheme as offering a financially secure route to personal and professional development.

Chapter 7: Findings (Part B)

7.1 Participant Overview (Part B)

Interviews were conducted with six members of staff at the case study university between 2022 and 2024, including module coordinators, teaching staff, and individuals involved in marketing graduate apprenticeships. Table 7.1 outlines their participant identifiers, role at the time of engagement, and when each interview was conducted.

Identifier	Participant Role	Programme	Interview Date
S1	Academic	Programme A	March 2022
S2	Academic	Programme A	May 2022
S3	Professional Services	N/A	May 2022
S4	Academic	Programme A	June 2022
S5	Academic	Programme B	November 2023
S6	Academic	Programme C	November 2024

Table 7.1: Staff participant interview schedule

It is acknowledged that the extended data collection timeframe creates a contextual limitation in terms of interpreting findings, as accounts provided in the initial data collection phases may not reflect the programmes' current structures or activities. For this reason, an additional meeting was held with S4 in September 2025. This was not a second interview but a brief discussion to follow up on key points raised in the initial meeting.

7.2 Overview of Findings (Part B)

The first three themes represent points of alignment with apprentice accounts, with the discussion diverging in themes four and five. While this study foregrounds the voice of the learner, the staff accounts described in this chapter provide crucial context with regard to programme structure and curricula design. Moreover, staff participants offer insight into how these conditions are shaped by stakeholder dynamics, funding constraints and institutional pressures.

Theme 1: Mentorship, Support and Engagement focuses on the support elements of the scheme's tripartite structure, examining the role of academic and workplace mentorship in shaping the learner journey. As staff reflect on their experiences, the importance of consistent, learner-centric support is highlighted, as well as the challenges of sustaining meaningful collaboration with a diverse range of industry partners.

Theme 2: Personalisation of Learning and Teaching considers programme structure. Delivery models, academic content and pedagogical approaches are scrutinised to establish how apprenticeships meet the diverse and distinctive needs of apprentices without compromising the academic rigour of the curriculum.

Theme 3: The Role of Experiential Learning focuses on the flagship work-based learning modules to understand how these differentiate graduate apprenticeships from traditional full-time degrees. This theme also considers how practice is assessed within an academic programme and the real-world impact delivered by graduate apprenticeships.

Theme 4: Retention and Progression looks at the key challenges faced by those delivering graduate apprenticeships, including ongoing issues with learner retention and progression. This introduces the topic of motivation and what drives both learners and employers to engage with the scheme. In turn, this raises questions around how academic success is defined and measured in the context of graduate apprenticeships.

Theme 5: Within Navigating External Influences, participants offer their perspectives on a number of external factors that influence the scheme. This section examines tensions between the university's ambitions for its graduate apprenticeship programmes and a number of operational hurdles, including funding mechanisms, employer engagement, and apprentice recruitment practices.

7.3 Theme 1: Mentorship, Support and Engagement

7.3.1 Academic Mentorship

Staff were asked how academic mentorship was delivered in their programme. After Programme A's launch, the teaching department identified that a more consistent relationship with mentors would enhance the learning experience, and so a number of dedicated academic positions were created. S4 described how this decision has benefitted the programme:

The link tutor is assigned from year one and works for – hopefully – the full four-year duration with that student on the programme. So, because of that strong buy-in, they're fully aware of the project they're involved in. They get emotionally involved in the relationship with the student. What I mean by that is, they want them to succeed. They actively want to see them progress.

Apprenticeship frameworks mandate that academic mentors visit each apprentice's workplace. At the time of interviewing Programme A staff, site visits had been paused due to Covid restrictions, which

saw many of their mentees forced to work from home. In response, participants began offering virtual meetings, a practice that has been permanently adopted due to the benefits it offers apprentices:

Contractually, the students have to have one face-to-face on-site visit per term. That's three visits a year, but they also get constant Teams calls or Zoom calls. When I say constant, I mean we slot them in the diary as [the learner] needs them, so they're getting ongoing support. [...] I generally try to have a call once a month with my students, even just a check-in call. *S1, Programme A*

This is supported by learner accounts, which praised Programme A mentors for their responsiveness. Another participant reflected on the positive impact this change has had on the working relationships with their mentees:

We've got a relationship with the students developing. We are available, whereas before it was very much a case of, that's your tutor meeting done. Okay, now what? Now they can say, "could I ask you this quick question?" *S2, Programme A*

This commitment to ongoing support is reflected in other programmes. S5 described how Programme B's small cohort allows them to foster an environment that provides apprentices with holistic support beyond academic needs:

We're quite a small team. They're small classes. They know us well, we know them well. That relationship, I think, makes it hard for folk to come and say, "I'm leaving". I think they know we look after them and so they – there's a level of support that goes beyond teaching and learning. I think there's a level of nurture and there's a level of support there that, for some of our GAs, is an additional layer of support for wellbeing, support for whatever's going on in their life, that they wouldn't have if they weren't in the course, so they stay. I think we do a good job of looking after them.

Shortly before S6 engaged with this study, Programme C had been in a state of flux and had undergone several changes, including programme leadership and curriculum amendments. There had also been a change to the duties of academic mentors on the programme, which demonstrates a recognition of the key role they play in the learning experience. S6 acknowledged a need for greater harmonisation across the tripartite structure:

This is the first time we are organising meetings for the work-based learning module. So, the academic supervisor, they have to make two visits. They have to visit the workplace – the site. They see what the apprentice is doing there and they have to meet with the mentor. [...] It's important to develop a connection between the two – the supervisor and the mentor.

7.3.2 Workplace Mentorship

When asked about their experience of employer engagement in Programme A, S2 candidly described it as "completely and utterly scattergun". They explained that workplace support often dwindles when apprentices progress through the programme, as mentors assume their input is no longer required. S2 offered their thoughts on why some take a more hands-off attitude than others:

It's really, really inconsistent. So, year one is probably the easiest to pin down the mentors. The easiest to actually get people to commit to supporting. This sounds terrible but as they start to see results coming through from these students, the organisations go, "actually, I'm just going to let them run with this". They're doing so well and they're delivering projects to add value to the organisation, so some companies are just going, "actually, no, we'll just let them get on with it". Other organisations are much more closely involved, but it's not consistent.

This variability of workplace support was echoed in a number of staff accounts. Another Programme A academic explained that such gaps in mentorship are difficult to mitigate as they are frequently the result of external factors, such as staff turnover:

That can be quite a strong relationship or it can be quite standoffish. We, as a university, can't really influence that, we can only make the mentor aware of what we would expect, but I don't go chasing people. [...] In some organisations, the support is excellent, the mentor is really up to speed and the student has a good link with them. With others, it's a bit patchy, you know. That's just the nature of what can happen. What we've also seen, just because of what's happening in industry, staff are moving on. So, maybe the mentor has moved on, or they've been promoted, or the business is cost-cutting and they're no longer there. *S1, Programme A*

As touched upon in chapter six, in some cases, workplace mentors demonstrate a lack of clarity around the apprentice's role or how best to support them. Yet it appears that many are unwilling or unable to make use of the training or resources offered by the university. S5 (Programme B) expressed their frustration that, despite sustained efforts to connect with mentors, engagement remains low:

We set up a number of workplace mentor events. In-person, online, during the day, early evening. I'm conscious that people are at work and they're busy, but they're really poorly attended. I get that folk are busy and whatever but there's also an expectation, I think, if you commit to supporting any student, whether it's an HNC or a degree student or a GA, you've then got a commitment to find out about their programme. I mean, even the online sessions, I record them and I send them the link to the recording and say, if you couldn't make it along in person and you couldn't make it to the online one, here's the recording, but you still get problems coming up. So, you have a chat and you ask, "did you come to the meeting?" and it's "no, I didn't have time, I was working". "Did you manage to come to the online session?" "No, I didn't have time". "Did you watch the recording?" "No, I've not had time to do that". And I think, well, this is why we are where we are.

7.3.3 Employer Commitment to the Programme

Discussion with staff turned to the apprenticeship model's 80/20 delivery. While protected study time is a core tenet of the tripartite agreement, this document is not a legally binding contract. Rather, as S5 pointed out, it is an "article of good faith". Reflecting on how apprentices should be accommodated in the workplace, S2 (Programme A) experienced a disconnect between their expectations and reality. They described how apprenticeships are deprioritised by many employers, often resulting in negative consequences for the learner:

We say to employers, "you should give your students a day a week to do their studies" but the reality is lots of employers go, "you'll do your studies in your own time". Even though they're working on things that are benefitting the organisation, that's an add-on. [...] We've had a couple of students who went on Interruption of Study because their workplace was just not being supportive enough, and that's an issue.

The importance of protected study time was underscored by S4 (Programme A), who expressed their disapproval toward practices that contravene the employer's commitment to facilitating the learning journey:

What we require is that they are given sufficient time – quality time – to undertake their academic study because it is a rigorous programme and the graduate apprentices do require that time given by their workplace. [...] Some organisations – they shouldn't do this, but they're asking GA students to use their holiday allocation to come to the on-campus days, which is against the contractual obligation. We discourage that at every attempt once it's known to us.

It was also highlighted that, in some cases, learners' workloads have not been reconfigured to reflect the 80/20 split. However, it seems this is due to misconceptions of what the programme entails rather than a reluctance to accommodate the apprenticeship. As S5 (Programme B) explained, employers may be unaware of the academic demands placed on their employee:

Every year we'll encounter challenges and difficulties with a number of workplaces and managers and mentors not understanding the programme, not understanding the qualification that the person is going to get [...] and just, at times, not having a basic understanding, which frustrates me. This person is not a student on placement, this person is an employee of your organisation, in your workplace, who is studying a programme that's fitting alongside their day-to-day practice. [...] I say, "when you ask them to do staff cover on a Friday, that's what they miss. They've lost a lot of time".

These examples indicate a need for consistent messaging and increased clarity in the communication between the university and employers. However, as evidenced in section 7.3.2, academic staff often struggle to engage employers or workplace mentors due to demanding schedules. Furthermore, four years is a significant period of time, which invites the risk of unforeseen challenges that create a barrier

to an apprentice's progress. Employers may sign the tripartite agreement with positive intentions but changing organisational needs, staffing requirements or financial pressures may make it impossible to honour their commitment. Indeed, S5 (Programme B) offered an example of this scenario:

We did, unfortunately, have one person who had to withdraw because their employer was no longer able to support their day release on the Friday. [...] The employer's circumstances had changed. Their staffing had changed, the [clients'] needs had changed, and it was just very much a case of "we can't let you out on a Friday".

7.3.4 Top-Down Support for Mentors

Although learners reported largely positive experiences of academic mentorship, staff acknowledged areas for improvement, particularly with regard to strengthening their relationships with employers. However, this commitment is constrained by resources:

We go out to settings to do the observations of practice that we need to do as part of the programme, but I'd love for us to have more time as a team for academic tutors to go out and do visits. Not to assess, just to go out and build relationships and get to know the setting and get to know the team that the GA is working with to support that relationship more fully. But we don't get time allocated to do that, so it's not possible. *S5, Programme B*

If [tutors] need any support from the university or the division – like, this is the first time we are organising site visits so the faculty member, they ask for the head of division to do the approval. [...] They do the approvals but there is nothing from the university in terms of support for this type of position. *S6, Programme C*

7.4 Theme 2: Personalisation of Learning and Teaching

7.4.1 Programme Structure and Delivery Model

As described in chapter six (Table 6.3), apprenticeships at the case study university run the gamut in terms of how teaching is delivered, which provides an opportunity for intra-institutional comparison. Participants were therefore asked for the rationale behind each delivery model. Launched in 2018, Programme A was intended to be delivered online from the outset. Staff described the benefits of this approach, particularly how it reduces the tangible impact on employers compared to the traditional day-release model:

[Programme A] is oversubscribed every year. [...] I think there are a number of reasons for that. I think one of them being that, predominantly, graduate apprenticeships operate on day-release. We view that criteria slightly differently in that our day-release is not predetermined by a set day. So, our delivery is predominantly done online with two workshops over each academic term, and we believe that this works for our target market for our graduate apprenticeship really well. [...] Our interpretation of what a GA delivery method should look like – I think we've done that really

well in our programme. We've stated that it's 80/20 but how you factor that into your working week is completely up to you. As long as you're giving that candidate that appropriate time, we're not going to outline to you how you do it. *S4, Programme A*

Because it's essentially online, there's less impact on the business in terms of releasing somebody. And I don't know if there's maybe a bit more – that might be a bit more about personal and professional development. You might have an employer who actually says, "yeah, you know, if they want to do their GA, I'm not going to have to release them one day a week". There's less tangible impact in terms of the day-to-day operations, whereas with other programmes, you're having to manage around that. *S3, Professional Services*

Programme B, on the other hand, operates a hybrid model. Learners are taught face-to-face for the first year of the programme, with a blended approach in year two, and then the third year is delivered online. S5 explains that the rationale for this model was partially motivated by financial uncertainty, exemplifying how institutional pressures shape apprenticeship design:

Any programme with small numbers and small class sizes is always at risk of being subsumed by something else or, worse than that, being cut entirely. I'm always mindful of resources and trying to be economical with delivery where we can, hence the online [delivery for year three]. It's not just because they're more independent in their study skills at that point, there is also a resource saving for staff as well, to make it more economically viable in terms of delivery cost.

Despite their concerns that Programme B may be subsumed by a larger programme, S5 clarified that they have no intention of modifying the current delivery pattern, either to reduce costs or to influence recruitment by appealing to employers:

I have no doubt that it would suit employers in [the sector] far better if we didn't request a study day for everyone doing the programme on a Friday. If we moved it to online delivery in the evening, or moved it to weekend delivery, or said, "we'll provide a lot of resources online and you need to give your GAs seven hours of protected time a week to engage with it as and when". I've no doubt that we would recruit more heavily to the programme. I've also no doubt, though, that the issues we just discussed around retention and progression and graduation would go in a different direction. [...] As long as we continue to have employer support for the study day, I'll continue to keep the model of delivery the same.

Programme C employs the traditional day-release model, with learners attending face-to-face lectures once a week for the duration of the degree. With the exception of the work-based learning elements, Programme C's modules are not bespoke, but rather apprentices join the equivalent full-time degree cohort for lectures. This decision was made, in part, to save costs by making use of existing resources.

In contrast with S5's concerns around the increased costs of tailoring apprenticeship delivery, S6 implied that Programme C's less personalised approach bears minimal financial impact:

As for the financial aspects, there's no burden on the university or the student or the employer's part. It's from the government, so it is fully funded.

The decision to pool apprenticeship and full-time resources was also informed by the practical nature of the programme, which necessitates access to campus facilities. Furthermore, S6 expressed a desire to enforce a separation between work and study:

They need one full day. They have to come to the university and also there are independent working hours for each module. Like, for one 20-credit module there's 160 hours additional, so they have to do that work. So that, I think, is a break. Not completely a break, but still some time from the work. [...] And additional time in the lab. We give them this facility if they are busy, so out of office hours they can use our laboratory.

The structural alignment of full-time and apprenticeship provision implies that resource efficiency was prioritised during the design process. This interpretation was confirmed by S3 (Professional Services), who described having "debates" with academic colleagues around apprenticeship timetabling:

Some programmes have had to align with full-time delivery because of the [student] volumes that we've got. [...] Some of those logistical things have been quite challenging.

7.4.2 Evolution of Graduate Apprenticeship Curricula

While Programmes A and C largely align with the structure and content of their full-time counterparts, staff described how they are receptive to learner feedback. S4 (Programme A) explained that they are happy to adjust elements like submission deadlines to better accommodate apprentices' schedules:

If you asked any student on the programme, "does the programme team work on feedback?", hopefully the majority of them would say, "yes, they take this on board". It might be minor things like, okay, we work Monday to Friday. For full-time students, the normal assessment hand-in day is a Friday at five o'clock. For a graduate apprenticeship student, can that be a Sunday? Yes, no problem.

Staff have also observed the needs of learners and employers in the years since the programmes were launched. In response, incremental changes to content and assessment have been implemented:

In our current delivery, the work-based learning module involves three assessment components. It runs over three terms. If they don't complete one assessment, they can't progress to the next level of study, so there's a delay in progression. Reducing the credit element and moving work-based learning over into one dedicated term serves us twofold. It benefits the candidate in

regard to if they miss an assessment, they can progress and pick it up at the re-sit diet. Secondly, and this is the major justification of why I reduced the credit element, is the element of a break. A holiday. Because for graduate apprenticeship students on our current method of delivery, it's ongoing. It never really stops for four years. [...] That was the major justification. It was based on student feedback. *S4, Programme A*

For the first two years, the link tutor role was actually done largely by people who were associate lecturers. They weren't employed by the university so there wasn't that sense of commitment to the course, maybe even from the university's point of view. [...] Since we've been appointed to manage the students, things have changed because our relationship, the interaction between the student body and the link tutors, has been a lot more solid. When we say to students, it'll be [S2] for four years, that's what it will be. So, the same link tutor is in charge of that individual, or working with that individual, all the way through their studies. That's the idea anyway. The consistency is, I think, already reaping rewards for us. *S2, Programme A*

We sent a survey to [employers], like, what do you want from this GA programme? What is your feedback? What type of content do you want us to include? And what we updated is also based on their demands. We added several contents to the programme. [...] Previously, there were no options and now we are providing options. We added a list of elective modules, now it's better understood what [the learners] need. Previously, it was only [module name] and students had to take that. Now we have added two electives. [...] Similarly with the final year, there's one module previously they had to take but now we are looking forward to adding two options. [...] Each industry student may have different – may need different things and different skills, so that's based on their requirements. *S6, Programme C*

Programme B was launched in 2019, forming part of a pilot scheme to address specific skills shortages in a regulated industry. Its structure conforms to a newer framework (in essence, GA 2.0) in which SDS has embedded meta-skills, described as "timeless higher order skills that create adaptive learners and promote success in whatever context the future brings" (Skills Development Scotland, 2019b). Evidencing these meta-skills is a stipulated learning outcome, which influenced the decision to design a suite of bespoke modules for this programme. S5 reflected on the employer feedback that prompted the introduction of meta-skills:

The meta-skills GAs came about for exactly that reason – because employers went to SDS and said, pretty much, "we are fed up with employing graduates who are very knowledgeable and have wonderful ideas but can't actually – they're not ready for the workplace. They don't actually know how to do the job, so can you do something about that, please?" Stop sending degree-qualified people that are very clever but don't actually know how to work in a team, don't have very good communication skills, they're just not – they don't know how to transfer their degree knowledge into their workplace context. There were then four GA programmes across different disciplinary areas and different universities in Scotland that were developed with the meta-skills embedded in the framework.

At the time of interviewing S5, no structural changes had been made to Programme B since its launch. These had not been necessary due to the bespoke curriculum, which apprentices unanimously praised for its relevance to their practice. S5 reflected on the design process, explaining how both industry and learner needs were embedded throughout the curriculum:

As well as doing the mapping to the framework and the mapping to the graduate attributes, we also had to map the content to the meta-skills framework that was provided by Skills Development Scotland as well. So that was the kind of initial – before we even got to deciding on exactly what readings and what the lectures were going to look like, the overview of the programme started from that point. [...] I think we really embraced [the meta-skills]. We didn't ever see them as an add-on and we said from the start that it makes perfect sense. This is just kind of what we do. We're training practitioners, we're not training philosophers or folk that are going to be just theorising. We train people that go out to do a professional job. So, it made sense to us from the start and I don't think we were particularly fazed by it, but we did feel that they need to be threaded through and they need to be embedded and we need to be talking about them. They're not an add-on or a tick-box.

7.4.3 Academic Content

Work-based learning modules at the case study university carry a weight of 40-60 academic credits, so apprenticeships are supplemented with 60-80 credits of additional classes. While these must align to "a broad set of employer-defined outcomes against which universities can position their intended provision" (Skills Development Scotland, 2019a), no stipulation is made in terms of how this should be presented, leaving curriculum design open to interpretation. In the cases of Programmes A and C, their respective teaching departments opted to align apprenticeship curricula with content from the full-time offering:

There are what we call the theory modules – modules that the full-time students would be doing as well. [...] The lecturers who deliver those to the full-time cohort deliver them to the graduate apprenticeship cohort, and that is done through support sessions on a weekly basis. *S4, Programme A*

There's at least one session a week for an hour and sometimes there's a tutorial every few weeks, but they're generally in the evening because the selling point of this programme is that it's one hundred percent remote. [...] There's a lot of independent work put in by the students because I think the module is effectively the same as a full-time student would get, the expectation is that they'll just do more reading around it. *S1, Programme A*

It's the standard lectures, yes. [...] What we have in the existing division, we had to use those resources. [...] The one-to-one support with the student is only related to one module – the work-based learning module. The other modules, the GA students and other students are treated in the same way. *S6, Programme C*

The design of Programme B was approached differently, as described by S5 in section 7.4.2. Reflecting on the programme's delivery in the years since its launch, S5 described how the choice to separate full-time and GA cohorts was reinforced by the distinct needs of the learner demographics:

It's a separate programme. It has different modules. It's the same delivery team, if you like, but they're taught entirely separately. It kind of just sits as its own separate programme. [...] I'm mindful that it's additional resources and you could put them into a class with another group of students, but I prefer that it's separate. They're quite a discrete group; they have their own identities as students and as practitioners, the GAs, that wouldn't necessarily sit easily alongside another full-time programme.

7.4.4 Pedagogical Approaches to Teaching Apprentices

Staff consistently expressed how interactions with apprentices encouraged them to reflect on and adapt their pedagogical approaches. In contrast with the traditional teacher-student relationship, one participant characterised their role as facilitative. They emphasised how, in apprenticeships, personal and professional development is as valuable as academic achievement:

I think our job, or part of our job, is to facilitate the journey of where they're starting and where they're going to end up, and more so how they can actually sell the skills they've acquired. [...] We've actually started focusing on that being central to what they're doing, so the degree is almost a byproduct. What they're actually doing is developing themselves towards this aim of a progression of some sort. *S2, Programme A*

This sentiment was echoed by S1 (Programme A), who viewed the relationships with their mentees as more akin to professional coaching than academic supervision:

They've got that experience. They've got that knowledge. What we've got to try and do is draw it out further. That's the way I see my role for this because otherwise it's a lecturer-student relationship, and I don't see it like that. I think it's a professional relationship. It's not like just saying to somebody, "this is how you need to improve". It's more developmental. That's my take on it, anyway.

Discussion turned again to apprentice engagement, this time in the context of the programmes' taught modules. Reflecting on their experiences, S4 (Programme A) offered a comparison between teaching apprentices and teaching full-time students:

I found it more rewarding than teaching a hundred students in a lecture theatre where there is no engagement. [...] On the GA route, there is engagement, there is conversation, there's dialogue taking place. I suppose what I'm saying is that on a GA route, there are aspects of more enjoyment from a lecturer position and, as such, your role is what you signed up to do: to teach. To engage with your field of study rather than simply delivering a PowerPoint for an hour to a

classroom that feels like they aren't taking it in. They're there because they have to be there, or because there's nothing better to do on a Monday morning [laughing].

S5 (Programme B) complemented this account, describing how their pedagogical approach is shaped by the cohort's distinct needs. Mindful of apprentices' time constraints, class activities are designed to maximise efficiency:

I think what we do slightly differently, and something we do really well on the GA programme, is the prep tasks or the consolidation tasks for every week. If they do them, they build something towards the assessment. [...] They've still got work to do towards the assessment but some of it has been prepared as we've been going through. That is just because I'm so mindful that they're in work four days and they're with us on the Friday so, effectively, assessments are written in the evenings and weekends because they don't have any other time to do it. It's about me trying to kind of help design the programme and the modules to support them through that. We don't necessarily do that on our other programmes because full-time students, you know, should be in the library.

7.4.5 Apprentices' Attitudes to Learning

In general, staff reported high levels of motivation from learners enrolled in their programmes. One participant offered their view on why motivation is often more evident in apprentices and part-time learners compared to full-time students:

There is more engagement on the part-time and GA routes. The reason why is because the majority of them are working towards the degree programme for professional reasons and personal enjoyment, so they want to get as much out of the programme as they can. [...] They actively want to engage with their cohort and their lecturer, and sometimes challenge the lecturer on what they're actually delivering. *S4, Programme A*

The word *challenge* was used to characterise apprentices several times, with S3 describing them as "a challenging group" and "quite demanding". This word is not intended to demean or chastise, however; staff recognise that successfully balancing full-time work and study requires a level of directness:

If they're on campus, they're on one day a week, so they can't faff about. They can't come back to see you tomorrow. So, they can be quite demanding from that point of view but as long as they do it professionally and respectfully, I don't have any issue with them challenging me or anybody else. *S3, Professional Services*

S3 was then asked if graduate apprentices typically appear more confident than full-time students, not only in terms of challenging ideas but also when engaging with peers or proactively seeking help:

From my experience, yes, they are. There's probably a difference there, and it might be an age and confidence thing.

The idea that apprentices are more direct in their communication was reiterated by S6 (Programme C), who reflected on their greater need for structure and clarity around deadlines compared to their full-time peers:

If you release the assessment in the middle of the term, that's fine with [full-time students] but the apprentices, the GA students, they will prefer to get the idea of each and every thing before the term started. They will need what type of assessment we will have, what is the deadline, when you will release, and when the exam will be. So, they need more clarity as compared to the non-GA students.

This preference for clarity, structure and direct communication can be understood through the lens of intersectionality. While the typical undergraduate student is assumed to be a school-leaver with limited responsibilities (Sykes, 2021, p.81), apprentices are navigating the pressures of degree study, full-time employment and personal commitments. These overlapping conditions often leave them time-poor, shaping interactions in the learning environment and ultimately accounting for their "demanding" approach. Staff accounts also align with Balloo, Pauli and Worrell's observations that age and caring responsibilities shape student expectations of tutor responsiveness and clarity. In this sense, such attitudes likely reflect the realities of negotiating intersecting identities rather than an inherent communication style.

7.4.6 Internal Challenges and Influences

Entrenched cultural stigma and misperceptions of vocational study present a significant challenge to graduate apprenticeships, which is often compounded by snobbery within academia (Mazenod, 2016; Hanshaw, 2024). Indeed, Basit *et al.* (2015) found that a number of university lecturers were reluctant to deliver work-based learning, believing that this would diminish their roles from educator to trainer. This concept was explored during interviews with staff, who were asked if they had witnessed similar reticence. Participants in academic roles reported experiencing little to no reluctance from colleagues:

"No" is the simple answer to that. I've never experienced anyone that has been involved in a graduate apprenticeship feeling that the role has been diminished somehow because they're associated with a graduate apprenticeship programme. I suppose credit for that has to go to [the department] because they have situated it in such a position that it is regarded as a full-time degree programme. S4, Programme A

However, it was pointed out that stigma may be linked to the accepted norms in a specific disciplinary area or industry sector. S5 (Programme B) explained that on-the-job training is typical in their area, so apprenticeships tend to attract fewer negative perceptions:

I don't know necessarily about stigma because it's an apprenticeship, but that might be just the nature of [subject area] because there's very much an understanding that you train on the job.

S6 (Programme C) alluded to indirect resistance in their department. However, this is largely due to logistical and time constraints rather than overt negativity toward apprenticeships:

So far, I didn't have any negative feedback or hesitation, I think, from any faculty member. But they need more time, definitely. Like, now they are organising the site visits, so this is some additional time. They need additional time and resources to manage these things.

While the majority of reflections from academic participants were positive, S1 (Programme A) offered a more nuanced perspective, drawing on their own time spent in industry:

It might just be due to the communication within the HE environment; people don't realise there's so much value in working with learners in industry. For a lot of academics, it would really help them to get closer to industry rather than just reading about it in a publication. You know, actually being hands-on and being out. If you think about it, academics will teach full-time students doing undergraduate degrees, so there's really no difference teaching someone who's doing a graduate apprenticeship. [...] It's probably more about awareness and education, I reckon.

Despite academic participants in this study encountering only positivity toward teaching apprentices, the case study university is not immune to the negative attitudes described in chapters two and three. As the only participant employed in a professional services role, S3 dispelled the notion that their colleagues are universally accepting of apprenticeships in higher education:

At the risk of being hit by a bolt of lightning, yes, absolutely. Amongst colleagues in [case study university] – academic colleagues. [...] There certainly was a reluctance among some individuals, some sections of the university, to take it on board. [...] I think there was a perception that the students wouldn't be of the calibre of the full-time students because there was that perception of, well, if they could have gone to university, why did they choose a different route?

S3 clarified that this reluctance was demonstrated in the initial period following the scheme's launch. They have since witnessed a shift in attitude from some academic staff who had previously expressed their disinterest, which S3 attributed to the university establishing a pattern of successful outcomes:

The feedback in terms of their performance is – quite frankly, it's outstanding, and I think now colleagues are seeing that.

7.4.7 Aspirations for Future Development

Looking beyond the practical elements of curriculum design, participants were asked what changes they would make if they were not subject to structural and budgetary constraints. While their answers varied, they demonstrated a common desire to enhance the learning experience.

S2 (Programme A) emphasised their learner-centric vision for apprenticeships, arguing that relational pedagogy should be more widely adopted:

I think I'd probably create more opportunities to discuss that ultimate question: what's in it for them? For me, it's the thing that defines not just the graduate apprenticeship programme but, actually, the whole higher education system. [...] That's what I think is important at the moment. We've got a lot of work to do.

S3 (Professional Services) expressed their desire to reach more learners, both by increasing apprentice intake and by expanding the university's offerings to meet a wider range of industry needs:

The programmes that we offer and the number of places that we have are constrained. [...] We would like to see that autonomy to develop the programmes that we think are appropriate, and we would like to see greater flexibility around the numbers. You know, if we can identify sixty Business Management [applicants], let us do that rather than holding us to forty.

S5 (Programme B) pointed to a need for greater engagement and collaboration. Echoing a comment made by S6 (section 7.3.1), they articulated the benefits of strengthening the tripartite relationship:

It's really all about relationships. Relationships with the [professional] setting, relationships with the theory and learning and what it looks like in practice, and having an environment on campus that would support that. I suppose that's what I would focus on.

7.5 Theme 3: The Role of Experiential Learning

7.5.1 Integrating Work-Based Learning

The work-based modules in Programmes A and C focus on integrative projects, requiring apprentices to deliver measurable improvements within their workplace. Programme A takes a flexible approach; project topics are identified by the apprentice, enabling their learning to be shaped by organisational needs. S1 (Programme A) described how they encourage their mentees to drive the design of the project, deferring to them as a subject expert in their field:

We're very flexible in the type of projects that students can do because it's coming from the organisation, so unless I feel it's a bit light and there's not enough depth in it, I'm certainly not going to stop someone. [...] I'm not going to say to someone, 'that's a really good project' or 'that's not so good a project', because they've got that experience.

S2 (Programme A) echoed this, explaining how they encourage their mentees to critically evaluate the value proposition of their project before selecting a topic:

We've been really focusing on getting them to look at the project proposal in a different way. What's the cost-benefit analysis? How is the organisation going to benefit? Because if it's not going to benefit, why are you doing it? [...] We don't have students doing something just because they think it's a good project.

In contrast, the work-based assessments in Programme C take a much more prescriptive format, with apprentices given a defined brief to carry out in their workplace:

In the first year, their project is mostly related to [module name]. In the second year, [...] they have to do some projects on what type of sustainability they can bring to the organisation. In the third year, their project is related to project management. *S6, Programme C*

Programme B places equal emphasis on the importance of work-based learning as a cornerstone of the scheme. However, it does not follow this project-based approach to work-based learning due to the fact that the programme was developed to meet the needs of a specific, practice-based industry. Assessment of the work-based learning modules for Programme B is carried out through workplace reflections, a longitudinal portfolio and a practical observation within the professional setting.

7.5.2 Bridging Theory and Practice: Part B

As discussed earlier in the chapter, the work-based learning modules are supplemented by academic classes to ensure breadth of disciplinary knowledge. At the case study university, the assessment methods in these supplementary modules mirror the full-time equivalent, which means apprentices are required to complete a traditional diet of essays and exams. While it can be argued that this aids in preserving the academic rigour of the degree, staff accounts suggest that this approach overlooks the unique needs of apprentices. One participant expressed the view that practical outcomes are of greater value in the context of an apprenticeship, suggesting that this should be held in higher esteem than the delivery of abstract theory:

We want them to apply theory to real-life problems, and the way they do that is more important than scattering loads of journal articles about [subject area] theory. The results are much more important because that's the thing that's going to give them the real edge, and that's the thing that will get them the promotion in the future. *S2, Programme A*

S5 (Programme B) also called for recognition of apprentices as practitioners. They put the onus on the wider academic community, challenging the utility and accessibility of academic publications in their current form:

We need to shift as academics. We need to shift the culture a bit more in higher education in terms of, if we want journal articles and literature to reach practitioners, we need to write it in an accessible form. If we don't, it will reach academics, it might reach policy holders, it might reach legislators, but it's not necessarily going to reach [practitioners]. So, if you want to reach those folks, you need to write it in a way that they find it accessible and useful in their practice.

Graduate apprenticeships are framed as a vehicle for widening access (Skills Development Scotland, 2021b), so this raises an interesting question around the accessibility of academic materials with which students are expected to engage. Expanding on this, S3 (Professional Services) pointed out a tension between increasing access through RPL and the demands of apprenticeship curricula:

It's trying to get that balance. You want to recognise the industry experience, the skills and knowledge that somebody has built up, but then you're talking about putting them into what is still an academic programme.

7.5.3 Measuring the Impact of Experiential Learning

Although the success of a graduate apprenticeship is generally measured through learners' academic attainment, programmes have the potential to deliver significant impact for partner organisations. S3 (Professional Services) reiterated the importance of recognising the scheme's contribution to industry, highlighting the need for a more nuanced overview of programme success:

The other thing for the employer is the work-based learning element of it. The apprentice is bringing that into the business, you know, so the business is getting a direct business benefit from that. We've not been very good, maybe, at capturing and measuring some of that, and I think that's something that we probably need to be a bit smarter about, trying to quantify some of that.

This point was reinforced by S2 (Programme A), who offered examples of work-based projects carried out by apprentices. In some cases, their contributions have had a significant organisational impact:

We've got some great examples of huge investment into organisations as a result of projects run by our GA students. You know, [industry partner] has invested a million pounds into the plant there to facilitate higher productivity on the back of a project proposal from a first year student. Unbelievable, but that's the quality of people we're working with.

They went on to explain that the value apprentices are delivering for employers through work-based learning projects is tangible evidence of their development, which is a catalyst for career progression:

[The work-based project] actually has to have a tangible benefit for the organisation, and that's where we're seeing students across the four years developing an internal reputation as people who are able to deliver. I think that's probably why we're seeing, towards level 10, this ability for students to move into better jobs – because they've actually got a really good track record.

Enhancing employability is also a focus in Programme B. S5 credits the embedding of meta-skills with introducing another facet of learner development to the scheme, suggesting that emphasising these learning outcomes offers apprentices a competitive advantage over traditional graduates:

I think sometimes the GAs get fed up with us talking about [meta-skills] but they then also develop that language, so when they're evaluating their practice, when they're going for job interviews and so on, they have the right words to be able to describe their skill set and their strengths and what they still need to develop. It gives them that tool, if you like, to be able to talk about it. Which, again, I think is really useful because I don't know that degrees on their own necessarily do that.

7.6 Theme 4: Retention and Progression

7.6.1 Retention

Of the three programmes explored in this chapter, only Programme B is free from retention concerns. S5 noted that, due to the demographic in the subject area, Programme B sees a significant number of formal study breaks. However, the vast majority of these apprentices return to complete their degree:

Maternity leave is the main reason for interruption. We very, very rarely see withdrawals and I think, again, retention tends to be good because it's keeping people in work. It's keeping people in paid employment and they know they need – some of them need to finish the degree to get that professional status. Our retention is good in comparison, I would say, to other undergraduate programmes in our area.

Conversely, apprentice attrition is an ongoing challenge in Programmes A and C, particularly in the transition from level 9 to 10. It should be noted that direct comparison with Programme B is difficult because it is three years long and does not offer the option of completing Honours. As S6 (Programme C) described, some learners exit after three years because they are satisfied with an ordinary degree:

There are some withdrawal cases. This is a challenge. And the progression from level 9 to 10 is another challenge. Mostly, like, if they complete level 9, they get a bachelor's degree, so some students are out to get the bachelor's degree. Some are going for the Honours and there are some cases where they're looking for their master's degrees, but they're very few.

This is supported by apprentice accounts, who may opt to exit after three years if an ordinary degree satisfies their goals. However, S6 went on to explain that as Programme C progresses, the academic demands of the modules increase significantly. In their view, this is a contributing factor in some early exits from the programme:

There are some tough modules but not as in the third year, which is completely technical – fully technical. So, they are getting some tough times because they have to manage the work and then also study this stuff. So, they're struggling there, some of the students. So, then some students opt to take the bachelor's degree rather than go for Honours.

S2 (Programme A) also reflected pragmatically on the profile of the average graduate apprentice as a contributing factor. They highlighted that the risk of student attrition is more challenging to mitigate when the target demographic is mature professionals, who often have more competing priorities than the typical full-time student:

We want to start with thirty-five folk at level 7 and take them all the way through to level 10. In reality, I don't think that's ever going to be the case. I just don't. There are so many external factors. [...] If your studies are becoming an issue that's affecting your work or your family life, then that's the one that will always give. And we have to accept that because we're dealing with people who have mortgages to pay, spouses, children, commitments.

Another Programme A academic reported that the majority of apprentices who opted not to progress to level 10 did so because their individual goals had been achieved, and so had insufficient motivation to undertake another demanding year of study:

Throughout each year, our fourth year cohort has been dwindling. [...] When the third years were going into fourth year, the majority of them were turning around and saying, "I've been doing this for personal reasons. I don't need it for an employer aspect. I've gained my ordinary degree and I'm happy with that. I don't need Honours, so that's me – I'm out". S4, *Programme A*

This quote was offered by S4 during their interview in June 2022. In September 2025, they provided a brief update on apprentice retention rates in the intervening years. Converting apprentices from level 9 to 10 continues to be a challenge in Programme A, with a lack of motivation to pursue Honours still the most commonly cited reason. The number of apprentices completing Honours since 2021/22 has stagnated, which represents a real-terms reduction in retention due to an increase in enrolments.

However, S4 contextualised this by explaining that a second programme was recently launched in their subject area, resulting in a number of transfers to the new pathway. This has skewed the retention data; although learners have exited Programme A, they are still enrolled in an apprenticeship within the department.

7.6.2 Learner Motivation

Staff were asked to reflect on the wide-ranging and often deeply personal factors that inspire people to enrol. In Programme A, understanding an apprentice's motivation is a core pedagogical principle:

I ask that specific question: why have you decided to apply? Why, at this particular period in your life, have you decided to apply? And the responses I receive are numerous, ranging from "I want to do it for myself, I want to gain a degree" to "my 18-year-old child is starting a university degree. In four years' time, they're going to have a degree and I want one as well". [...] The reasons are numerous and they are varied. Professional, personal, seeking a new challenge. The life experience of these students varies enormously. *S4, Programme A*

Our focus is actually about what's in it for them. So, what is the whole point? Why are they doing it? What is their reason for actually signing up to the GA programme? And when they come in at first year, that's something they don't often know the answer to. Usually, it's because they want to get promoted at work or whatever, but there's no real understanding of how they're going to achieve it through doing the studies. *S2, Programme A*

A similarly diverse demographic is seen in Programme B, whose cohort blends school leavers, career-changers and veteran practitioners who wish to stay up to date with sector developments:

There's a mixture of people that are completely new to the sector and completely new to the employer, and people [...] already in posts but they're using it for CPD, I suppose. We've also had a couple of people with more than twenty years of experience but who want to achieve a degree. [...] They want to enhance their practice, and a GA will let them do that. *S5, Programme B*

In contrast, the motivations of apprentices in Programme C are often rooted in achieving professional accreditation, and they are vocal about understanding how the programme will aid in this:

We are continually getting feedback from [the apprentices] related to their qualification – how they will get the chartership, et cetera. So, they are interested in this, yes. *S6, Programme C*

7.6.3 Employer Motivation

Employer motivations are similarly varied and have evolved as graduate apprenticeships have become more established. Staff reflected that in the early years of the scheme, marketing and recruitment efforts were entirely on the part of the university, as these programmes were unknown to employers. Now, employers increasingly approach the university and have identified (as termed by S3) "preferred suppliers" for apprenticeship provision across Scotland. A common point of discussion was the value proposition of sponsoring an employee through an apprenticeship compared to hiring externally:

The apprenticeship journey is out there and a lot of employers now are grabbing that. [...] Obviously they're seeing this working. So, they'll pay them a decent salary, they'll get them

educated and then hopefully in four years' time, they'll really get the big value back from them – if not sooner, because they'll start to lead and manage their functions. Whereas if you try to buy that in, it's harder. *S1, Programme A*

For some of them, it's a change in how they've traditionally recruited. [...] I think a number of companies are actually realising that the graduate apprenticeship is a more effective way. You know, after four years, they've got somebody who's got their degree, but they've got four years of experience in the business. They are a much more valuable asset to them than a graduate. *S3, Professional Services*

Another participant described how one of the university's industry partners now uses the scheme as a mechanism to address perceived knowledge gaps not covered by modern apprenticeships:

It varies from employer to employer. One employer very much is using it to upskill modern apprentices and I don't think they would mind me saying, it's because they're finding that the modern apprentice route is not necessarily – they are practitioners, they have a level 7 qualification at the end of it, but what they have found over recent years is that their modern apprentices, they don't feel, are adequately equipped to be in practice. *S5, Programme B*

7.6.4 Learner Outcomes

Several participants railed against traditional notions of academic achievement, highlighting a need to reframe what constitutes success. In their views, learning outcomes should be contextualised within the scope of the typical graduate apprentice profile and the unique demands of the hybrid model. *S3 (Professional Services)* expressed their disagreement with the narrow concept of success held by some external stakeholders:

We had four or five apprentices who all finished up last year. They all got to level nine, they took their degrees – great. For their sector and their employers, they don't really need Honours. It's not adding an awful lot to it. But from a funder's point of view, they're almost – I wouldn't say *failure* is the right word, but they're still classed as being an early leaver. They're not classed as being an achiever because they didn't do the full programme. But from my point of view, if you've got a guy in his mid-thirties who has come back to education with everything that's gone on with Covid and working through it with a family and all the rest of it, and who's got a degree out of it – well, sorry, but I think that's a success.

This position was reinforced by *S2 (Programme A)*, who argued that apprenticeship learning outcomes should be measured against contextual and relational goals as opposed to the traditional measures of academic achievement:

We're conscious that we support them at the right point for their career. We don't say, you must get promoted. We say, if you want to consolidate your position, if that's what it's all about, then great. Become a more effective manager, a more effective team member, whatever it may be – that's okay. As long as they're achieving the goals they're setting out.

Another traditional measure of success is the destination survey, which tracks where students go after graduating from a degree. Participants highlighted the limited value of this metric in an apprenticeship context, as the learners are already in employment. Indeed, as S2's example demonstrates, they may already be at the top of the organisational pecking order:

I'm mentoring candidates who are in jobs, and some of them are in really excellent jobs. They've got good destinations already and they're looking to further develop. *S1, Programme A*

We can't generalise. One of the level 10 students runs the company – there's nowhere for him to go. [...] Where do you go if you're at the top? *S2, Programme A*

7.7 Theme 5: Navigating External Influences

7.7.1 Marketing, Recruitment and Communication

Employer engagement was once more highlighted as an issue by participants, this time in the context of acknowledging the gravity of the programme as a full-time degree. Staff accounts described a pervasive lack of understanding around the demands of the programme or the expectations placed on them as the employer:

The cost is non-financial; it's the time element. It's the release aspect of giving your employee time for the undertaking of the degree. I don't think organisations fully appreciate that, and educational institutions need to make them aware of that. We do, but we could do more. *S4, Programme A*

This reinforces a comment from S5 (section 7.3.3), who reported encountering similar challenges each year with "a number of workplaces and managers and mentors not understanding the programme [...] and just, at times, not having a basic understanding". While it has been made clear that engagement during the apprenticeship is inconsistent, these comments suggest that clearer communication may be required from the university during the initial recruitment process. Another recruitment challenge is that national organisations with institutional partnerships across Scotland are now in a position to compare graduate apprenticeship offerings. This poses a risk of the scheme becoming subject to the same market-driven pressures described in the literature review, where employers may partner with the university they perceive as offering the best return on investment:

We're also finding that we've got organisations that, because they're located across Scotland, might have students at [different universities], so they're comparing offerings and who is having the best experience. So, it's more a case of who is giving the most to their students, what the students are coming back with, and if the students are actually able to deliver more for the organisation. *S2, Programme A*

Some of the employers will want to work with a preferred supplier – we have benefitted from that model and we have lost out on that model as well. Others are quite happy to work with multiple institutions and might leave the choice down to the individual. *S3, Professional Services*

Government intervention was also identified as an influence that must be carefully navigated. While it was established to drive economic policy, concerns were raised around the scheme being used as a vehicle to further other government agendas:

Anecdotally, there have been noises made in the past about GAs [...] focusing on a younger age group. I can understand why the Scottish Government would want to go down that road, because they've got that whole youth employment agenda and the Young Person's Guarantee and all of that, but I think that would make GAs a very, very hard sell. And, I think, grossly unfair to a lot of the apprentices that we have coming forward, and the businesses that are putting them forward. Our typical GA would not fall into that demographic. *S3 (Professional Services)*

7.7.2 Funding and Framework Constraints

Staff described several factors that both limit the scheme's scalability and present a threat to its long-term viability. *S3 (Professional Services)* explained that a commitment to apprenticeship development had been signalled at a policy level, but the university's ambitions of expansion have been hampered by a lack of concrete investment by the Scottish Government:

We have incredible frustrations that, as an institution, we're absolutely committed to GAs and we've got a vision of where we want to go, but we can't do that without the funders. And I guess that goes back, ultimately, to the Scottish Government. They seem to be committed to apprenticeships but we need to see evidence of that coming through.

S3 also had reservations about the scheme's viability if the funding model were to shift in a way that required a direct contribution from employers. However, they also acknowledged that the situation is nuanced, suggesting that this may not be an unreasonable expectation if it addresses an organisational skills gap:

Employers absolutely say all the right things about GAs but if they were having to put their hand in their pocket for it – I don't know. I don't know if the uptake would still be the same. [...] We need the employers on board. If employers are telling us that they can't recruit skills XYZ, you have to be prepared to invest in that yourself because it's meeting a need that you have.

As outlined in chapter two, skills funding has been in a state of flux for a number of years and a portion of apprenticeship funding was previously diverted into the Flexible Workforce Development Fund, which has recently been discontinued.

S5 was therefore concerned about how new changes to the funding model may impact Programme B:

At the moment, you can only access SAAS funding if it's a framework GA but I think universities would now like the SAAS funding to be opened up to other undergraduate degree programmes that provide a significant element of work-based learning. That is both an opportunity and a threat. It's a threat to the framework GAs because we know we have access to the pot at the moment and if that is then diluted... funding is finite, so if it's spread across more then I've no doubt that the smaller programmes with fewer students would be under threat.

7.7.3 Widening Participation, Diversity and Inclusion

Graduate apprenticeships are consistently positioned as a mechanism for widening access to higher education (Skills Development Scotland, 2021b). Staff participants celebrated the inclusive approach and noted the positive impact of RPL, which offers entry based on professional experience. While this undoubtedly opens doors for individuals who do not hold the typical university entry qualifications, the findings show that it can present a barrier to engaging with some programmes, particularly as academic demands increase in later years. This is highlighted by S3 (Professional Services), who described the challenges faced by some apprentices accepted through RPL:

One of the real benefits of the GA is that it's opening up degree-level education for people who, for whatever reason, didn't go down that road the first time. But then a large number of them don't have the standard entry requirements. Absolutely the benefit is that you take into account the industry experience that somebody has but, for some programmes, that doesn't necessarily translate over. [Programme D] is a great example. If you don't have the level of maths, you're not going to succeed in that programme no matter how much everybody puts into it. You're just really going to struggle.

When asked about university involvement in apprentice recruitment, staff described an employer-led model wherein the university allocates a number of places to partner organisations and, in turn, the employer nominates employees to fill the places. This is in keeping with practices described by Pullen *et al.* (2024), who highlight the negative implications of employers' tendencies to nominate individuals already identified for progression within the organisation. S2 (Programme A) was therefore asked if they felt that current recruitment practices risk perpetuating existing inequalities:

I absolutely do, and I think this is the downside to the whole scheme. So, [industry partner] is like a machine, giving us undergraduates every single year, but they're exactly that: they are white, middle-class, male. They're on a trajectory within the organisation and they've been identified as people that they want developed. That's unfair, but that's the reality. [...] Their face fits. If we were to look at our hundred-plus students, I don't think we'd actually say that we've got much diversity at all in terms of access.

This unequivocal response highlights a critical disconnect between two of the scheme's fundamental aims: widening access and narrowing skills gaps. Employer-led recruitment ensures that the scheme meets organisational needs, but it may undermine accessibility efforts by favouring individuals in more privileged positions. S1 (Programme A) approached this issue from an employer's perspective, framing nomination as a reward for those who have previously delivered value for the organisation:

The bottom line is they want to develop their staff, but it's a two-way thing. It's maybe staff who are showing potential or have already shown potential. [...] They want to make them feel important and an accepted part of the business by giving them opportunities to develop. [...] Then you get the loyalty, you know.

Staff accounts demonstrate that the scheme can positively contribute to equity goals through targeted recruitment. S5 (Programme B) offers an example of an employer recruitment drive which contributed significantly to increasing racial diversity in the programme:

Another colleague worked with that particular Local Authority one year to increase their recruitment of Black and minority ethnic practitioners. [...] They are in an area where there are a lot of Black and minority ethnic families, so that helped them to meet the needs of those [clients] better.

However, this was a singular event to address a need that had presented itself to the employer rather than a sustained effort to achieve racial equity. Moreover, this issue is not limited to Programme B. Although graduate apprenticeships have significantly increased access to the case study university through the RPL process, they demonstrate little diversity in other areas:

Have we got any students that are Black? I can't think of anyone. That in itself is a bit of a quandary. [...] Certainly in terms of male to female, I think we've got good diversity. That's good. That's solid. But other things? Disabilities? We've got a few people with learning disabilities. A lot of people who have dyslexia, et cetera, but people with significant disabilities? I don't think so. S2, Programme A

The same participant pointed to a lack of diversity within partner organisations as the root cause of the issue, suggesting that a re-evaluation of employer recruitment may be necessary to address it:

Our course is open to anybody. Of course it is. But who is being presented? Is it really diverse? No, it's not, and I think it's coming from the companies. [...] It might be one of those things that, regardless of the intention of the course, you're just not going to get [diversity] because it doesn't exist. Maybe it's about how we go and recruit the actual companies themselves.

7.7.4 Language and Perceptions

Due to persistent stigma and misperceptions attached to the word *apprenticeship* (Straw *et al.*, 2022; Withers, 2023), staff were asked to describe their experiences of attitudes toward the scheme. Despite efforts to modernise the apprenticeship model, it was acknowledged that outdated attitudes and stereotypes are a hangover that continues to impact public opinion:

I think you're absolutely right that there's still that perception, you know, that it's for people who can't get into university or college, it's for boys, it's for young people, it's for school leavers, and none of those things are true in any apprenticeship space now. *S3, Professional Services*

S1 (Programme A) agreed that the scheme's name poses an issue, describing how the word *apprentice* can cause confusion in potential recruits:

There's a language thing here that they need to re-look at. People go, "oh, we know what that is" but, in actual fact, they don't. [...] I think there is still this, sort of, misnomer out there. [...] When I first started speaking to some of the students, there were people who had been an apprentice at 16. They would say to me, "I was a wee apprentice working in the shipyards twenty years ago – what is this now?"

This is not a perspective shared by all staff participants, however. In S2's experience, apprentices are unfazed by the language attached to the scheme. Instead, they see the inherent value of a programme that empowers them to take charge of their professional development without the financial sacrifices of traditional degree study:

My experience so far would be the opposite. Without a shadow of a doubt, the majority of them go, "this is a great opportunity that I wouldn't have thought of doing, and this is the best way for me to do it". None of them would have left their job to go to university. *S2, Programme A*

Chapter three questions whether the concentration of graduate apprenticeships in newer institutions may compound negative perceptions of their legitimacy. The findings suggest this may be true in some cases, as S3 (Professional Services) confirmed that employer partners have elected to leave the case study university in favour of more prestigious institutions:

We have lost some employers where they have maybe opted to go with another institution. [...] The company took a strategic decision to go to [the University of] Glasgow, and you can't argue with that. No reflection on us.

7.8 Summary of Findings: Part B

Theme 1: Mentorship is framed as central to apprenticeship provision but staff accounts indicate that support is uneven, particularly within the workplace, where levels of engagement vary significantly. In addition, employers do not always honour their obligation to facilitate apprentices' participation in programme activities, though this seems to stem from a misunderstanding of the academic demands rather than deliberate obstruction. A desire to strengthen university-industry relations is also evident in staff reflections, though there are a number of institutional constraints that make this challenging. Moreover, employers are not always receptive to such efforts. This results in apprentices navigating work-based learning with variable levels of workplace support, and the university has limited scope to intervene.

Theme 2: Across the programmes, participants describe efforts to balance academic rigour with a responsiveness to stakeholder needs. Their ambitions for programme development indicate a shared commitment to the learning experience, with particular emphasis on expanding the university's suite of apprenticeship offerings, enhancements to the learning environment, and strengthening support networks. A number of academics at the case study university initially expressed some reluctance to be involved in apprenticeship delivery due to a belief that learners would not be of the same calibre as full-time students, though successful programme outcomes are attributed to a shift in attitude in the intervening years.

Theme 3: Work-based learning is a central tenet of graduate apprenticeships and this was reflected in the views of staff participants. However, their accounts highlight tensions in its delivery, particularly a misalignment between traditional methods of assessment and the scheme's emphasis on professional practice. Recognising the organisational impact often delivered through integrated projects, some participants advocate for greater emphasis on practical outputs. They call into question the relevance of summative assessment in apprenticeships, particularly for those in vocational settings.

Theme 4: Apprentice retention was flagged as an area of concern, particularly in terms of converting learners from level 9 to 10. Participant accounts suggested that the decision not to complete Honours is often tied to an apprentice's motivation for enrolling in the programme, the reasons for which are deeply personal and wide-ranging. Employer motivations are similarly varied, and the factors driving organisations to participate have evolved as the scheme has grown more established. Staff challenged the narrow definition of success held by many external stakeholders, arguing that, in the context of the typical apprentice profile, exiting the programme with an ordinary degree should be viewed as a

valid outcome rather than non-completion. Overall, there is a view that learner-led, contextualised apprenticeship outcomes may offer more value than traditional academic metrics.

Theme 5: Staff described a pervasive lack of understanding on the part of some employers around the demands of an apprenticeship and highlighted a need for clearer communication from the university. Clarity was also called for around the language attached to the scheme, as potential recruits continue to have misgivings due to outdated perceptions of apprenticeships. Staff therefore suggested that the language be updated to better reflect the scheme's purpose. As programmes have established a track record of successful outcomes, they have begun to face similar pressures seen in other areas of the sector, with employers comparing the value proposition of different offerings and adopting "preferred suppliers". There is also wariness of political agendas that threaten to make the scheme less attractive to employers, jeopardising its longevity. In terms of widening access, staff appreciated the benefits of RPL but acknowledged limited institutional efforts to increase diversity more broadly. Employer-led recruitment practices compound this by frequently favouring more privileged individuals.

7.9 Concluding the Findings

The apprentice and staff accounts presented in chapters six and seven form the empirical foundation of this study. Next, chapter eight synthesises the findings into a critical discussion, aligning the key themes to the five subsidiary research questions at the centre of this study. The focus then turns to answering the principal question of how learners define the value of apprenticeships.

Chapter 8: Discussion

8.1 Introduction

The principal aim of this research project was to establish how learners define the value of graduate apprenticeships. Due to their positioning in higher education, these programmes occupy a unique space between academic and vocational, which has raised questions around legitimacy and esteem. Additionally, employers operate as internal stakeholders, introducing a distinct power dynamic that threatens to overshadow the development needs of the apprentice. By exploring the value of these programmes from the learner perspective, this study contributes to a growing area of scholarship in which the apprentice voice is underexplored. Before approaching the central research question, the study first had to define value in the context of graduate apprenticeships, which is understood as the perceived worth, utility and legitimacy of a programme. The literature review then highlighted that an apprenticeship's value is relative to how it serves the priorities of each stakeholder. In order to address this question in a way that reflects these complexities, five subsidiary questions were explored:

- How do stakeholder dynamics shape programme design and delivery?
- How do apprentices navigate competing stakeholder expectations?
- How do programmes emphasise experiential learning?
- How do apprentices reconcile learning and practice?
- How do apprentices articulate programme value in relation to their goals?

Critical interrogation of these additional questions was necessary to obtain a panoramic overview of how apprenticeships at the university are delivered and experienced. Each question considered how internal and external factors shape programme design and, ultimately, how these decisions impact the value derived by apprentices. Having examined staff and learner accounts separately in chapters six and seven, this discussion weaves them together in an overarching interpretation of the findings. The themes that scaffolded the findings are also revisited and aligned to the five questions above.

Overlapping Themes	Learner Themes	Staff Themes
Mentorship, Support and Engagement	Learner Motivation	Retention and Progression
Personalisation of Learning and Teaching	Apprenticeship Value	Navigating External Influences
The Role of Experiential Learning	–	–

Table 8.1: Key themes by participant group

The subsidiary questions and themes each intersect numerous times, mirroring the multi-dimensional nature of graduate apprenticeships. This discussion examines these intersections to establish how sectoral tensions, stakeholder dynamics and curriculum design converge into value.

8.2 Introducing the Tripartite Value Model

The findings highlight that value is not a singular outcome in apprenticeships, nor can it be delivered unilaterally by any one party. Instead, it is a relational construct negotiated across the tripartite structure. As the significance of these relationships emerged from the data, it became necessary to conceptualise a means of capturing the complexities of how value is defined and experienced. This section therefore introduces the Tripartite Value Model, an emergent conceptual framework. At this stage, the model presented in Figure 8.1 is in its preliminary form, outlining the central relationships that influence the apprentice experience but not yet articulating the conditions required to maximise value. This initial concept serves as an interpretive scaffold, offering a visual representation of the interplay between stakeholder expectations in shaping value.

Figure 8.1: The Tripartite Value Model (Emergent)

The decision to present the model in its unfinished form reflects the abductive logic underpinning this study; it emerged through iterative engagement with the findings, and its refinement continues as the discussion unfolds. The model is revisited in the next chapter, where it is expanded and grounded in pedagogical literature. The final iteration synthesises the empirical findings with educational theory, offering a holistic approach to embedding value in apprenticeship design.

8.3 How do stakeholder dynamics shape programme design and delivery?

Stakeholder dynamics were identified as playing a vital role in shaping graduate apprenticeships. Key elements highlighted include mentorship and support, employer engagement, institutional priorities and cultural perceptions of work-based learning. These factors converge to influence not only the structure and curriculum of each programme but also the learning experience of apprentices. This section considers the interplay between these dynamics and how it dictates the value experienced by apprentices.

Intersecting themes:

- Mentorship, Support and Engagement
- Navigating External Influences

8.3.1 Mentorship, Support and Engagement

Employer engagement was widely identified as an issue by staff, who described inconsistent levels of support and challenges around communication with workplace mentors, who often cite workload and time constraints as the cause. This was supported by learner accounts, which described the challenge of scheduling meaningful time with their mentor due to demanding workloads. The individual in this role is typically the apprentice's line manager and, as such, works closely with them, albeit in a senior position. However, when an apprentice perceives the mentor's workload as a barrier to engagement, they seek to avoid placing further demands on their time as they do not wish to be viewed as a burden. There is also a trend of workplace mentorship dwindling as the programme progresses, which staff participants attributed to successful learner outputs signalling that mentor input is no longer required. However, educational value is maximised with regular tripartite engagement to ensure the learning journey remains aligned with all stakeholder priorities (Garnett and Reynier, 2025).

Although the majority of apprentices are satisfied with the support received in the workplace, a small number reported that their mentor appeared unclear on the learner's job role or the support expected from them, which is an issue commonly raised in the literature. While Quew-Jones and Rowe (2022) attribute this to a lack of central training and resources, the findings suggest it may not be a systemic issue. Staff accounts highlight that mentors are often reluctant to engage with training sessions delivered by the university, even when asynchronous, which indicates that relevant information and resources do exist, but they are simply not reaching the intended audience. This underscores a key

recommendation by the International Labour Organization (2020), who argue that pedagogic training should be a mandatory condition of an organisation's involvement with apprenticeships.

With regard to academic mentorship, approaches differ between programmes and a correlation was identified between mentor engagement and cohort size. While S5 described how resource constraints create barriers to Programme B mentors formally engaging beyond the assessment visits mandated by the framework, the small class sizes offer greater access to academic mentors, who are happy to offer informal support and guidance when needed. On the other hand, the findings indicate that gaps in mentorship are more likely to appear in larger programmes, particularly when their delivery is closely aligned with full-time provision. This is evident in Programmes C and D – the only programmes wherein apprentices reported having no contact with an academic mentor. In the case of Programme C, S6 recognised a historic lack of oversight in this area and described the introduction of processes that specify minimum levels of mentor engagement and better facilitate tripartite communication.

The findings indicate that this trend of mentorship gaps in larger programmes can also be mitigated through commitment to relational pedagogy. Programme A leadership identified a similar pattern in the early days of its delivery and took proactive steps to offer learners a dedicated mentor for the duration of their studies. These tutors are experienced in learner development and have proactively adopted a facilitative role, deferring to the apprentices as subject experts in their professional practice. Additionally, the relationship is scaffolded by a pedagogical approach that emphasises development and value for the learner. Programme A staff participants emphasised the importance of personal development planning and ensuring that learners not only identify goals but also reflect on how the programme will contribute to achieving them. This approach reflects Fielding's (2001) notion of radical collegiality, a concept explored further in section 9.2.3. Programme A mentors emphasise the relationship as professional and developmental, signalling the positionality of apprentices as partners in knowledge construction. Moreover, despite its large cohort size, learners are happy with the academic support they have received in the programme. Not only does this demonstrate the benefits of a relational and collaborative approach in apprenticeship delivery, but it also underscores the need for this to be embedded intentionally.

8.3.2 Perceptions of Apprenticeships

In a 2015 study, Basit *et al.* described a reluctance amongst some academic staff to deliver work-based learning due to concerns that it would diminish their role from academic to trainer. These views are also consistent with deep-rooted perceptions of vocational programmes across wider British culture.

However, the authors' observations must also be contextualised; the study was published two years before the formal launch of graduate apprenticeships and there is a faint suggestion that the scheme may be the first step toward changing these entrenched attitudes. Although participants in teaching roles have not experienced overt negativity toward apprenticeships, the findings demonstrate that there was reluctance from some academics, largely for the reasons highlighted by Basit *et al.* However, in the intervening years, there has been a shift in attitude as apprentices' academic contributions have challenged previous misconceptions of them as less able than their full-time counterparts.

Chapter two argued that achieving parity of esteem between academic and vocational degrees would require a culture shift within academia itself and these findings imply that the first steps may have been taken toward unsettling the academic-vocational dichotomy. Recent commentary (Pullen, 2024) has also observed that apprenticeships are drawing attention from more privileged groups, including private school pupils and their parents. Yet Scotland's ancient universities – typically the destination for school leavers from affluent backgrounds (Reay, 2021) – have largely disengaged from graduate apprenticeships, leaving their delivery concentrated in newer institutions. This juxtaposition reveals an irony that the thesis terms a *paradox of esteem*; such interest in post-92 institutions from privileged groups has the potential to strengthen the scheme's cultural legitimacy within the symbolic economy.

8.4 How do apprentices navigate competing stakeholder expectations?

There is an expectation that the tripartite structure will balance the needs of learners, employers and universities. The findings reveal tensions around how this is executed in practice, with implications for programme delivery, learner agency and equitable recruitment. This section explores these competing demands and how they shape learners' experiences and concept of value.

Intersecting themes:

- Personalisation of Learning and Teaching
- Mentorship, Support and Engagement
- The Role of Experiential Learning
- Apprenticeship Value
- Navigating External Influences

8.4.1 Programme Delivery

Programme A is delivered online, with face-to-face contact days offered each term. This was not in response to the pandemic, which was a catalyst for many courses shifting to an online delivery model;

the programme has been delivered this way since its launch in 2018. While a minority of learners appreciate the additional flexibility, many expressed a desire for more time on campus to enforce a separation of work, study and home. Indeed, the main beneficiary of online delivery is the employer, as there is less operational impact than a traditional day-release model. Lester and Bravenboer (2020) also warn that online delivery can lead to an erosion of protected study time, which is evident in this case. Despite being mandated by the framework, some employers display reticence around honouring the weekly study time, instead expecting that apprentices will engage with academic activities in their own time. Furthermore, some insist that on-campus days are taken out of apprentices' annual leave allowances. Although faculty members challenge these practices directly, this relies on the apprentice making the issue known to the university. Due to the inherent power structure in the workplace, some instances may fly under their radar due to a learner's reluctance to speak out against their employer. Not only do such practices undermine the tripartite agreement, but they also cause a disaggregation of the learning journey by limiting contextual application, underscoring the need for robust tripartite communication.

Programme B follows a tapered structure, shifting from face-to-face to online delivery with each year of the programme. Although institutional pressure around resource efficiency was a factor in adopting this hybrid model, learners appreciated the balanced approach, noting that it promotes self-direction by mirroring their increasing independence as learners. They also highlight the programme's VLE as a pedagogical space rather than simply a resource repository, which implies an intentional use of digital pedagogy to support the extension of learning beyond the classroom. The contrasting feedback from Programme A apprentices reiterates the importance of this intentionality in online delivery to ensure that learners feel supported (Serdyukov, 2015).

Programmes C and D adopt the traditional day-release model, with apprentices attending on-campus lectures alongside their full-time counterparts. Despite challenges presented by module content and assessment (discussed in section 8.5), learners expressed high levels of satisfaction with this approach and emphasised the benefits of weekly attendance. Though rather than praising the didactic teaching format, the comments highlight the value apprentices derive from frequent opportunities to engage with lecturers face-to-face. This supports Balloo, Pauli and Worrell's (2017) observation that mature students often attach greater importance to regular dialogue and prompt feedback.

These findings highlight that, in the eyes of the apprentice, programme value is not necessarily linked to the pedagogical ideal. In this case, learners value the (arguably outdated) lecture format because it

affords them greater access to their teachers. The implication of this is clear: to maximise the value of apprenticeships for learners, they must enforce a separation of work, study and home by embedding a relational space that encourages frequent dialogue, feedback and expression of ideas.

8.4.2 Learner Agency vs Structural Constraints

Chapter four argued that apprenticeship pedagogy should accommodate the realities of work-based learning, which are often complex and dictated by organisational needs. Although structural changes have been implemented in apprenticeships at the case study university, these largely reflect the needs of employers, whereas adjustments to delivery tend to be more superficial. They are also reactive, applied in response to learner requests rather than proactively seeking to accommodate their needs. This dynamic raises bigger questions around the legitimacy of learners' agency within apprenticeships.

Co-creation is implied in policy rhetoric but often absent in practice. Drawing again on Marx's notion of commodity fetishism, it can be argued that placing such conditions on agency risks its fetishisation; the learner is outwardly presented as the driver of their development (Skills Development Scotland, 2018) but, in reality, the ability to achieve their goals is often constrained by institutional and employer priorities. In this context, agency can be supported by inviting dialogue about how best to integrate learning into their individual contexts. For example, one apprentice described how the order of the modules was misaligned with tasks in their workplace, which limited their ability to apply learning in real time. Such challenges could be mitigated through co-creation that allows apprentices to align the curriculum focus with their needs, taking the first step toward reframing teaching as collaborative rather than imposed (Bovill, 2020a). This would have little impact on the educator's workload while validating learner agency and reinforcing their equal status within the tripartite relationship.

8.4.3 Access and Equity

Chapter three examined the recommendations of the Commissioner for Fair Access, who argued that a truly fair widening access policy must look beyond university admission (McKendrick, 2024, p. 23). Yet, despite apprenticeships being framed as a vehicle for widening access in policy discourse, the findings suggest that employer-led recruitment practices present an additional barrier at the point of entry. Staff confirmed that employers often nominate high-performing individuals, many of whom are on an upward trajectory within the organisation – a practice that Pullen *et al.* (2024) caution may potentially reinforce existing inequalities. While university-led recruitment strategies have proven to be unsuitable for work-based learning programmes in the past (Fuller and Unwin, 2011), employer-led practices present their own drawbacks and may compound advantage rather than open doors for

marginalised groups. This dynamic can be examined through the conceptual lens of Bourdieu's cultural reproduction, which posits that educational opportunities reinforce the existing distribution of capital. Employer-led recruitment favours individuals already in possession of the social and cultural capital valued by their employer, thereby reproducing advantage rather than widening access. Furthermore, Raffe and Croxford (2015) argue that the UK's institutional hierarchy perpetuates social reproduction by limiting access to opportunity. This demonstrates how graduate apprenticeships risk reproducing inequalities two-fold: once at the point of entry, where employers nominate individuals positioned for success, and again on a structural level, where the legitimacy and esteem of the programme is dictated by the institutional hierarchy.

As noted by staff participants, the individuals put forward by employers may simply be reflective of the wider employee demographic. If this is the case, greater diversity cannot be achieved if it doesn't exist within the local industry. This then raises the question of recruitment and whether universities should take more proactive steps to target organisations where apprenticeships may genuinely widen access. Without intervention, the scheme risks reinforcing the stratification of opportunity. Indeed, staff expressed concern for the long-term implications of this practice, noting that equity goals could be undermined if apprenticeships are used as a means of progressing high-performing employees. The Commissioner for Fair Access recently proposed a holistic, longitudinal measure of fair access to higher education. Borrowing from his logic, it is argued that safeguarding equity in apprenticeships requires a reframing of widening access that broadens the focus from parity of entry to parity of experience.

8.5 How do programmes emphasise experiential learning?

Apprentices were asked for their views on learning and teaching in their respective programmes. From their accounts, experiential learning emerged as a central theme. While work-based learning modules are present across all four programmes, the degree to which learners perceive them as opportunities for transformative learning varies. This section examines the factors that influence this, including how experiential learning is embedded and assessed, and the implications of these choices for practice.

Intersecting themes:

- The Role of Experiential Learning
- Mentorship, Support and Engagement
- Personalisation of Learning and Teaching

8.5.1 Embedding Practice in Practice

All of the programmes observed in this study deliver work-based learning modules, but the difference lies in the support structures that enable apprentices to translate theory into practice. As chapter four argued, experience alone does not lead to transformative learning. Similarly, it is not enough to offer opportunities for work-based learning; it must be intentionally underpinned by wraparound support and pedagogy that can act as a bridge between "doing" and "learning". This underscores the need for ongoing communication between academic and workplace mentors to adequately support learners in applying their new knowledge. However, workplace mentor engagement is inconsistent across all four programmes and university staff are limited in how they can enforce it. Although workplace mentors acknowledge their part in the learning journey by signing the tripartite agreement, this is not a legally binding document. Moreover, academics' demanding schedules prohibit active pursuit of disengaged mentors unless there is a significant issue that must be addressed. Nonetheless, inadequate workplace support has negative consequences for the learner (Chadwick, Dimungu Hewage and Hazzam, 2025) and so steps must be taken to address this structural weakness in the apprenticeship model.

In keeping with Spencer, Parr and Clark's (2022) observations of peer support in apprenticeships, one learner described the benefits of engaging with a community of practice. Recognising their workplace mentor's limitations with regard to academic insights, a group of apprentices established a community of practice to share ideas and offer encouragement during assessment periods. This account highlights the undeniable benefits of such groups, but they are not a substitute for the structured mentorship mandated by the apprenticeship framework. Workplace mentors are best placed to offer guidance in practical and cultural aspects of the programme but may lack pedagogical expertise. The academic mentor role is therefore designed to complement this, creating wraparound support as the apprentice navigates the dual learning environment. Although informal support mechanisms may temper a mentorship shortfall, an absence of formal guidance risks a fragmented learning experience. In other words, communities of practice can aid in sustaining motivation but transformative learning relies on ongoing support that connects academic concepts with workplace application.

This also reinforces the importance of regular communication between the academic and workplace mentors to ensure that learning outcomes remain authentic rather than symbolic. Based on Fuller and Unwin's (2003) expansive-restrictive continuum, expansive apprenticeships support integration and reflection, while restrictive programmes offer learners little support in connecting theory and practice. Inadequate communication shifts apprenticeships toward the restrictive end of the scale, creating a scenario in which apprentices are awarded credentials without achieving meaningful transformation.

This illustrates how value is maximised through tripartite communication. The findings also support Spencer, Parr and Clark's (2022) recommendation to formally embed peer communities of practice within apprenticeship curricula to complement formal mentorship provision. This would provide an additional support channel that benefits all apprentices, not only those who feel comfortable seeking guidance informally from peers.

8.5.2 Assessing Experiential Learning

The authenticity of experiential learning is also shaped by how it is assessed. Assessment approaches vary across programmes, with the chosen methods presenting a continuum of self-directed learning. At one end is the longitudinal portfolio approach championed by Spencer, Parr and Clark (2022) and Dean *et al.* (2024). These allow learners to evidence their development through sustained reflection and authentic integration with practice. At the other end, prescriptive project briefs constrain agency by offering apprentices little scope to tailor projects to their own contexts. Learners are unable to negotiate projects that address a need in their workplace, leaving them feeling as though they are penalised if their organisation does not align with the assessment topic.

This approach also inhibits knowledge construction by limiting opportunities to contextualise learning. Kolb's (1984) theory of experiential learning is explicit on this point: new knowledge cannot be created through experience without intentional transformation. Limiting engagement with the final step of Kolb's cycle (active experimentation) compromises the effectiveness of experiential learning and, in turn, the programme's value. Furthermore, requiring apprentices to fit their practice to standardised learning outcomes risks delivering symbolic value rather than transformative education (Brancaleone and O'Brien, 2011).

While bespoke programmes are perceived to offer the greatest relevance to practice, learners across the programmes report satisfaction with the combination of assessment methods used. Interestingly, L9 (Programme D) noted that these are "very much the same as any other programme", which implies that standardised assessments are accepted because apprentices have been conditioned to expect them at university. The findings illustrate the practical challenges of balancing institutional priorities with authentic work-based learning; while traditional assessment methods may simplify delivery and improve resource efficiencies, they limit opportunities for apprentices to negotiate outcomes that directly enhance their practice. Programme C's assessments exemplify the broader tension between efficiency and authenticity across the higher education sector.

8.5.3 Implications for Authentic Learning

At the scheme's inception, it was presumed that universities would design graduate apprenticeships with "significant ongoing involvement and contribution from employers", extending to "curriculum development, delivery and assessment" (Skills Development Scotland, 2016b). However, the findings show that the majority of programmes observed in this study are structurally aligned with full-time provision, which indicates limited employer involvement in their design. This reinforces the findings of Smith *et al.* (2021a), who argue that the employer-led design emphasised in policy rhetoric is often absent in practice, as the framework ultimately limits employers' influence over academic content by placing control of the curriculum with the university. Spencer, Parr and Clark (2022) also caution against this design choice, suggesting that adapting full-time degree content for an apprenticeship risks the programme being viewed as a "bolt-on" to existing provision. The authors further underscore the consequences of weak collaboration in curriculum design, warning that repurposing full-time content encourages learners to prioritise degree activities over apprenticeship activities. This is not to imply a calculated attempt to exclude employers from the process; rather, it may simply be a means of streamlining the convoluted process of establishing a new apprenticeship (Jackson, 2025).

The findings suggest that while universities benefit from increased resource efficiency and assessment clarity, the framework element of the model means apprentices and employers experience constraints in both agency and value. For learners, generic modules and assessments feel disconnected from their practice, which limits opportunities for transformation. For employers, apprenticeships may deliver symbolic credentials but not necessarily organisational enhancement. Programme B's bespoke design exemplifies how collaboration can enhance authenticity for practitioners, whereas Programme C illustrates the challenges that can emerge when programme design more closely resembles traditional degree structures. This feeds into the paradox of esteem and reinforces Withers' (2023) assessment of graduate apprenticeships as having "a misleading name, but a huge potential"; rhetorically, these programmes are industry-responsive and vocationally authentic but, structurally, they often mirror academic degrees. Yet, due to their association with the word *apprenticeship*, they remain culturally undervalued.

8.6 How do apprentices reconcile learning and practice?

The findings suggest that reconciling formal learning with professional practice can pose a challenge. Although some learners report a strong alignment of curriculum content and practice, others describe struggling to translate theory into their workplace contexts. This section examines how programmes bridge theory and practice, the extent to which professional experience prepares apprentices for their studies, and the tangible impact of work-based learning.

Intersecting themes:

- Mentorship, Support and Engagement
- The Role of Experiential Learning
- Apprenticeship Value
- Navigating External Influences
- Retention and Progression

8.6.1 Tensions Between Learning and Experience

Relevance to practice plays a central role in not only delivering educational value but also sustaining motivation to learn (Knowles, Holton and Swanson, 2005; Dziallas *et al.*, 2021; White, 2023; Garnett and Reynier, 2025). In Programme B's case, apprentices unanimously considered the content highly relevant to their daily practice. Though encouraging, this is unsurprising for two reasons: firstly, the curriculum is bespoke, designed as part of a pilot scheme to address a specific skills shortfall. Secondly, Programme B apprentices are employed in different settings but operate within a single, regulated industry and so their day-to-day practice is similar. This narrower focus streamlines the curriculum design process and allows for more targeted content. In comparison, apprentices in the other three programmes are situated across a wide range of roles and organisations, which presents a greater challenge in terms of ensuring content relevance. This was reflected in participants' accounts. Where the content is based on materials from the full-time degree, relevance to practice can be limited. Additionally, there were suggestions that the content could be more tailored to the needs of apprentices: "At times it feels like the content is designed for the full-time on-campus students and forced to fit the GA cohort" (L7, Programme A).

This tension is particularly prominent in Programmes C and D, wherein the curriculum *is* the full-time degree. In addition to the standalone work-based learning modules, apprentices attend the full-time cohort's classes once a week. As such, 80% of participants in the programmes report that the content is not relevant to their practice, and many describe limited tailoring to the apprenticeship cohort. The

most commonly cited issue is the broad curricular focus, which is designed to give aspiring graduates a comprehensive foundation for a career: "We are already working in industry, compared to standard students who are in the degree to get into the industry" (L19, Programme C). This misalignment of curriculum content and apprentice needs presents another risk of offering symbolic value rather than transformative learning due to a lack of authentic integration with practice.

This is further complicated by differences in length of service, with apprentices less established in their roles facing additional challenges. Although the vast majority of apprentices are existing employees looking to upskill, a few enrol as new recruits and the findings highlight how this presents a barrier to meaningful engagement. Newly employed apprentices reported that a lack of experience in their role left them struggling with the self-directed work-based learning elements of the programme. Based on Fuller and Unwin's (2003, 2004) argument that an expansive apprenticeship should guide a learner from peripheral to mainstream participation in the workplace, a relational, spiral-shaped approach to integrated work-based projects would more effectively accommodate differing levels of experience, with tasks growing in complexity as apprentices develop.

This pattern of increasing complexity is present in other modules across apprenticeship curricula. With academic mentorship only offered in the work-based learning module, the jump in academic demands without additional support can deter some apprentices from completing Honours. This is a common concern for those accepted through RPL, who may lack the foundational disciplinary knowledge of their peers, leading to struggles with more technical aspects of a programme. This also contributes to the high rates of early exit from apprenticeships, as highlighted by S6 in chapter seven. L19 similarly reported seeing peers leave Programme C for this reason: "The workplace doesn't prep you for the math-heavy side of things and I've seen people drop out and finish after year three since they couldn't handle the math anymore". RPL is framed as a widening access mechanism, yet these findings show how equity can be undermined when practical experience does not adequately prepare learners for the academic demands of a degree. This reveals a tension between workplace experience and formal learning, highlighting the importance of reconciling them.

These findings illustrate how finely balanced experience and learning are. For example, the amount of situated experience can dictate an apprentice's continued motivation to engage with the programme. These accounts underscore an argument presented in chapter four: experience does not automatically equate to transformative learning. Without an appropriate pedagogical underpinning, learners may struggle to meet the demands of degree study. At the same time, apprentices emphasise that when

the content reflects their practice, their integration becomes a source of increased confidence and respect within the workplace. It seems that the tension is not the value of professional experience but how programmes support learners in translating it into the academic sphere. This presents a tipping point: apprenticeships must either lean into their transformative potential or risk their value becoming symbolic.

8.6.2 Bridging Theory and Practice

A number of apprentices highlight the relevance of curriculum content as an issue, which presents a barrier to engaging with work-based learning projects due to a misalignment with their practice. This is especially pronounced in programmes whose content mirrors the equivalent full-time degree, which leads to apprentices feeling they must fit their practice to the programme rather than the programme being tailored to their practice. Rather than stemming from a single root cause, this disconnect is likely to be a combination of issues. Firstly, due to the limited apprenticeship options and the slow rate of framework expansion, some learners may be enrolled in programmes that are peripherally relevant but outside their scope of practice. Institutional emphasis on efficiency also shapes decisions in terms of curriculum design and delivery method. If this is compounded by a lack of consultation with industry partners, existing resources may be repurposed and a programme designed that is too broad to meet specific employer needs (Lester and Bravenboer, 2020). The issue may also lie with a learner's support network rather than the content itself. If they are not adequately supported through the Kolbian steps of experiential learning, they may be unable to translate theory into practice, leading to a perceived absence of relevance. On the surface, learner accounts imply a systemic issue with content relevance. However, this can be unpacked to reveal several distinct factors that may be experienced separately, some of which universities can do little to mitigate. Nonetheless, they accumulate and contribute to a broader perception among apprentices that the content lacks relevance, even if each learner only encounters one issue in isolation.

This is particularly pronounced when comparing highly tailored programmes with those more closely resembling full-time provision. Indeed, several participants described shaping their practice around content they felt had not been designed with apprentices in mind. In contrast, Programme B learners described how the bespoke content informs and improves their practice in tangible ways that mean they feel "ten steps ahead" of colleagues in their settings.

8.6.3 Tangible Impact of Graduate Apprenticeships

The findings also highlight the organisational impact of graduate apprenticeships, particularly through integrated work-based projects, and Garnett's (2005) notion of project capital provides a useful lens for understanding the broader value they generate. Garnett argues that effective work-based learning programmes generate project capital by facilitating projects that re-energise existing resources to enhance an organisation's structural, human, customer and intellectual capital. On this basis, the findings show work-based projects to be a source of significant project capital, which staff attribute to the fresh perspectives apprentices bring when approaching a problem. Their accounts also illustrate the measurable impact delivered for organisations, including a striking example of an industry partner investing £1 million into site infrastructure in response to an apprentice's proposal. In the same way that successful outcomes have positively influenced academic attitudes toward apprenticeships, this record of delivering organisational impact has prompted a similar shift in employer perceptions. Staff participants report that employers increasingly recognise the tangible benefits offered by the scheme, which is reflected in changes to their recruitment practices: "Obviously they're seeing this working. So, they'll pay them a decent salary, they'll get them educated and then hopefully in four years' time they'll really get the big value back from them" (S1, Programme A). Accumulating positive outcomes also evidences professional development, allowing apprentices to establish a reputation as reliable and capable employees.

The concept of project capital captures not only the value offered by graduate apprenticeships to each stakeholder but also the symbiotic relationship between them. The workplace provides an authentic learning environment for the apprentice's development which, in turn, enhances areas of the business beyond their immediate role. However, a correlation is noted between project capital and project self-direction. Recently, Garnett argued that universities must be flexible in their delivery and assessment of apprenticeships to "facilitate alignment with real-world work priorities and patterns" (Garnett and Reynier, 2025). As the findings highlight, prescriptive project briefs limit the extent to which learners can problematise within their workplaces and this, in turn, constrains the amount of project capital generated.

Meta-skills emerged as another key area of impact. Embedded throughout Programme B's curriculum, they were identified as significantly enhancing learners' capacity for communication and reflection. Although the benefits may not be immediately apparent, S5 explained that apprentices often see their value retrospectively when required to reflect on their practice, such as during job interviews: "It gives them that tool, if you like, to be able to talk about it. Which, again, I think is really useful because I

don't know that degrees on their own necessarily do that". By embedding meta-skills in learning and teaching, apprenticeships look beyond technical competence, cultivating the ability to reflect on and articulate their development – a skill that is increasingly sought after in the labour market (Brown and Souto-Otero, 2020). This is then reinforced through the use of individual reflections and longitudinal portfolios in assessment, which require apprentices to document, reflect on and articulate the impact of their learning across each year of the programme.

The findings suggest that the integration of meta-skills and reflective practice adds a distinctive layer of value to apprenticeships. When structured reflective practices are emphasised, learners develop both the confidence and language necessary to articulate their development. Although meta-skills have not been retrospectively added to frameworks published prior to 2019 (Skills Development Scotland, 2020), the findings indicate that embedding these reflective practices across apprenticeship provision may offer an additional dimension of value.

8.7 How do apprentices articulate programme value in relation to their goals?

The findings indicate that apprentices ultimately define a programme's value by how it contributes to achieving their goals, which include career progression, enhanced employability and satisfying a sense of personal achievement. To answer the final subsidiary research question, this section considers how apprenticeship design supports or constrains these goals and how success is defined in this context.

Intersecting themes:

- Retention and Progression
- Learner Motivation
- Personalisation of Learning and Teaching
- Apprenticeship Value

8.7.1 Reimagining Academic Success

Apprentice retention is highlighted in the literature as a persistent issue (Rowe *et al.*, 2017; White, 2023; Skills Development Scotland, 2025), a phenomenon that extends to the case study university. Although staff participants are understanding of the distinct pressures faced by apprentices, there is evidently a desire to improve retention rates. However, this may not be an issue of attrition so much as an issue of perspective.

Chapter three proposed reform of how the success of an apprenticeship programme is measured, arguing for a shift in focus away from labour market outcomes and apprentice completion rates. This was echoed in staff accounts, with one participant expressing disagreement with how SDS defines a successful apprenticeship outcome. Currently, only those who complete their entire programme are considered successful and individuals who exit at any point before this, even if they graduate with an ordinary degree, are characterised as early leavers.

However, there are a variety of reasons that an apprentice may choose not to pursue Honours. While full-time students and apprentices often have similar motivations for undertaking a degree (Smith *et al.*, 2018), apprentices have a very different learner profile and must navigate distinct pressures while studying. As such, many apprentices are mature learners with defined career goals, which can often be achieved with an ordinary degree. In some cases, career progression is not the objective at all, and the programme is simply viewed as a welcome opportunity to achieve a degree for personal satisfaction.

On average, 40% of graduate apprentices left a programme early between 2017/18 and 2020/21 (Skills Development Scotland, 2025). However, as Table 8.2 outlines, the majority of early leavers received a partial award. The exception to this was 2020/21 but this likely reflects the impact of the pandemic; the lockdowns that year changed many people's circumstances in ways that would present a barrier to study.

	2017/18	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21
Early Leavers (No Award)	26.7%	31.9%	40.6%	51.5%
Early Leavers (Partial Award)	73.3%	68.1%	59.4%	48.5%
Early Leavers (Total)	101	407	503	480

Table 8.2: Breakdown of early leavers (2017/18 - 2020/21)

Source: Skills Development Scotland (2025)

These figures illustrate the false dichotomy of "achiever" and "leaver" in this context; the prevalence of partial awards suggests that a significant number of apprentices achieve meaningful outcomes without completing the programme. This is also evident in how apprentices articulate the benefits to their practice. In line with Garnett and Reynier's (2025) observations, increased workplace confidence is the most common outcome for apprentices in higher education. Participants expressed this in a number of ways, from carrying out technical tasks and volunteering to take on more responsibility to feeling more self-assured as a leader. In addition, career progression is incredibly common while still

enrolled, with one academic noting that all of their mentees had received promotion either before or during their final year. This dovetails into another measure of success typically used in universities: the destination survey. While entirely appropriate to track the progress of traditional students post-graduation, this is less useful in the case of graduate apprenticeships as the learners are all in full-time employment: "Some of them are in really excellent jobs. They've got good destinations already" (S1, Programme A).

Chapter three discussed recommendations from the Commissioner for Fair Access, who called for a holistic measure of widening participation initiatives. Borrowing from his observation, this thesis then advocated for a similar metric that looked beyond enrolment to the apprenticeship experience as a whole. Extending this to the point of exit underscores the need for a more relational view of academic success in an apprenticeship context. When examined through the lens of intersectionality, it becomes clear that current attitudes toward retention are misaligned with both the apprenticeship model and the learner demographic it serves. Participation is often shaped by the competing pressures of full-time employment, individual life stage, personal commitments and career trajectories – conditions that make progression to Honours unnecessary and unrealistic for many. As participant S2 explained: "If your studies are becoming an issue that's affecting your work or your family life, then that's the one that will always give. And we have to accept that because we're dealing with people who have mortgages to pay, spouses, children, commitments."

In short, the current measures are too narrow and fail to account for the typical learner profile, their life stage or their ambitions. This thesis therefore echoes Brown and Souto-Otero's (2020) call for re-evaluation of what constitutes merit. It also repeats Merrill's (2015) advice that institutions "listen to the voices of adult students and understand withdrawal from their perspective rather than viewing it as a failing process and an economic cost".

Recent literature has pointed to employer-identified learning outcomes as effective success markers in apprenticeships (Smith, Henderson and Mapletoft, 2023) but the findings of this study highlight the benefits of negotiated outcomes that better reflect learners' goals.

8.7.2 Motivators, Aims and Outcomes

Apprentices often expressed a desire for career progression but, in some cases, a tension is visible between their desired and probable futures. Drawing on Markus and Nurius' notion of future selves, Harrison and Waller (2018) observe that those who enter university through non-traditional routes

often experience a disconnect between their aspirations and what they consider to be achievable within their social context. This is particularly evident in L1's reflection, offered as they approached the end of their programme: "I never thought I would ever have a degree. I mean, I've been a joiner for sixteen years". This is in keeping with Dziallas *et al.* (2021), who found that a number of apprentices view the scheme as opening the door to a career previously assumed to be inaccessible. Ryan and Deci's (2000) self-determination theory also offers some insight into this phenomenon. Although apprentices demonstrate a strong intrinsic motivation to meet their goals, longstanding cultural narratives still reinforce an educational hierarchy and emphasise vocational learners as being less suited to academic pathways.

Interestingly, this comment implies an internalisation of the vocational-academic dichotomy. Despite feeling strongly that the scheme's value is in no way diminished by its association with the word *apprenticeship*, it appears that the misalignment between L1's desired and probable futures stemmed from a belief that academic credentials were inaccessible due to their occupational identity. In terms of motivation, L1 entered the programme intending to complete three years and achieve an ordinary degree with a view to promotion. As demonstrated in section 8.7.1, this is not formally recognised as a successful apprenticeship outcome. Despite this, L1 was promoted to a leadership position during the programme and, crucially, achieved their goal of completing an ordinary degree, thereby aligning their desired and probable futures.

Like L1, participant L9 cites career progression as their motivation for undertaking an apprenticeship, emphasising the scheme's value proposition in terms of enhancing employability: "By the end of my qualification I will already be approximately 5 years ahead of my peers that graduate through a full-time programme in terms of industry experience". Unlike L1, however, L9 previously opted for the traditional academic route but left full-time study due to financial pressures and limited employment prospects. Rather than facing social or cultural constraints, L9's route to academic credentials was hindered by practical barriers, both of which are resolved by the *earn while you learn* apprenticeship model. Viewed side by side, these reflections demonstrate the relationality between motivation and perceived value, as well as how value is experienced individually through the overcoming of barriers separating desired and probable futures.

This also reveals a paradox between how learners experience value in apprenticeships and the cultural narratives that shape how that value is perceived. Drawing on Giddens' (1984) theory of structuration, it can be argued that graduate apprenticeships are bound by a duality of structuration. On one hand,

they challenge cultural hierarchies by pushing the boundaries of what learners perceive to be possible within their individual context. On the other, their positioning and esteem remain constrained by the narratives through which the hierarchies are reproduced. The interplay between internal (agency) and external (constraint) shapes undergraduate provision across the sector, but it risks undermining the scheme's transformative potential unless apprentices' goals and circumstances are acknowledged as integral to how value is defined and experienced.

8.7.3 The Value Proposition of Apprenticeship Learning

When asked what motivated them to apply for an apprenticeship, the vast majority of participants expressed a desire to enhance their employability. Furthermore, the responses suggest that they understand the scheme as offering a distinct form of value in this regard, particularly when compared to traditional degrees. Although the symbolic recognition of credentials remains important to those seeking promotion within industries that demand a degree, many participants emphasised how the integration of study and on-the-job experience provides a competitive edge over traditional graduates in the employment market. This suggests an awareness of the effects of credentialism, prompting apprentices to pursue a qualification that demonstrates their competence and workplace readiness. Notably, more than a third of participants held either an undergraduate or postgraduate degree prior to enrolment and have chosen to complete the apprenticeship in order to retrain, fill knowledge gaps following a lateral job move, or increase their confidence in a new sector. Several described how the programme complements their existing sectoral knowledge, emphasising its role in bridging academic legitimacy with vocational identity.

This resonates with Bourdieu's notion of capital. In addition to the symbolic capital provided by the degree qualification itself, apprentices highlight an accumulation of social and cultural capital through workplace participation and engagement with professional networks. Learner reflections consistently frame the scheme's value as multi-dimensional, offering credentials, confidence and capital rather than simply a means of obtaining a degree: "I believe that a mix of studying and learning on the job is the best way to progress [...] rather than having a fancy certificate with no actual experience" (L18, Programme C). This reflects the principles of Lave and Wenger's (1991) situated learning theory, which argues that meaningful learning occurs through observation, participation and contribution within a community of practice.

For those without prior higher education experience, the scheme's value proposition was articulated in pragmatic terms. For instance, some participants described approaching a "ceiling" in their earning

potential, where further progression required a degree. However, the emphasis on workplace practice was often the deciding factor in choosing an apprenticeship over traditional options. Apprenticeships are viewed as less restrictive in terms of employment opportunities; the experiential focus is perceived as introducing a transferability that may open doors across disciplines in the future. This illustrates how apprenticeships complement a broad strategy for career resilience and mobility.

For others, the programme represents the fulfilment of a longstanding aspiration, offering academic validation and the opportunity to connect a lifetime of expertise with contemporary theory: "This is something I have been meaning to do for around 25 years" (L8, Programme A). At the other end of the scale, early career apprentices described the scheme as the most viable route into a new sector. Their accounts highlight the complexities of returning to higher education as an adult, pointing to the security of a funded degree and full-time employment as the deciding factor in "taking the plunge". Collectively, participant accounts frame graduate apprenticeships as a multi-dimensional model of education, the value of which lies in its capacity to meet a diverse range of needs.

8.8 Learner-Defined Value in Graduate Apprenticeships

Having addressed the five subsidiary questions, this section now turns to the final question at the centre of this study: how do learners define the value of graduate apprenticeships? Interpretation of the findings indicates that value is not a singular outcome, rather it is a layered and relational concept, continuously shaped by the interplay between stakeholder dynamics, curriculum design and learner agency. Furthermore, apprentices articulate value in a number of ways. While the academic credential is viewed as a source of legitimacy and progression, its value extends beyond this symbolic capital to the confidence and peer recognition afforded by truly transformative learning. Participant accounts also highlighted the potential for integrated work-based projects to deliver impact through personal and organisational development, illustrating that value is experienced individually and collectively.

The findings emphasise the inherent duality of these programmes, with apprentices simultaneously positioned as students and employees. The dual learning environment is a key strength of the model, creating opportunities to integrate theory and practice that full-time degrees simply cannot replicate. However, it also presents a number of challenges. When a programme's content and structure mirror full-time provision too closely, opportunities for meaningful learning can be constrained, which risks limiting the scheme's potential value to symbolic credentials. Apprentices are keen to avoid this, as they experience far greater value when curriculum content reflects their practice. This tension is also evident in assessment; prescriptive briefs may constrain agency and limit project capital, whereas

approaches that encourage independence and reflection enable apprentices to manage and measure their own development.

Beyond the benefits of enhancing practice and delivering organisational impact, apprentices associate work-based learning with future opportunities, viewing the experiential element of the programme as providing a competitive advantage over traditional graduates in the employment market. For those not seeking new career opportunities, it offers a means to build professional confidence and earn peer recognition, validating both the apprentice's experience and the legitimacy of the credential. The findings show that value emerges from the alignment of three crucial elements: authentic application of experiential learning, negotiated learning outcomes, and robust pedagogy that validates agency. It is not delivered unilaterally by universities or employers; rather, it is constructed by stakeholders in relation to their goals. In short, learners define the value of a graduate apprenticeship by its ability to deliver transformative learning that bridges the gap between aspirational and achievable.

8.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter has synthesised the research findings to address the questions at the centre of this study. First, the Tripartite Value Model was introduced in its preliminary form as an interpretive scaffold for the discussion that followed. The discussion established that value is not a singular outcome but is negotiated and constructed by apprentices in relation to their personal and professional goals. The findings also revealed that value is contingent on several elements pertaining to programme structure, curriculum design and delivery mode.

Next, chapter nine focuses on educational theory, synthesising the empirical findings with literature to illustrate how these structural components shape how value is experienced. The Tripartite Value Model is also revisited, with the final iteration presented in section 9.6. Following this, chapter ten delivers the conclusions of the study. Recommendations for universities, employers and policymakers are outlined, as well as implications for both policy and practice. The contribution to higher education scholarship is also considered, alongside limitations of the study. Lastly, areas for future research are identified before a final reflection is offered on the doctoral research process.

Chapter 9: Embedding Value in Graduate Apprenticeships

Engaging in practice, rather than being its object, may well be a condition for the effectiveness of learning.

– Lave and Wenger (1991)

9.1 Problem Statement

Graduate apprenticeships are framed as practice-based and collaborative, but this study finds that the extent of this is contingent on a programme's structural design. Despite being described as "uncharted territory" by Skills Development Scotland (2016a) at their launch, the positioning of the scheme within universities has ultimately led to them facing the same resource pressures that shape undergraduate provision across the sector. As a result, apprenticeship curricula and assessment are often aligned to full-time degree programmes, favouring efficiency over authentic practice. As established in chapter eight, apprentices derive value from meaningful integration of theory and practice, opportunities for which are limited without tailored curriculum content.

The tripartite relationship is arguably the scheme's unique selling point, yet it currently represents a structural weakness in the model. Each stakeholder brings distinct strengths and limitations, which underscores the complementary nature of the partnership and the need for robust communication to realise its value. Employers can dictate the focus of work-based learning but may lack the pedagogical expertise or workload capacity to support it effectively. Universities are responsible for academic quality but navigate institutional pressures that can restrict personalisation. Apprentices contribute a multitude of motivations and experiential insights, yet their agency is often constrained by employer and university expectations. The findings also show that a misalignment of these dynamics risks the delivery of symbolic value rather than transformative learning. This chapter therefore highlights the role of collaboration in mitigating these limitations and achieving meaningful outcomes.

Addressing these issues requires intentional pedagogy that looks beyond adapting traditional degrees to honour the distinctive nature of apprenticeship learning. Through an exploration of key literature, supported by insights from this study, the discussion illustrates how programme value is maximised through intentional and relational curriculum design. Section 9.6 then revisits the Tripartite Value Model, expanding it to reflect the core dimensions required for coherent apprenticeship design. The final model offers both a conceptual lens for understanding how value is constructed and a practical framework to guide the design and delivery of graduate apprenticeships.

9.2 Negotiating the Curriculum

9.2.1 Industry-Academia Collaboration

Though cooperation between universities and industry has been accelerating since the early twentieth century (Soysal and Baltaru, 2021), the graduate apprenticeship model extends this collaboration to an unprecedented extent. Unlike placements or internships that aim to complement learning in full-time degrees, apprenticeship programmes are designed around the needs of the labour market, and the tripartite agreement sees employers embedded as internal stakeholders. Given the many sectoral pressures that shape undergraduate provision (Palfreyman and Tapper, 2014), introducing employer oversight adds a further layer of complexity. As Dillard, Sisco and Collins (2024) highlight, work-based programmes present distinct power dynamics, arguing that employers often dictate what knowledge and experiences are considered valuable. While their study focuses on how this dynamic perpetuates social inequities, their observations around curriculum influence offer a useful point of contrast with this study. Rather than influencing apprenticeship curricula, the findings suggest that employers are more likely to exert control over how and when apprentices engage with learning activities, such as limiting protected study time or access to workplace support.

In fact, despite graduate apprenticeships carrying an explicit expectation of collaborative design (Skills Development Scotland, 2016b), staff accounts indicate that employer input is uneven, generally taking place retrospectively rather than during the design process. There is evidence of resource efficiencies shaping every programme structure to varying extents, and those most closely aligned with full-time provision have the least scope for meaningful stakeholder input. This is exemplified by Programme C, which shares teaching activities with the equivalent full-time degree. Although industry partners were recently surveyed for input on curriculum content, this took place several years after the programme was established, indicating that this consultation was a corrective measure rather than a foundational principle of co-design. Apprentices also reported a disconnect between academic content and their practice, reinforcing the inference that employer needs were not embedded in the programme as a matter of course. These accounts suggest that curriculum design remains largely university-led and is shaped by institutional constraints as much as pedagogical intention.

Beyond curricula, the findings also challenge broader assumptions in literature and policy discourse, which often present collaboration as being of equal benefit to the entire tripartite structure (Garnett, 2005; Crawford-Lee and Moorwood, 2019; Lester, 2020; Emms *et al.*, 2021). In this framing, employers reap the benefits of upskilled staff at no (direct) cost, universities demonstrate their responsiveness to economic policy agendas, and apprentices have the opportunity to earn while they learn. Stated in

such plain terms, the model appears to offer a win-win-win scenario. However, despite both industry and academia having a vested interest in developing effective work-based learning, Roodhouse and Mumford (2010) suggest that collaborative efforts often fall short in practice due to the absence of a "common language". The findings reflect this disconnect, as participants reported that employers and mentors often misunderstand the aims or demands of the programme, the apprentice's job, or their role in supporting the learning journey. Staff also described how mentors frequently failed to engage with information sessions, even when asynchronous. In this case, though, the findings point to time constraints rather than a lack of commonality between industry and academia. This is also in keeping with Brockmann, Clarke and Winch's (2010) observation that employers tend to prioritise immediate business needs over the qualification, often viewing the learning elements of work-based learning as a "hindrance" to effective practice. This pattern illustrates how a misalignment of priorities can limit opportunities for communication, ultimately eroding the collaborative potential of the partnership.

In practice, the "employer-led" nature of apprenticeships largely refers to industry consultation by the apprenticeship advisory group (Figure 2.1, p.22) during framework development. Collaboration should not end there, though; ongoing communication is required between employer, university and learner to ensure a coherent delivery that maximises value for all (Garnett and Reynier, 2025). Yet the OECD (2022) reports that apprenticeships in Scotland attract notably low levels of employer engagement compared to countries that either incentivise or mandate strong involvement. The report notes that Scotland is "underperforming relative to leading apprenticeship countries" and describes employer participation as "fragmented and inconsistent", which reflects the findings of this study. Moreover, even when mentors display initial enthusiasm, staff and learner accounts suggested that support often dwindles, leaving apprentices to navigate their work-based project independently.

Norman, Lambert and Partridge (2025) illustrate the importance of communication through the Police Constable degree apprenticeship. The authors report the programme as successfully delivered, with conceptual knowledge translated into practice through effective workplace-educator collaboration. Yet, according to their own findings, apprentices felt that support was poorly articulated and, as the programme progressed, a significant number reported declining confidence in their ability to perform their jobs. This highlights a disconnect between stakeholder perceptions of value and raises questions around how the success of apprenticeship delivery is measured. While Norman, Lambert and Partridge praised the communication between the academic and industry stakeholders, the misalignment in their findings underscores the importance of effective communication in generating tripartite value.

This is echoed by the present study, which identifies a correlation between engagement with support mechanisms and overall learning experience.

Productive collaboration does not rest solely on employer engagement, however; commitment from universities is equally important in ensuring educational value. Given that (i) apprenticeship delivery is expensive, (ii) government funding does not account for their resource-intensive nature, and (iii) broader SFC funding has stagnated across post-92s, there is a risk of reduced institutional commitment due to a poor return on investment. This would likely manifest as cost-cutting measures and a more transactional approach to participation in the scheme (Rowe, Moss and Moore, 2018; Jackson, 2025). These pressures were acknowledged by staff participants in this study, noting how limited resources influenced programme design and constrained the number of workplace visits by academic mentors. Some accounts indicated a level of resistance to institutional pressures: "As long as we continue to have employer support for the study day, I'll continue to keep the model of delivery the same" (S5, Programme B). This suggests that staff buy-in may mitigate the risk of transactional participation.

Ultimately, collaboration is a strength and a challenge of the graduate apprenticeship model. Drawing on Etzkowitz and Dzisah's (2008) triple helix model of university-industry-government cooperation, stakeholder contributions should be made through distinct but complementary roles. This means each party "staying in their lane": employers facilitating engagement with academic activities, universities emphasising curricular integrity over employer demands, and the government committing adequate funding to support the delivery of high-quality provision.

9.2.2 Agency and Ownership

Curriculum design occupies a contested space in higher education. Bovill and Woolmer (2019) argue that curriculum is simultaneously framed as content, process, student experience and collaborative practice, each of which informs how learners are positioned in relation to pedagogy. This is particularly pronounced in graduate apprenticeships; universities design programmes according to their priorities, employers want responsiveness to organisational needs, and apprentices seek learning that reflects their practice. Curriculum ownership is therefore fragmented, with each claim carrying implications for its perceived value. This pattern was evident in the findings, particularly in cases where programme content mirrored full-time provision. A number of learners from Programmes A, C and D described curricula as overly broad and insufficiently tailored for apprentices, with L7 (Programme A) noting that modules felt like they were designed for traditional undergraduate students and "forced to fit the GA cohort".

The tripartite structure offers the opportunity to harmonise curriculum ownership in apprenticeships. However, as the previous section demonstrated, this must be understood as meaningful co-creation rather than mere compliance. Ferrández-Berrueco, Kekäle and Devins (2016) propose a framework for effective work-based learning, which rests on three pillars: participating organisations, programme structure, and people involved. The authors stress that the quality of work-based learning relies on ongoing and productive interaction between these elements, which the findings suggest is a structural weakness across the case study university's apprenticeship provision. Learner accounts reflect Lester and Bravenboer's (2020) observation that apprenticeship programmes are often designed to appeal to a broad sector, resulting in limited relevance to individual practice. This implies minimal employer involvement in curriculum design at the case study university and supports Lester and Bravenboer's assertion that in the absence of collaboration, programmes will default to mainstream content.

Ferrández-Berrueco, Kekäle and Devins cite the inspiration for their framework as Garnett's (2005) conceptualisation of higher education apprenticeships, in which he describes how curricula should be a tripartite negotiation. His definition also emphasises "significant" learning outcomes for apprentices through integrated workplace projects, the pedagogical implications of which are explored in section 9.4.1. Garnett's foregrounding of apprentice value in programme design also raises questions of how learners navigate agency and identity construction in practice. Occupying an employee-student role underscores their distinct position in higher education, with identity construction further complicated by the academic-vocational divide described in the literature review. Brockmann and Laurie (2016) frame qualifications as socially constructed frameworks imbued with a cultural hierarchy that favours academic pathways over vocational. This places apprentices in a unique position in which they must construct their identities as legitimate university students while enrolled in programmes perceived as second tier, even by the academics tasked with teaching them (Basit *et al*, 2015).

Although the findings revealed some discomfort around the word *apprenticeship* amongst the cohort, this did not contribute to a sense of isolation or exclusion from the wider student community. Rather, apprentices opted not to socialise outside of the group: "We didn't really mix with anybody in the uni. [...] We didn't really mingle with the other students but I wouldn't say I've felt like an outsider" (L1, Programme A). This suggests that their learner identities were primarily shaped within the apprentice cohort, reinforcing the distinctiveness of their role within the university.

In sum, the academic legitimacy of graduate apprenticeships depends on the negotiation of significant learning outcomes that offer tripartite value. Nottingham (2019) identifies independent study and

critical reflection as key sources of value for apprentices – an observation mirrored by this study, which finds that value is intrinsically linked to self-directed enquiry and the authentic application of learning. Such outcomes should be facilitated by curricula that encourage agency, validate vocationalism, and accurately reflect their tripartite ownership.

9.2.3 Relational Teaching and Co-Creation

Relational pedagogy is a learning and teaching approach that centres relationships, emphasising the importance of meaningful teacher-student engagement in educational value. By reframing students as active partners in their learning journey, relational pedagogy challenges traditional approaches to knowledge transmission. Bovill, Cook-Sather and Felten's (2011) conceptualisation of co-creation goes beyond consultation, advocating for learners as partners in shaping curricula and pedagogy. Effective partnership in this context relies on what Fielding (2001) calls "radical collegiality", an inclusive and dialogic practice wherein teachers and learners share responsibility for transformative learning.

At the case study university, only Programme B appears to embed such dialogue in its delivery. Across the other three programmes, staff expressed their willingness to negotiate, but there is little evidence of significant divergence from full-time provision. As such, most of the apprentices in Programmes A, C and D reported that the modules were not relevant to their practice. Fielding's perspective on shared responsibility is echoed by Bovill (2020b), who emphasises the importance of reciprocity and respect in curriculum design. Teaching practices should therefore consider the lived realities of apprentices. By inviting dialogue about how best to integrate learning into their individual contexts, educators both validate learners' agency and reinforce their equal status in the tripartite structure. In contrast, the opposite experience was reported in this study, with L9 (Programme D) saying they feel "penalised" by lecturers if their workplace context does not align with areas of the curriculum.

Relational teaching approaches are described by Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild (2024) as "pedagogy of mattering", which is exemplified by the introduction of dedicated academic mentors in Programme A. Participants L1 and L2 had experienced the previous model, in which engagement was infrequent and less consistent. Programme A staff consistently emphasised a relational approach to mentorship in the new model, which was supported by L1 and L2; both indicated that having a dedicated mentor who was responsive to their needs made them feel valued and supported. Programme A apprentices reported notably greater satisfaction with their academic mentor compared to other programmes of a similar size, which suggests that relational pedagogy may be more effective when embedded as a programme-wide commitment rather than an approach adopted by staff on an individual basis.

The benefits of programme-wide adoption extend beyond mentorship. Bovill (2020b) suggests that engaging an entire cohort in co-creation can contribute to a sense of belonging, which White (2023) argues plays a central role in sustaining apprentices' motivation to engage with their programme. Fostering belonging in an apprenticeship can be challenging due to the 80/20 delivery model, which Dziallas *et al.* (2021) find can lead to feelings of isolation from the wider university community. Whole-class co-creation can also be used to establish an apprenticeship cohort as a social learning system, which, according to Wenger (2000), fosters a sense of belonging through three modes of participation: engagement, imagination and alignment. Engagement is the most prominent mode in this context, described by Wenger as "doing things together, talking [and] producing artifacts". From this system emerge communities of practice, which were identified as beneficial by apprentices in this study.

Learners highlighted the value experienced through peer relationships and how they compensated for shortcomings in formal support. Despite being entitled to workplace support, L1 (Programme A) implied that asking their mentor for help would be bothersome: "He's got a busy job himself so I don't really like taking up his time". From this, it can be inferred that learners often know what support or accommodations they require to succeed but may be reluctant to voice this due to a perceived power imbalance in the tripartite structure. Intentionally embedding whole-class co-creation can combat this by establishing a relational space that affirms apprentices' agency and invites them to articulate their needs.

Ultimately, relational pedagogy offers a means to counteract the sectoral tensions explored in chapter three. When educational value is threatened by external forces, relational approaches reiterate the importance of meaningful dialogue and shared responsibility in transformative learning design. Bovill (2020a) highlights how co-creation can reframe teaching as something done *with* learners rather than done *to* them. The author also emphasises the role of negotiation, a principle this thesis identifies as central to maximising value in graduate apprenticeships.

9.3 Principles of Adult Education

To advance the chapter's discussion of apprenticeship pedagogy, this section introduces three key theories of adult learning: andragogy, heutagogy and academagogy. Each approach offers a different insight into learner agency, curriculum relevance and the role of effective support networks, all of which featured prominently in apprentice accounts. By exploring these theories, the chapter provides a more nuanced interpretation of how programme design facilitates or constrains meaningful learning within graduate apprenticeships.

9.3.1 Andragogy

The word *pedagogy* is embedded in learning design at all levels and while it is typically used to describe structured learning activities centred around teacher instruction (Newfield, 2025), this Ancient Greek word translates to *leading children*. In contrast, andragogy is specifically a theory of adult learning. Developed in the 1970s by Malcolm Knowles, andragogy emphasises the relevance and applicability of knowledge to a learner's immediate needs (Knowles, 1980). The central aim is to acquire the skills of self-directed learning, described by Knowles as "learning how to learn".

Knowles, Holton and Swanson (2005, p. 64) posit that adult education is most effective when the learner understands the relevance to their own context. Brown, Collins and Duguid's (1989) concept of situated cognition expands upon this, arguing that conceptual tools are context-dependent and their meaning is "a product of negotiation within a culture and of practice in authentic activity". They also explicitly state that "appropriate use is not simply a function of the abstract concept alone". This aligns with the findings, as apprentices consistently highlighted the value of learning that reflected their practice. Programme B's bespoke curriculum was unanimously described as highly relevant by learners, who attributed this to sustained motivation and enhanced confidence. In contrast, the more prescriptive approach taken in Programmes C and D meant that apprentices experienced a disconnect, which limited opportunities for authentic integration of theory and practice: "It feels as though the module is trying to force our work to adapt to the module content when, in my opinion, the module should complement our work-based learning. [...] We shouldn't be made to feel bad, guilty or left behind if our work isn't directly tying up with what is being asked of us in class" (L9, Programme D).

However, andragogy has faced intense scrutiny. Hartree (1984) characterises the theory as reductive and Knowles' assumptions as "shaky". This is supported by Tennant (1986), who argues that the theory makes assumptions about adult learning based on a mischaracterisation of how children learn. More recently, Wozniak (2020) highlights limitations in andragogy's assumptions about adult learners. She

notes that empirical research frequently contradicts the idea that adults are inherently self-motivated, citing studies that identify varying levels of regulation, persistence and readiness for self-direction. Despite these negative views, the tenth edition of *The Adult Learner* was published in 2025, pointing to the continued relevance of Knowles' work. Indeed, Henschke (2011) defends andragogy, dismissing criticism as "hollow pleas" due to a lack of conceptual understanding.

Overall, andragogy presents a useful starting point for guiding adult learning, and the core principles would serve graduate apprenticeship design well. By engaging in tripartite co-creation rather than drawing on full-time provision, universities can refine apprenticeship curricula to ensure relevance. Andragogy's emphasis on "learning how to learn" also reflects the aim for apprentices to undertake increasingly complex self-directed projects as they develop. However, success in this respect requires work-based modules to grant greater autonomy, as the findings illustrate how prescriptive briefs limit apprentices' ability to meaningfully apply their learning in context.

9.3.2 Heutagogy

Building on andragogy's aims of self-directed learning, heutagogy focuses on self-determined learning, wherein the learner dictates both what and how they learn (Agonács *et al.*, 2020). This theory disrupts traditional teacher-student roles by centring learner needs and positioning the teacher peripherally. Though not specifically directed at adults, the core principles of heutagogy require high levels of focus, independence and intrinsic motivation, meaning the approach is well-suited to adult learners (Canning and Callan, 2010; Mann *et al.*, 2017; Moore, 2020).

A heutagogical approach allows the learner to build their own curriculum. While such autonomy is likely to increase motivation by aligning learning with personal goals and interests, it also carries risks. Barnett (1997, p. 108) warns that, without adequate structure, independent learning can result in narrow or superficial engagement with a topic. Agonács *et al.* (2020) also caution that self-determined learning requires a specific blend of characteristics. In their study of a massive open online course (MOOC), less than 5% of participants displayed the self-efficacy and motivation required for successful self-determined learning. Although highly contextual, the findings highlight limitations around a broad application of heutagogy in learning activities. There are also a number of practical barriers to learner-directed curricula and assessment in higher education, such as satisfying accreditation requirements (Moore, 2020).

Despite these challenges, an argument can be made for a more heutagogical approach to graduate apprenticeships. Currently, their design often reflects university and industry needs, which dictate what is learned and when. This is evident in the findings, as apprentices highlighted a misalignment between academic and workplace calendars. One learner indicated that their programme's value was constrained by the running order of its modules, which were out of sync with their needs: "Most of the content isn't that relevant to the work we are carrying out – or would have been more relevant at a different point within the course" (L12, Programme D). This extends to delivery mode, particularly in programmes taught online. Multiple staff accounts described employers as the main beneficiaries of online delivery due to the lack of tangible impact on day-to-day operations, and learner reflections support this; a significant number of Programme A apprentices described an erosion of weekly study time and expressed a desire for more in-person interaction.

As noted earlier in the chapter, learner agency can be encouraged through the co-creation of flexible timetables that reflect individual apprentice needs. Learners demonstrated a strong capacity for self-direction when managing workplace projects and so greater flexibility around module and assessment timelines could redistribute scheduling pressure points. Overall, the findings suggest that apprentices would benefit from self-determined learning but structural elements of programme delivery currently limit their autonomy. While there are practical constraints to the wholesale integration of heutagogy, the approach highlights the benefits of a more learner-centric apprenticeship design.

9.3.3 Academagogy

Academagogy offers a balanced theory of adult learning design, integrating elements of pedagogy, andragogy and heutagogy. Academagogy does not promote teacher-led or learner-led education as a rule; rather, it acknowledges that a programme of learning may require dynamic engagement with all three approaches. McAuliffe and Winter (2014) describe the approach as a "buffet" for educational design, allowing teachers to select the approaches best suited to a curriculum. Using a comparative case study, the authors demonstrate improved academic outcomes and student satisfaction following the adoption of heutagogical principles. In particular, learner participants in their study derived value from collaboratively shaping course delivery. However, potential barriers to adoption are highlighted. They acknowledge the resource-intensive nature of this approach, which may reduce its appeal for graduate apprenticeships as they are already more resource-intensive than full-time degrees (Jackson, 2025). The authors also explain that educators must take on a facilitative role, which they recognise may be a source of tension for some. This reflects Samarji and Hooley's (2015) theory of an ontological

and epistemological continuum. The adoption of academagogy may be met with resistance due to a disconnect between its epistemology and the educator's ontological view of their role.

McAuliffe and Winter's integrative view is supported by Newfield (2025), who argues that effective education draws on the strengths of multiple approaches. He explains that academagogy's blend of pedagogy, andragogy and heutagogy supports a transition from dependent to independent learning, which is a core aim of graduate apprenticeships. The findings of this study also underscore the need for a balanced design – a dynamic which is present in the work-based learning modules of Programme A. S2 described how dedicated mentorship offers apprentices a relational safety net as they develop toward self-direction: "When you join the programme, you're really quite needy but as you get more experience, it dips". This is also evident in Programme B's delivery mode, which reduces face-to-face interaction with each year. This was praised by apprentices, who noted that the structure mirrors their increasing independence and promotes self-direction. In contrast, many Programme C and D learners value face-to-face teaching, due to both its compatibility with their personal learning styles and the access it affords to academic staff. Furthermore, while learners appreciate Programme A's approach to mentorship, the majority would prefer more face-to-face engagement within the wider curriculum. This highlights that some learners require more pedagogical scaffolding than others, reinforcing the argument for personalised and relational design.

In sum, academagogy offers a pragmatic framework for apprenticeships, allowing a dynamic response to learners' contexts with minimal impact on university and employer needs. Of the three approaches discussed in this section, academagogy provides the most effective balance of tripartite demands.

9.4 Apprenticeship Pedagogy

9.4.1 Work-Applied Learning

Chapter two provided the rationale for describing graduate apprenticeships as work-based learning. Based on the findings, this section extends the scope of this using Abraham's (2012) concept of work-applied learning. While work-based learning is typically designed to facilitate the development of specific skills, a work-applied approach emphasises the collective dimensions of learning. With roots in action research and action learning, it focuses on integrated workplace projects as a means of stimulating both individual and organisational transformation. Abraham's view of learning as a catalyst for wider change reinforces the potential for graduate apprenticeships to generate tangible value through their immersion in a workplace setting. The benefits of integrated projects as an assessment method are considered in section 9.5.3.

Abraham posits an iterative cycle of observation, reflection, planning and action that echoes Kolb's (1984) experiential learning model. However, these steps are situated within the specific context of organisational change, as seen in Figure 9.1.

Figure 9.1: The work-applied learning cycle

Source: adapted from Abraham (2012, p. 5)

Chapter eight introduced Garnett's (2005) notion of project capital, which the author positions as a central tenet of apprenticeships in higher education. This complements the principles of work-applied learning, with both framing workplace projects as key mechanisms for individual and organisational development. Together, they underscore the pedagogical distinctiveness of graduate apprenticeships within the higher education landscape, as well as their capacity for transformation, which extends beyond the credential itself.

Self-determined workplace projects were consistently identified as a source of value by participants in this study. The findings demonstrate that meaningful application of learning through such projects can generate significant project capital, particularly when compared to more prescriptive approaches. Apprentice accounts described how self-determined projects enabled them to showcase academic and professional development, enhancing their social and cultural capital with superiors: "They were so impressed. [...] That academic knowledge has just opened up a lot of opportunities for me at work because I think I'm taken a bit more seriously" (L2, Programme A).

9.4.2 Expansive and Restrictive Learning Environments

Drawing inspiration from Lave and Wenger's (1991) situated learning theory, Fuller and Unwin's (2003, 2004) framework for apprenticeship design proposes an expansive-restrictive continuum. The authors emphasise participation as central to apprenticeship design and highlight that employer engagement often dictates the quality of participation. They argue that this shapes both apprentices' development and the construction of learner identity.

Expansive learning environments provide three core elements:

1. Engagement in workplace and non-workplace communities of practice
2. A multi-dimensional acquisition of expertise through applied practice
3. Access to related qualifications

Additionally, expansive learning environments demonstrate a commitment to off-the-job training. In contrast, restrictive learning environments often limit meaningful participation through narrow tasks, competence-based outcomes and the prioritisation of immediate organisational needs over long-term development.

The findings of this study show a clear correlation between a programme's structure and its position on the expansive-restrictive continuum. Programme B apprentices described engaging in meaningful participation, where they were supported by engaged mentors, entrusted with greater responsibility, and encouraged to undertake new tasks: "My current module has allowed me to carry out a project which involves introducing materials to support [client] wellbeing" (L14). Participants also reported notable increases in confidence and professional identity, with L15 describing the programme as a "game-changer" for them.

In contrast, apprentices in programmes closely aligned with full-time provision often described more restrictive experiences. In Programme A, this manifested as a loss of protected study time, which was exacerbated by its online delivery mode. In cases where employers displayed reluctance to facilitate on-campus activities, they made the learning environment more restrictive by limiting apprentices' participation in non-workplace communities of practice. On the other hand, Programmes C and D limited meaningful participation in workplace communities of practice. Work-based project topics are set by the university and described by L9 (Programme D) as "very broad and general". Participants described how this limits opportunities for authentic application of learning and expressed frustration that this was reflected in their grades. These accounts highlight the extent to which programme structure shapes value by either emphasising or constraining authentic integration, reinforcing Fuller and Unwin's argument that meaningful participation is central to the quality of apprenticeships.

9.5 Designing Effective Apprenticeships

9.5.1 Learner Motivation

Learner motivation plays a key role in shaping the value of a degree programme. This extends beyond the initial reasons for enrolment to the factors that sustain a learner's engagement for the duration of a programme (White, 2023). While acknowledging that this is an oversimplification of a complex phenomenon, motivation in this instance is understood to be driven by intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Ryan and Deci, 2000). In graduate apprenticeships, these dimensions often intersect due to their delivery across a dual learning environment.

Early exploration of the scheme identified career aspirations and financial security as key motivators for enrolment. In a comparative study of apprentices and full-time students, Smith *et al.* (2018) found that both cohorts were motivated to succeed academically by the prospect of securing well-paid jobs. However, apprentices' motivations were tempered by the pressure of meeting employer expectations while undertaking a degree, highlighting the challenge of sustaining motivation under competing demands.

From a widening access perspective, Harrison and Waller (2018) observe that university entrants from non-traditional routes often experience a misalignment of their desired and probable futures. They argue that these individuals often hold high aspirations but their expectation of achieving these goals is constrained by socio-economic factors. Given the number of mature graduate apprentices accepted through RPL (Hughes and Saieva, 2019), it can be suggested that many will be motivated by a desire to better align their aspirations and expectations. Findings from Dziallas *et al.* (2021) support this; they indicate that many participants of their study viewed the programme as a second chance at a career that had previously felt inaccessible. They report that motivation was sustained by the curriculum's relevance to career aspirations and the opportunity to immediately apply learning in practice. The same patterns are evident in this study. The majority of participants pointed to career progression, financial security and future-proofing employability as motivators for enrolment. However, in line with the findings of Dziallas *et al.*, a number of mature learners framed the programme as opening the door to a career that was previously inaccessible due to financial barriers. The findings also suggest that motivation is sustained when academic content feels relevant, allowing apprentices to enhance their practice in real time: "The more I study and learn, the more I want to succeed" (L15, Programme B).

Garnett and Reynier (2025) conducted interviews with degree apprentices and the motivations they report mirror those of participants in this study. Additionally, apprentices and employers in their study

identified the relevance of workplace projects as playing a central role in programme value. They also sustained apprentices' motivation through tangible outputs, such as financial impact for the business. Employers described their motivation in terms of staff retention and succession planning, highlighting an intrinsic-extrinsic intersection of organisational priorities with personal goals.

White (2023) frames motivation in apprenticeships as socially embedded, shaped by organisational culture and collective meaning-making. He also adds further nuance by drawing a distinction between motivation and persistence, identifying the latter as a key contributor to poor retention rates. White's thesis demonstrates how authentic engagement in the workplace encourages persistence, while poor integration and inadequate support can erode it. This further supports Fuller and Unwin's argument of participation as dictating apprenticeship quality.

9.5.2 Self-Directed Learning

Self-directed learning plays a key role in adult education, with Peno (2024) framing it as both a process and an attribute. As the latter, she describes this as a proactive approach to knowledge creation driven by intrinsic motivation and curiosity. The process, on the other hand, involves identifying learning objectives, scheduling academic activities and monitoring progress against a target. This method of learning is not new; self-direction is a central aim of andragogy and is often a prominent feature in apprenticeships. Spencer, Parr and Clark (2022) suggest that, when implemented effectively, the apprenticeship model contains all of the necessary components to support increasing self-direction as the learner progresses. However, there is a long-held assumption that adult learners are inherently curious and self-motivated (Knowles, 1980), which Keller and Raemy (2025) argue is not always the case. In their experience, adults in vocational programmes often express a preference for traditional instruction methods and resist attempts to implement self-directed approaches.

Although many apprentices in this study expressed a preference for more traditional instruction, such as face-to-face lectures, the findings nonetheless support Peno's observation of self-motivation. Staff described how apprentices are more likely than full-time students to take initiative in organising their studies, including seeking clarity around assessment deadlines. While S3 acknowledged that this may be "an age and confidence thing", staff largely attributed this diligence to competing time pressures. The same initiative was also evident in learner accounts. As discussed in the previous chapter, a group of apprentices proactively overcame a shortfall in workplace support by establishing a virtual study group to motivate each other through assessments. Additionally, while learners appreciate face-to-face teaching for the access it affords to lecturers, those in online programmes are quick to seek out

the help they need: "I'm quite a confident person, without being arrogant or a know all, and [...] when it comes to asking questions, seeking advice, contributing to workshops, or on campus, or engaging via [the VLE] – I don't hold back" (L8, Programme A).

These accounts suggest that the graduate apprenticeship model *does* contain all of the components needed for self-directed learning, but these components only function effectively when intentionally scaffolded. In the example of the study group, the apprentices demonstrated curiosity and motivation, but these were directed toward filling gaps in formal support rather than guided learning. In this case, self-direction emerged as a coping mechanism rather than an intentional element of learning design. This highlights the need for a pedagogical safety net, embedded without a presumption of motivation or readiness for independent enquiry. This should be understood as scaffolded autonomy; apprentices are encouraged to steer their own development (Skills Development Scotland, 2018) but their agency must be bolstered through intentional curriculum design and responsive support.

9.5.3 Integrative Assessment

Generally speaking, graduate apprenticeships follow the modular pattern described in chapter three. Standalone work-based learning modules sit at the centre of their curricula and are supplemented by additional classes from the disciplinary area to provide breadth of study. In some cases, including three of the programmes observed in this study, these supplementary classes are the conventional modules delivered as part of a full-time degree.

Hordern (2017) argues that the curricula and pedagogy underpinning degree-level apprenticeships offer programme graduates a significant degree of future-proofing due to the type and transferability of knowledge gained. However, the elements of the curriculum that Hordern identifies as offering an employability "guarantee" are likely to be conventional modules that mirror full-time offerings. This creates a tension: while the work-based modules offer contextual assessments and targeted academic mentorship, apprentices are subject to standard summative assessment in their other classes (Nabi *et al.*, 2025) and, as staff participants confirmed, often without additional guidance. Richardson (2015) argues that summative assessment is inappropriate for adults returning to education or for assessing deep learning, both of which are central to apprenticeships. Yorke (2011) critiques summative grading as "quasi-measurement", noting that its narrow criteria struggle to capture complex achievement. These views also support Lester and Costley's (2010) argument for work-based learning to be viewed as a transdisciplinary field, separate from traditional academic practices.

Recent literature presents a range of alternatives better suited to apprenticeships. Dean *et al.* (2024) demonstrate the benefits of capability frameworks and portfolios in facilitating and assessing self-directed learning. They highlight portfolios as encouraging deeper engagement by shifting the focus from high-stakes summative assessment to long-term capability development. This approach aligns assessment more closely with the constructivist principles underpinning apprenticeship learning. This is reinforced by Spencer, Parr and Clark (2022), who illustrate how portfolio assessment promotes self-management and captures richer evidence of workplace development than summative methods. Although the authors note that this approach is highly resource-intensive due to its individualised nature, their findings underscore the importance of assessment methods that validate apprentices' experience. Nabi *et al.* (2025) report similar findings in a graduate apprenticeship context, arguing that longitudinal portfolios and reflective exercises provide stronger evidence of learner development in the later stages of a programme.

Garnett (2005, p.119) suggests that degree-level apprenticeships can forgo conventional modules in favour of stakeholder-negotiated curricula, though this thesis has presented a number of key financial, structural and systemic constraints which make this unrealistic in practice. However, Spencer, Parr and Clark (2022) demonstrate how outcomes can be personalised using negotiated learning contracts, offering a reasonable middle ground between Garnett's approach and current provision. The merits of self-determined projects are also underscored by learners in this study: "Because it's something I'm doing already [...] it doesn't feel like an extra thing that I have to do" (L2, Programme A). Graduate apprenticeships are inherently integrative due to their dual delivery environment and assessment methods should reflect this, both to safeguard their transformative potential and to maximise learner value.

9.5.4 Embedding Scaffolded Autonomy

A central aim of graduate apprenticeships is to produce increasingly self-directed learners who can contribute to workplace needs with confidence. Yet, as this chapter has established, self-direction must be intentionally developed rather than assumed. The findings demonstrate strong initiative from apprentices when they are motivated, driving them to seek out whatever support is necessary for participation. Conversely, their capacity for self-direction is limited when academic and workplace expectations are misaligned.

Section 9.5.2 proposed that apprentices be guided toward independent learning through scaffolded autonomy – a concept which is understood as a developmental trajectory. Drawing on andragogy's

aim of "learning how to learn" and the heutagogical principle of self-determination (Knowles, 1980; Agonács *et al.*, 2020), this approach positions learner autonomy as something that must be cultivated through structured opportunities for negotiation and reflection. This pattern is evident in the findings, as staff described how apprentices become less reliant on academic mentors as their confidence increases. In addition, Programme B learners appreciate that face-to-face contact is gradually reduced, mirroring their growing independence. This illustrates how autonomy is strengthened when learners are empowered to take ownership of their development within an intentional and robust pedagogical framework. It also aligns with Barnett's (1997, p. 111) recommendation that autonomy be developed through supported knowledge construction, which helps learners to avoid forming a partial or overly simplistic understanding.

However, autonomy is also dictated by the structural conditions of a programme. As demonstrated in section 9.2, apprentice agency is often limited within the tripartite structure, constrained by employer demands or rigid curriculum design. Embedding scaffolded autonomy therefore requires universities to design programmes that allow apprentices to negotiate aspects of their learning while retaining academic depth and coherence. This echoes Bovill's (2020a) argument for co-creation to validate learner agency and reframe teaching as collaborative rather than imposed.

Scaffolded autonomy also requires a reframing of formal support mechanisms. Rather than viewing mentorship in terms of interactions mandated by the framework, the findings indicate that it should be ongoing, relational and responsive to make learners feel valued and supported. This is particularly important in programmes delivered online, where opportunities for informal interactions with staff are limited. When embedded intentionally, these practices create a pedagogical safety net for learners in their transition to independence. The findings also show that engaged academic mentors play a crucial role in supporting apprentices to identify and achieve goals, which is key to value construction.

Finally, these practices must extend to assessment. As the findings highlight, value is diminished when assessment limits meaningful application of learning, while an integrative or longitudinal approach provides apprentices with structured freedom to negotiate outputs. This also aligns with the principles of work-applied learning, which enables development to be evidenced through tangible organisational impact. As well as validating experience, this encourages apprentices to take responsibility for the direction of their learning journey, reinforcing the development of autonomous practice.

9.6 Revisiting the Tripartite Value Model

The emergent model introduced in chapter eight offered a preliminary framework for interpreting the dynamics within the tripartite relationship. Subsequent analysis of the findings then revealed the dimensions that shape how apprentices define and experience value. Figure 9.2 therefore presents the Tripartite Value Model in its final form.

Figure 9.2: The Tripartite Value Model

The model is presented as an equilateral triangle to emphasise equality and reciprocity between the three stakeholders. The apprentice is situated at the apex, supported by the university and employer at the base. Although each role holds equal importance within the structure, this configuration was selected to visually reinforce that a successful learning journey is contingent on a strong foundation of academic and workplace support. The sides are connected by the three elements identified in this study as vital to programme value: experiential learning, negotiated learning outcomes and relational pedagogy. Drawing inspiration from the cumulative nature of Bloom's (1956) taxonomy, the layered centre illustrates how these elements interact to enable the authentic application of relevant knowledge. By highlighting the interdependence of these elements, the model captures the multi-dimensional nature of value within the tripartite structure.

Furthermore, as well as providing a conceptual lens for understanding how value is constructed, it represents a practical framework to guide apprenticeship design. Finally, the model serves as a visual conclusion to this chapter, which asserts that value emerges from the alignment of programme design, stakeholder expectations, and the conditions that shape meaningful participation.

Chapter 10: Conclusions and Recommendations

Without a good understanding of the value of degree apprenticeships to all stakeholders [...] there is a high risk of policy failure.

– Lester and Bravenboer (2020)

10.1 Conclusions

This study set out to understand how learners define and articulate value in graduate apprenticeships. Following an in-depth exploration of how programmes are designed, delivered and experienced at the case study university, it presents five key conclusions:

Value is not a singular outcome. It also cannot be delivered unilaterally by universities or employers. Instead, it is a layered and relational concept that is negotiated by stakeholders across the tripartite relationship. Although delivery, content and assessment can vary enormously between programmes, value is maximised if the structure emphasises the application of knowledge in an authentic context, negotiated outcomes, and a robust pedagogical scaffolding.

Apprentices look beyond credentials for value. Both the degree and the academic legitimacy it offers matter, but not more so than the learning process itself. To apprentices, increased confidence in their professional abilities, gaining the respect of their superiors and future-proofing their skillset is equally important – all of which is achieved through authentic learning rather than merely gaining a credential.

The academic-professional positioning is a strength and a challenge. The dual delivery environment is distinctive and offers the opportunity to apply learning in a way that is impossible to replicate in a traditional degree. This distinctiveness should therefore be reflected in the curriculum, as mirroring full-time provision risks programme value becoming symbolic.

Agency and reflection are key. Apprentices derive greater value from a programme when it empowers them to reflect on their practice and steer their development through self-determined learning.

Value is contingent and contextual. It relies on a transformative learning process, which hinges on stakeholder collaboration, effective communication and the alignment of structural conditions. Value ultimately emerges from learning that bridges the gap between what apprentices aspire to and what they believe they can achieve.

10.2 Contribution to Scholarship and Practice

The title of this section, like so many areas of graduate apprenticeships, reflects a duality. In this case, the findings of the study offer both a contribution to scholarly discourse and practical insights for universities, employers, and policymakers.

The principal strength of this study lies in its apprentice-centric perspective, which foregrounds the learner voice and complements existing graduate apprenticeship scholarship, which largely focused on employer and institutional perspectives in the years following the scheme's launch. Although the learner experience features more prominently in recent literature, this exploration of how apprentices define value and achievement adds a new perspective to the discourse.

Additionally, it contributes by extending debates around apprenticeship education. In chapter eight, this thesis called for a re-evaluation of how academic success is defined in apprenticeships. This is an area recently considered by Smith, Henderson and Mapletoft (2023), though their study approached it from a perspective of industry engagement and recruitment. They recommend adopting employer-focused outcomes that measure apprenticeship success in terms of business impact and, although this study complements the authors' argument for a new measure of success, it shifts the focus to learner-negotiated outcomes that emphasise agency, ownership and relational value.

However, the most significant contribution of this thesis is the introduction of the Tripartite Value Model. The model synthesises the structural, relational and pedagogical dimensions of apprenticeship programmes that shape the overall learning experience. As well as providing a practical framework for structural design and curriculum delivery, the model also highlights how value is negotiated within the tripartite structure. By reframing value as a shared construct, it reinforces the principle that value in graduate apprenticeships is not owned by any single stakeholder.

In empirical terms, this thesis provides one of the first detailed accounts of how apprentices define the value of graduate apprenticeships. It highlights that learners find value beyond the credential in a way that was astutely described by participant S2: "The degree is almost a by-product". As such, this study illustrates how apprentices find value in the learning itself, which enables them to connect academic study with professional development.

It also demonstrates the role that programme design plays in value construction. When the content or delivery mirrors a traditional degree structure, apprentices perceive a disconnect. If they cannot

see their practice reflected in learning activities, it limits authentic participation and diminishes their value. The nuance captured through the lived experiences of apprentices contributes to the empirical understanding of how transformative learning is enabled or constrained by apprenticeship design.

10.3 Recommendations

The findings highlighted several areas where graduate apprenticeship provision can be strengthened at a practical and a policy level. This section therefore offers ten recommendations for universities, employers and policymakers.

10.3.1 For Universities

Recommendation 1: Programmes should be designed with the aim of being expansive experiences that guide learners from peripheral to mainstream workplace participation. Using Fuller and Unwin's (2003, 2004) continuum, section 9.4.2 illustrates how expansive apprenticeships are intentionally scaffolded to support apprentices as they translate theory into practice. Educators should therefore emphasise a relational pedagogy that validates the apprentice's position as a developing professional rather than a passive recipient of information.

Recommendation 2: Where possible, programme delivery should emphasise in-person interaction to enforce a separation of work and study. While online delivery offers benefits in terms of flexibility and accessibility (highlighted in section 3.5.3), the findings show that apprentices identify significant value in regular opportunities to engage with academic staff in person. In addition, on-campus activities should facilitate dialogue and collaboration rather than defaulting to a lecture format.

Recommendation 3: As discussed in section 8.5.1, communities of practice should be embedded as a peer support mechanism. Such communities quickly become student-led and require minimal staff oversight once established (Spencer, Parr and Clark, 2022), providing a sustainable support network to complement the tripartite mentorship. While not a replacement for formal mentorship, they may help to mitigate the impact of inconsistent employer engagement.

Recommendation 4: Universities should aim to deliver consistent academic mentorship by specifying expectations of staff engagement, clearly signposting communication channels to apprentices, and ensuring that gaps in support are addressed promptly. As described in section 8.3.1, shortfalls are more likely to appear in programmes with larger intakes and where their structure mirrors full-time provision, and so particular attention must be paid to ensure a consistent approach across the cohort.

10.3.2 For Employers

Recommendation 5: Workplace support plays a vital role in shaping the learner experience (Chadwick, Dimungu Hewage and Hazzam, 2025) but participant accounts presented in sections 6.7.2 and 7.3.2 reveal inconsistent levels of engagement. In addition to assigning each apprentice a suitable mentor, employers must facilitate regular contact. If a gap in support occurs due to workload constraints or staff turnover, a replacement must be identified promptly. In addition, tripartite meetings between the apprentice and their workplace and academic mentors are vital to ensure wraparound support.

Recommendation 6: Section 8.4.1 describes employer reluctance to honour protected study time and so the thesis echoes Lester and Bravenboer's (2020) warning around organisational priorities eroding this core facet of the graduate apprenticeship model. When agreeing to support their staff through an apprenticeship, employers also commit to honouring the mandated study time, which equates to 20% of the working week. Skills Development Scotland (apprenticeships.scot, no date a) specifies that any time spent on academic activities is considered "time spent at work" and an apprentice's duties should be reconfigured to reflect this, even if teaching is delivered online or outside of working hours.

10.3.3 For Policymakers

Recommendation 7: In line with the recommendation of the International Labour Organization (2020) highlighted in section 8.3.1, policymakers should consider introducing standardised pedagogic training for potential workplace mentors, drawing on international apprenticeship models such as the German dual system. Implementing such training would be unfeasible at an institutional level due to resource constraints but national policy could incentivise employer participation to ensure that apprentices receive consistent workplace support.

Recommendation 8: Policymakers should consider changing the name of graduate apprenticeships. Smith, Henderson and Mapletoft (2023) argue that changing the name would help to distinguish the distinctive value proposition of degree-level apprenticeships, increasing their appeal and encouraging parity of esteem. These observations are supported by this study's findings; both apprentices (section 6.7.3) and staff (section 7.7.4) described how the word *apprenticeship* can be a bone of contention – particularly with mature learners, as it can feel patronising to experienced professionals. Changing the terminology would distance the scheme from misperceptions about apprenticeships and better reflect the character of work-based higher education.

Recommendation 9: Similarly, rhetoric that aligns the scheme with either trade apprenticeships or full-time undergraduate degrees should be avoided (Smith, Henderson and Mapletoft, 2023). This recommendation complements the argument made in chapter three against framing apprenticeships as supernumerary to full-time degrees. While this is key to achieving parity of esteem, section 8.6.1 underscores how overcorrecting and aligning programme structures too closely risks undermining the inherent value of work-based learning. Maintaining a distance between provisions would safeguard the distinctiveness and value proposition of apprenticeships.

Recommendation 10: In section 7.7.3, staff explained how the apprentice nomination process risks perpetuating existing inequalities and so it is recommended that policymakers reconsider recruitment practices. Employers will understandably prioritise organisational benefit and so recruitment should be approached as a collaborative process between policymakers, universities and industry. Targeted outreach or sectoral guidance could help align organisational interests with broader equity goals.

10.4 Implications for Policy and Practice

10.4.1 Policy Implications

At a policy level, the study underscores the limitations of current success measures, which are narrow and overlook contextual factors such as the diverse learner profiles in graduate apprenticeships. The study also illustrates the meaningful impact for both apprentices and their employers, even without completing Honours. By failing to consider these broader achievements, the current characterisation of "achievers" and "leavers" presents a misleading dichotomy that obscures the real-world value of apprenticeships. Policymakers should therefore adopt a more holistic measure of programme success, recognising partial awards and career progression as legitimate achievements. Not only would such measures address wider calls to re-evaluate success in vocational higher education, but they would also better reflect the lived experiences of apprentices and improve retention narratives.

Policy also plays a crucial role in safeguarding equity within the scheme. Employer-led recruitment practices risk inadvertently reproducing existing inequality and undermining their framing as a vehicle for widening access. If apprenticeships are to challenge stratification across the sector, intervention is required to encourage a more inclusive approach to apprentice nomination.

Finally, policy discourse must move beyond rhetorical parity of esteem and actively promote graduate apprenticeships as distinct and impactful qualifications in their own right. The scheme is widely held in lower regard than traditional degrees (UCAS, 2021) and so vocational higher education must be

reframed to dispel cultural misperceptions. By evidencing the contextual value proposition of graduate apprenticeships, policy can take the first steps toward this.

10.4.2 Practice Implications

For universities, the findings demonstrate the importance of developing tailored curricula that reflect apprentices' needs. Although apprenticeships and full-time degrees deliver equal credentials, they are distinct in both structure and mission. An apprenticeship should not mirror the delivery, content or assessment of its full-time equivalent; doing so reduces opportunities for authentic learning in practice and, ultimately, limits the value for apprentices and employers.

In the case of employers, they must recognise their role in shaping apprentices' learning experiences. Poor engagement with the university and gaps in mentorship undermine the tripartite relationship, which is a core element of the apprenticeship model.

10.5 Limitations of the Study

Alongside the strengths outlined in section 10.2, the study also presents a number of limitations. As discussed in chapter five, this study was conducted from the perspective of a mature learner turned insider researcher, which presented a number of challenges (Fleming, 2018). All reasonable steps were taken to mitigate these through active reflexivity, but the influence of the researcher's presence is acknowledged as unavoidable.

In terms of research design, a single case study approach can limit the generalisability of the findings. Although they are likely to transfer between universities operating within similar contexts (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p. 124), wholesale application across the sector is neither expected nor intended. In addition, employer accounts were not pursued due to time and resource constraints, and so industry recommendations are based on secondary data. Participant self-selection may also skew the findings toward positive perspectives, raising the question of potential underrepresentation of less favourable experiences.

The extended timeframe of staff interviews presents another limitation, as early accounts may not reflect subsequent developments. This was mitigated by a follow-up discussion with a Programme A academic to ensure that the current provision is not misrepresented in the findings. Incorporating a longitudinal element may have strengthened the study but this was infeasible due to time constraints.

Although the decision to observe multiple programmes sacrificed depth of understanding for breadth, this ultimately revealed critical points of comparison that shaped the core findings.

10.6 Areas for Further Research

This study provides important insights into how apprentices define and experience value in graduate apprenticeships. It also highlights a number of areas that would benefit from further exploration. First and foremost, the transferability of the findings would be tested beyond a single case study through comparative research across multiple contexts. Examining the experiences of apprentices in different universities or countries may provide insight into how structural or cultural factors shape learners' definition of value.

A longitudinal approach could also be adopted to gain further insight into how value is constructed. The central finding of this study builds upon Harrison and Waller's (2018) notion of desired and probable futures. In turn, following learner outcomes over a longer period of time could build on this study's findings by examining how perceptions of value and achievement evolve in relation to changes in the learner's professional or personal context. Looking beyond programme completion would also offer insight into how the benefits of apprenticeship learning (such as greater workplace confidence) are sustained long-term. This would complement the reflections in this study, which offer a snapshot of each participant's experience during their time as an apprentice.

Finally, the Tripartite Value Model's robustness and adaptability should be tested through application in multiple apprenticeship contexts. Additionally, the model may be strengthened by incorporating employer perceptions of programme value, which may also serve to address the subject of workplace mentorship, which is currently a structural weakness. Incorporating employers' conceptualisation of value and success would enhance the model's validity for tripartite application.

10.7 Final Reflections

Having spent several years examining the apprentice learning journey, the final chapter of this thesis provides an opportunity to reflect on my own.

Chapter five highlighted my position as an insider researcher. It also outlined my non-traditional route to higher education to explain my interest in graduate apprenticeships and how it undoubtedly shaped my early perceptions and expectations of the scheme. As a practitioner-researcher with thirteen years

of higher and further education experience, I am acutely aware of how institutional and sectoral pressures can create a disconnect between intention and implementation of new programmes. When curriculum drift occurs, it is almost always the result of funding or resource constraints rather than by design. Over the course of this study, I have identified areas of apprenticeship design that do not represent best practice in terms of learner outcomes but my insider knowledge tempered my critique. While I may not endorse a decision, I understand the rationale behind it.

This is also informed by my professional practice. Although I have taught in higher education, my perspective is rooted in instructional design and educational technology. I therefore approached the research questions from a viewpoint of how programmes are constructed to support learners rather than a classroom practitioner. It was also through this lens that I interpreted apprentices' accounts, noting how structure and curricula shaped their experiences and perceptions of value. Being embedded in the study made me more conscious of my multifaceted role (researcher, practitioner, non-traditional mature student) and the responsibility it holds.

Conducting the study has also had a profound impact on other areas of my professional life. Beyond the act of data collection itself, the content of participants' reflections challenged me to re-evaluate areas of my own practice. During my interview with S5 (Academic, Programme B), they highlighted the inaccessibility of some academic publications due to the language used:

We need to shift as academics. We need to shift the culture a bit more in higher education in terms of, if we want journal articles and literature to reach practitioners, we need to write it in an accessible form. If we don't, it will reach academics, it might reach policy holders, it might reach legislators, but it's not necessarily going to reach [practitioners]. So, if you want to reach those folks, you need to write it in a way that they find it accessible and useful in their practice.

This comment resonated with me, prompting critical reflection on my own writing. I internalised this observation and have since strived to write in a way that is direct and accessible. This reflects a broader ethos of challenging knowledge gatekeeping and ensuring that research is accessible to a more diverse audience.

These final thoughts address the personal impact of my learning journey. The description of my educational background in chapter five provided crucial context that informed how this study began. Coming full circle, it becomes relevant again as the study draws to an end. While writing this thesis, I found myself relating to a number of the apprentice participants, particularly those who reflected on their achievements in disbelief. Making connections between their thoughts and Harrison and Waller's

(2018) notion of desired and probable futures highlighted a disconnect between my own perceived selves. Mirroring the circumstances of many graduate apprentices, I left school without the standard university entry qualifications, yet I now find myself nearing the end of my PhD. In a moment of meta-reflexivity, I connected learner experience to theory, simultaneously answering this study's central research question and reducing the distance between my own desired and probable futures.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Indicative Interview Schedule (Learners)

1. Which programme are you enrolled in?
2. What year of the programme are you in?
3. Had you completed any further or higher education before this?
4. How long have you been in your role?
5. What made you want to apply for the apprenticeship?
6. Is your employer supportive?
7. Do you have a workplace mentor?
8. Has the university been supportive?
9. How have you identified your work-based learning projects?
10. What was your perception of apprenticeships before you started and has that changed?
11. What is your motivation/what do you hope to gain from the programme?
12. Have you taken a formal break at any point during your studies?
13. Do you feel that your job role has prepared you for the programme?
14. Do you feel that the academic content is relevant to your work?
15. Have you been able to apply your new knowledge to your role?

Appendix 2: Indicative Interview Schedule (Staff)

1. Please confirm who you are and what you teach.
2. How is the academic content selected for the programme?
3. How is the content delivered?
4. How do you emphasise the experiential element of the programme?
5. In your experience, what is the main motivation for apprentices?
6. In your view, what is the main motivation for employers?
7. In your experience, is there adequate practical support from employers?
8. How are apprentices assessed?
9. Do you feel that traditional summative assessment is beneficial in this context?
10. Have you noticed differences between apprentices and traditional undergraduates?
11. What has been your experience in terms of retention and interruption of study?
12. Do you think work-based learning has a place in higher education?
13. How involved is the university with recruitment/selection of apprentices?
14. What do you think the scheme needs to do in order to succeed long-term?
15. Given the freedom, what changes would you make to the programme?

Appendix 3: Questionnaire (Demographic Questions)

This is a copy of the questionnaire text from Microsoft Forms. Programme names have been removed.

This section of the questionnaire asks for background information about you, including your employment and education history. Your responses are anonymous but if you do not feel comfortable giving an answer, questions 3-9 offer a "prefer not to say" option.

The "prefer not to say" option is **not** offered on questions 1 and 2. This information is required to ensure that only responses from eligible participants are included in the data analysis. However, your anonymity is assured and you cannot be identified by providing this information.

Completion time: 5 minutes

Q1. What is your student status?

I am currently enrolled on a graduate apprenticeship programme

I have graduated from a graduate apprenticeship programme

I left a graduate apprenticeship programme before completion

Q2. What is/was your programme of study?

Programme A

Programme B

Programme C

Programme D

Q3. What is your age?

Under 18

18-24

25-34

35-44

45-54

55 or over

Prefer not to say

Q4. What is your gender?

Male

Female

Non-binary

Prefer not to say

Q5. When did you start the graduate apprenticeship?

2017

2018

2019

2020

2021

2022

2023

Prefer not to say

Q6. At which level of study did you enter the graduate apprenticeship?

Year 1 (SCQF 7)

Year 2 (SCQF 8)

Year 3 (SCQF 9)

Year 4 (SCQF 10)

Prefer not to say

Q7. What is your current year of study?

Year 1 (SCQF 7)

Year 2 (SCQF 8)

Year 3 (SCQF 9)

Year 4 (SCQF 10)

Prefer not to say

Q8. Before you joined the programme, what was the highest qualification you held?

No formal qualifications

Standard Grade, National 5, GCSE or equivalent

Higher, Advanced Higher, A-Level or equivalent

HNC/HND, BTEC, SVQ or equivalent

Undergraduate degree

Postgraduate degree

Prefer not to say

Q9. How long have you been with your current employer?

<1 year

1-2 years

2-3 years

3-4 years

4-5 years

5+ years

Prefer not to say

Appendix 4: Questionnaire (Open-Ended Questions)

This section asks you to discuss your experience as a Graduate Apprentice. There are four questions, each with space to type a response.

You will see a number of additional questions below each of the four main questions. These are examples or prompts, and it is not expected that you will respond to each of the individual examples provided.

Please include as much detail as possible in your answers; the information you provide about your experience as a Graduate Apprentice is pivotal to this study, and your time and participation are hugely appreciated.

Completion time: 10-15 minutes

Motivation

What inspired you to apply for the Graduate Apprenticeship programme, and what motivates you to complete the qualification?

Overall, what do you hope to gain by completing your degree? For example, taking a step toward achieving a career goal, or to satisfy a personal sense of achievement.

Learning

How do you feel about the education you are receiving through your programme at [university]?

Are the learning materials or events delivered online or face-to-face? Do you find the course content to be relevant to your work? Have you been able to apply your new knowledge to your role? Are you involved in identifying work-based projects as part of your studies? As an employee, do you feel that your time in the workplace has prepared you for your degree?

Assessment

How does the assessed components of the course relate to your professional role?

What format do the assessments take, e.g. essays, exams, practical observation? Does your course include work-based assessments? Do you feel the assessments allow you to accurately demonstrate your knowledge and experience?

Support

What is your experience of accessing support or mentorship as a Graduate Apprentice?

Do you have access to a dedicated tutor or mentor, both at university and in the workplace? Do you have regular meetings, and who attends those meetings? Reflect on the relationships you have developed with your tutor(s) or mentor(s) - do you feel able to speak up when you have a problem?

Appendix 5: Coding Template (Interviews)

		Codes	Themes
Interviewer			
Participant			
Interviewer			
Participant			
Interviewer			
Participant			

Appendix 6: Coding Template (Questionnaire)

Q1. Motivation			
ID	Response	Codes	Themes
L3			
L4			
L5			
L6			
L7			
L8			

Appendix 7: Project Information (Staff Information)

This is a copy of the text from the Microsoft Sway site. Details of the case study university have been redacted and links removed.

Researcher: Jessica Brennan

Supervisors: Dr Eilidh Kane and Dr James Riordan

Department: School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Who are you and what is the project?

My name is Jessica Brennan and I am a doctoral researcher in the School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland. For my PhD project, I am looking at the design and delivery of Graduate Apprenticeships at [university] and I would like to observe and interview staff involved in delivering these programmes.

Why do you want to talk to me?

I would like to speak with you because you are currently involved in delivering one or more Graduate Apprenticeship programme at [university].

What do I have to do?

If you agree to participate in this study, we will meet once and I will conduct an interview. During the interview we will discuss your thoughts, opinions and experience of the design, delivery and impact of the programme. The interview will last for approximately one hour. This can be arranged at a time and place most convenient to you, either via videoconferencing software (Teams or Zoom) or in person at a [university] campus. Please note, the interview will be recorded. The method of doing so (audio and video or audio only) will depend on whether our meeting is virtual or face-to-face.

Is it anonymous?

Following the interview, I will create a transcript of our conversation. The transcript will be anonymised and no identifying details will be used in the final dissertation. Excerpts or direct quotes from your interview may be included within the final research material but neither you or the programme will be identifiable from these. The transcript and video/audio recording will be stored securely in line with GDPR legislation, accessible only by me and my supervisors, and held for the duration of my research project.

Do I have to take part?

No, participation in this research is voluntary. If you choose to take part, you can decline to answer a question during the course of the interview and you retain the right to withdraw your consent at any time. If you withdraw from the study after your interview but before publication of the research, your data will be removed.

I am interested but I would like more information first.

If you would like more information or an informal conversation before committing to an interview, you can register your interest using this form [link removed] and I will get back to you via email as quickly as possible.

How can I contact you?

If you would like further information about my research, please email me: [removed]
Alternatively, my supervisors can be contacted at [removed] and [removed].

Appendix 8: Project Information (Learner Version – Interviews)

Researcher: Jessica Brennan

Supervisors: Dr Eilidh Kane and Dr James Riordan

Department: School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Who are you and what is the project?

My name is Jessica Brennan and I am a doctoral researcher in the School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland. For my PhD project, I am looking at Graduate Apprenticeships at [university] and I would like to interview apprentices enrolled on these programmes.

Why do you want to talk to me?

I would like to speak with you because you are currently enrolled on, or have recently graduated from, a Graduate Apprenticeship programme at [university].

What do I have to do?

If you agree to participate in this study, we will meet once and I will conduct an interview. During the interview we will discuss your thoughts, opinions and experience of your time on the programme. The interview will last for approximately one hour. This can be arranged at a time and place most convenient to you, either via videoconferencing software (Teams or Zoom) or in person at a [university] campus. Please note, the interview will be recorded. The method of doing so (audio and video or audio only) will depend on whether our meeting is virtual or face-to-face.

Is it anonymous?

Following the interview, I will create a transcript of our conversation. The transcript will be anonymised and no identifying details will be used in the final dissertation. Excerpts or direct quotes from your interview may be included within the final research material but neither you or the programme will be identifiable from these. The transcript and video/audio recording will be stored securely in line with GDPR legislation, accessible only by me and my supervisors, and held for the duration of my research project.

Do I have to take part?

No, participation in this research is voluntary. If you choose to take part, you can decline to answer a question during the course of the interview and you retain the right to withdraw your consent at any time. If you withdraw from the study after your interview but before publication of the research, your data will be removed.

How do I arrange an interview?

You can follow this link [removed] to book an appointment slot directly using my Microsoft Bookings page. It is linked to my calendar so my availability is updated in real time. The booking system will automatically create a Teams appointment but if you would prefer to meet in person or using Zoom, please let me know at [email].

I am interested but I would like more information first.

If you would like more information or an informal conversation before committing to an interview, you can register your interest using this form [removed] and I will get back to you via email as quickly as possible.

How can I contact you?

If you would like further information about my research, please email me: [removed]
Alternatively, my supervisors can be contacted at [removed] and [removed].

Appendix 9: Project Information (Learner Version – Questionnaire)

Researcher: Jessica Brennan

Supervisors: Dr Eilidh Kane and Dr James Riordan

Department: School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Who are you and what is the project?

My name is Jessica Brennan and I am a doctoral researcher in the School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland. For my PhD project, I am looking at the design and delivery of Graduate Apprenticeships at [university].

Why do you want to talk to me?

You have been given the details of my study because you are currently enrolled on, or have recently graduated from, a Graduate Apprenticeship programme at [university].

What do I have to do?

To participate in the study, you are invited to complete a two-part questionnaire.

The first section of the questionnaire asks, in general terms, about your background and programme of study. There are nine questions and answers are selected from a drop-down. This section should take no more than five minutes to complete. The second section contains four questions, which ask more specifically about your experience as a Graduate Apprentice at [university]. Space is provided to type an answer in your own words and you are encouraged to include as much detail as possible.

Is it anonymous?

Yes, all responses are completely anonymous. You can access the questionnaire without signing in to your [university] account, so your email address is not recorded, and none of the questions ask you for identifying information such as your name or student number. I will be able to read all responses but I will have no way of knowing by whom they were submitted. If a participant accidentally includes identifying information, this will be removed from their response and not included in the final study.

Do I have to take part?

No, participation in this research is voluntary. If you choose to take part, you are in control of how much detail you provide. While anonymity is assured, I appreciate that there are certain details someone may not wish to disclose and so there is a "prefer not to say" option for every question in part one of the survey. By completing the survey, you are consenting to your information being used in the final research project. This may be in the form of statistics generated from all responses as a whole, or as direct quotes from your free-form answers. However, the final project will not include any information that can be linked to one participant. Please note, you will not be able to withdraw consent for your participation after you have submitted your response on Microsoft Forms. Your response will not be linked to your name, student number, or email address and so it will not be possible to identify and delete it. Please therefore give careful consideration before participating. If you have any questions before completing the survey, my contact details can be found below.

How do I access the questionnaire?

You can complete the questionnaire here: [removed]

How can I contact you?

If you would like further information about my research, please email me: [removed]

Alternatively, my supervisors can be contacted at [removed] and [removed].

Appendix 10: Interview Consent Form

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

1. I confirm that I have read the project statement and I have been given the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I consent to this interview being recorded and my responses being used for the purpose of this research study. I understand that my responses will be anonymised and I will not be identifiable in the final research output.
3. I understand that I am free to decline to answer any question or terminate the interview for any reason. My participation in the study is voluntary and I may withdraw consent at any time.
4. I understand that my data will be securely stored in accordance with GDPR legislation for the duration of the study.
5. I understand that my signature is not a waiver of any legal rights.

1. I have read and understood the above statements and I wish to participate in the research project. *

Yes, I consent.

No, I DO NOT consent.

2. Full Name (in lieu of physical signature): *

Enter your answer

3. email address: *

Enter your answer

Submit